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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)* is a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). It is a peer-reviewed journal published both offline and in hardcopy, focusing on cutting-edge research and practical solutions in business management and related disciplines.

Scope

GRJBM invites research articles from a broad spectrum of topics, including but not limited to organizational behavior, strategic management, financial management, human resource management, entrepreneurship, and the impact of technology on business processes.

Vision

To be a global leader in fostering scholarly debates and disseminating high-quality, timely, and impactful research on contemporary business management issues.

Mission

To continuously provide an intellectually stimulating platform for academics, practitioners, and policymakers to share insights, drive innovation, and contribute to the advancement of business management practices worldwide.

EDITORIAL PREFACE

We are pleased to present Volume 3, Issue 1 of the *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)*, a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). As a trusted platform for the dissemination of impactful research, GRJBM continues to deliver high-quality, peer-reviewed articles that address contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of business management.

This issue features an engaging collection of articles that examine critical themes such as retirement planning, insurance operations on manufacturing, market risk, and the role of board traits on earnings. Together, these studies reflect the journal's commitment to advancing knowledge and informing practice within Nigeria and beyond.

We are deeply grateful to our contributors for their insightful work and to our reviewers and editorial team for their dedication to maintaining the high standards of GRJBM. The unwavering support of AMSSRN has also been instrumental in the continued success of this journal.

We trust that the articles in this issue will stimulate meaningful discussions and provide actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

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RETIREMENT PLANNING AND POST RETIREMENT WELL-BEING

**RETIREMENT PLANNING AND POST RETIREMENT WELL-BEING OF CIVIL
SERVANTS IN AKWA IBOM STATE**

By

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This study was conducted to investigate the influence of retirement planning on post-retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The objectives of the study were to evaluate the influence of investment, savings, and spending on post-retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology: Survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of 7011 retirees from which a sample size of 379 was determined using Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination. Data were collected using questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to 379 respondents out of which 315 were filled and returned. Data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation, and simple percentage, while simple and multiple linear regression analyses were used to test the null hypotheses.

Research Findings: Findings revealed that investment, savings and spending have significant positive influence on post-retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, with t – value of 33.757, 31.677, 34.055 and f – value of 178.9-20, 1003.434, 1129.712 with a corresponding p - value of .000, .000 and .000 respectively ($P < 0.05$). Thus, it was concluded that investment savings, and spending have significant positive influence on post-retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations: Therefore, it is recommended that the retirees should invest in assets and financial ventures to supplement their pension income. Also, they should plan and set up new businesses to ensure steady in-flow of income and enhance their post-retirement well-being. The retirees should be encouraged to participate in the contributory pension scheme to ensure that they conserve adequate savings that will help to sustain their post-retirement well-being. They should moderate spending patterns according to their needs at different stages of lives to improve the post-retirement well-being.

Key Words: Retirement Planning, Savings, Investment, Spending an Post Retirement Well-being.

RETIREMENT PLANNING AND POST RETIREMENT WELL-BEING

Introduction

In Nigeria, the public service allows for a statutory age of retirement at 60 years or 35 years of unbroken service prior to retirement. However, some employees retire on their own volition aside statutory provision. On retirement, retirees are entitled to retirement benefits known as pension and gratuity. This is a form of reward to workers for their services to the state and or the nation for the development of its economy. However, the pension and gratuity received by workers hardly can sustain them hence, the need for personal savings and investments. Retirement terminates the employment of employees, and in some cases it introduces changes like social and psychological effect that may be quite traumatic to retirees. Such changes are likely due to stoppage of regular financial payment from paid employment and may mount pressure on some staff into falsifying their true age and career records so as to stay longer in service and avoid retirement. Again, today's workers in both private and public sectors in Nigeria perceive retirement as most intractable problem (Abdullahi, 2012 and Denga ,2017).

Retirement can be seen as that phase of life when serving employees have to disengage from active employment. According to Cole (2011), employee retirement signals when the employee had reached the terminal point of a working career. Onoyase (2013) explained retirement as an experience allowing the employees to leave their work places permanently and so begin preparation towards their twilight days. The employees' retirement stage comes with some identified challenges such as ill-health and stress. These challenges could bring about discomfort or endanger retirees' lives especially in case of inadequate planning which would not make for a proper transition from one's work to retirement upon leaving the service.

The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of retirement planning on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom state. The specific objective was to: evaluate the influence of investment, savings and spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The research question was raised to guide the study: To what extent has investment, savings and spending influenced post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State:Therefore to evaluate the symbiotic linkage between investment, savings , spending and post retirement well-being, the research hypothesis was formulated in null form to guide the study: There is no significant influence of investment, savings and spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom state. Savings has no significant influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review Retirement Planning

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Retirement Planning is the term used in describing the plan embarked upon in order to prepare serving employees towards their exit from service. It emphasizes all the activities and programme as well as strategies designed to make the lives of retiring employees meaningful in their retirement. Sule (2016) advised that the right time to start planning employee retirement ideally should be once the employee assumes duties.

Savings

But early empirical studies (Cagan, 1965; Katona, 1965) which discovered that pensions did raise savings rather than reducing it instigated researchers to look at other factors that may have accounted for their findings. A possible explanation for the positive impact of pensions on savings from the studies of Cagan (1965) and Katona (1965) is that pension plans and schemes raise the awareness for retirement needs, and provides an avenue where individuals can accumulate adequate retirement income (Munnell, 1976). Feldstein (1974) suggested that workers who are covered by pension schemes tend to retire earlier compared to those without pension coverage. This may encourage them to accumulate wealth so as to finance their early retirement.

Spending

The spending on consumption goods and services constitutes an essential part of post retirement well-being and is, moreover, considered to be a hallmark of the prevailing lifestyle in Nigeria. The well-being of private household is ultimately defined by the level, kind and quality of their consumption of goods and services, even if it may turn out to be debatable whether or not further growth in material wealth seems to be desirable considering the level of property which the retirees have achieved. As it seems rather obvious to consider spending as potential drivers of retirement well-being, even though some empirical research is lacking. However, there is ample evidence that spending can only be the source of retirement well-being if the resources needed by the retirees are available at their disposal. The absence of necessary financial means after retirement causes distress, discontent and absolute or relative deprivation (Sullivan, 2006).

Retirement Well-being

According to Young (2013), employees who plan well while in service are bound to experience retirement wellbeing. This implies that pre-retirement planning was linked with retirees' wellbeing. The argument presented here is that the would-be retirees who should be able to plan so as to have in their possession amount of resources that is enough to guarantee that they experience betterment in terms of their economic, physical, psychological, social and overall wellbeing in retirement. At the same time, those in retirement must necessarily provide for the

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amount of income that is enough and sustainable to guarantee they will be able to maintain the kind of lifestyle which boost a healthy life in various dimensions.

Theoretical Review

The theory was developed by Robert Atchley, in 1989, and the theory states that individuals seek continuity by linking things in the past with changes in the future. In the view of Atchley, continuity can be internal or external. The author described internal continuity as those aspects of a person's personality. These may include emotions, temperament, and experiences unique to him/her. On the other hand, external continuity comes from the individual environment; physical and social which include the roles each of us is involved in and the jobs we perform. The author added that friendships and phasing out of employment are examples of maintaining external continuity in old age. He explained that phasing out of employment means that there will be more time for family and friends and volunteer/personal pursuits in new work role either as a business man, part time or full time work. Also, external continuity allows retirees to adapt to changing environmental demands. Therefore, retirees should engage in meaningful roles that reflect what they like to do and what motivates them.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was used for the study. The use of the design involved selecting a sample from the population of retirees in Akwa Ibom State to study their characteristics to be able to make an informed judgment on the population.

The population of this study from 2016-2020 consisted of 7011 retirees who had served in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service as it was recorded from the office of the accountant general (OAG) (2020). The sample size was 379 which were determined through the use of Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination. The equation was given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population size

e = The acceptable sample error (0.05)

1 = Theoretical Constant

$$n = \frac{7011}{1+7011(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{7011}{1 + 17.5}$$

$$n = \frac{7011}{18.5}$$

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$n = 379$

The judgmental sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study. This enabled the researcher to elicit responses from the respondent conveniently without stress. Respondents were those retirees who were seen as strong and capable of supplying relevant information. These respondents were retirees who visited the Uyo Office of National Union of Pensioners and Accountant General Office on routine basis. The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents in their convenience without subjecting them to rigorous stress before responding to the questions. Data used for this study were obtained from primary sources. Primary sources of data collection were questionnaire which was administered on the respondents.

The research instrument used for this study was the questionnaire and it was divided into two parts. The first part was on personal information of respondents. Details required were gender, age, experience, qualification and when they retired from service. The section also asked the most important factor which affect retirement planning among civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The second part consists of the 4- point modified Likert -scale type questions which focused on the research variables, retirement planning and post retirement well-being. A 4- point modified rating scale was used in assessing the opinions of respondents. It consisted of 4 = strongly agree, the highest. This was followed by 3 = agree, then 2 = disagree, then 1 = strongly disagree.

The Cronbach Alpha reliability test was conducted to test the reliability of the research instrument as shown in Table 31. The test indicated an overall result of 0.748.

Table 3.1: Reliability Table

Variable	Number of Items	(Cronbach Alpha)
Investment	5	0.864
Savings	5	0.713
Spending	5	0.776
Post retirement well being	5	0.639
Overall	20	0.748

Source: Field Survey Data (2021)

To ensure that the instrument was valid for use in the study, the research instrument was presented to the supervisor and other experts who made useful suggestions that led to its modification. Hence, the instrument had face validity which is essential for the study. Data for

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the study were collected through questionnaire administration. Collection of data lasted for thirteen weeks. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents during visiting hours. This was done by the researcher and two research assistants. Data collected from the study were presented using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and simple percentage while the null hypotheses were tested through simple regression and multiple regression analysis. Both methods were applied in an attempt to establish the influence of the independent variable (retirement planning) on the dependent variable (post retirement wellbeing) in the study. The significance level was set at 0.05 confidence level

Conceptual Specification of Model

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Retirement Planning

Post Retirement Wellbeing

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Model

Source: Researcher's compilation (2021)

3.10 Empirical Specification of mode

$$PRW = f(I, S, G) \quad 1$$

$$PRW = X_0 + X_1I_1 + X_2S_2 + X_3G_3 + e \quad 2$$

Where:

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PRW	=	Post Retirement Well-being
X_0	=	Intercept
I	=	Investment
S	=	Savings
G	=	Spending
$X_1 - X_3$	=	Coefficient of the independent variable
e	=	Error term

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data Presentation

During the course of the research, three hundred and seventy nine (379) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to retirees from the Akwa Ibom State civil service, out of which, 315 copies were filled and returned. This number represents 95.4% response rate.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis I

Table 4.9: The Result of Linear Regression Analysis on Influence of Investment on Post Retirement Well-being of Civil Servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Durbin Watson
1	.982	.965	.965	1.407

a. Predictor (Constant), Investment

b. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Model Fit

Model	Sum of Squares	df	F	Sig.
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1 Regression	187.005	1	8618.367	.000 ^b
Residual	6.792	313		
Total	193.797	314		

a. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

b. Predictor: (Constant), Investment

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized	t	Sig.
			Coefficient Bata		
(Constant)	.112	.038		2.920	.004
Investment	.968	.010	.982	92.835	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Source: Researcher's Computation (2021)

The result in Table 4.9 indicates the influence of investment on Post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, with R²-value (coefficient of determination) of .965, F-value of 8618.365 and a corresponding P-value of .000. The result shown that investment accounted for 96.5% variation in predicting the dependent variable (post retirement well-being). Therefore, it can be affirmed that investment is effective in explaining post retirement well-being of civil servant in Akwa Ibom State. The result is supported by beta coefficient of .968 which implies that one unit increase in investment would leads to increase of 96.8% level of post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The F-value of 8618.367 shows that the model is fit with critical table value of 3.84 under the degree of freedom 1 and 313 confidence levels. The result further indicated the P-value of .000 is less than 0.05 (p<0.05) respectively, based on this result, it can therefore be affirmed that investment has significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of investment on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State was rejected and the alternative accepted, meaning that there is significant positive influence of investment on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

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Hypothesis II

Table 4.10: The Result of Linear Regression Analysis on Influence of Saving on Post Retirement Well-being of Civil servants Akwa Ibom State.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Durbin Watson
1	.930	.866	.865	.181

- a. Predictor (Constant), Savings
b. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Model Fit

Model	Sum of Squares	df	F	Sig.
Regression	167.788	1	2019.234	.000 ^b
Residual	526.009	313		
Total	193.797	314		

- a. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being
b. Predictor: (Constant), Savings

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficient Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.001	.060		16.684	.000
Savings	.756	.017	.930	44.936	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Source: Researcher's Computation (2021)

Table 4.10 reveals the simple linear regression, which indicates the influence of savings on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, with R²-value (coefficient of determination) of .866 and F-value of 2019.234 with P-value of .000 respectively. This shows that savings accounted for 86.6% change in post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

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The result is supported by Beta Coefficient of .756, meaning that one-unit increase of saving leads to 75.6% in the level of the well-being of retired civil servants. The F-value of, 2019.234 further shows that the model is fit in predicting the influence of independent variable on the dependent variables (post retirement well-being) with table value of 3.84 at the degree of freedom 1 and 313 confidence level. Therefore, since the P-value of .000 is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), it can be concluded that savings has significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the null hypotheses which stated that there is no significant influence of savinge on post retirement well-being of civil servants is rejected, meaning that there is significant positive influence of savings on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis III

Table 4.11 The Result of Linear Regression Analysis on Influence of Spending on Post Retirement Well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Durbin Watson
1	.931	.866	.866	.181

- a. Predictor (Constant), Spending
 b. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Model Fit

Model	Sum of Squares	df	F	Sig.
Regression	167.853	1	2025.026	.000 ^b
Residual	25.944	313		
Total	193.797	314		

- c. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being
 d. Predictor: (Constant), Spending

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficient Bata	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.030	.059		17.376	.000
spending	.749	.017	.931	45.000	.000

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a. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

The result in Table 4.11 a reveals the influence of spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, with R^2 -value (coefficient of determination) of .866 and F-value of 2025.026, with a corresponding P-value of .000. The result implied that spending accounted for 86.6% change in post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, spending is effective in explaining the post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. This is supported by Beta Coefficient of .749, meaning that one unit increase of spending leads to .74.9% increases in post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, since the p-value of .000 is lied below alpha value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), it can be affirmed based on this result that there is significant positive influence of spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. More so, the F-value of 2025.026 shown that the model is fit with t-value of 45.000 at the degree of freedom 1 and 313 and the table value of 3.84 with a corresponding p-value of .000 ($p < 0.05$) respectively. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that spending has no significant influence on post retirement well-being is rejected and the alternative accepted, meaning that spending has significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis IV

Table 4.12 The Result of Multiple Regression Analysis on the Joint Influence of Investment, Savings, and Spending on Post retirement Well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.985	.971	.971

a. Predictor (Constant.), Spending, Saving, Investment

b. Dependent Variable: Post Retirement Well-being

Model Fit

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig
Regression	188.188	3	3478.325	.000
Residual	5.609	311		
Total	193.797	314		

a. Dependent variable: post retirement well-being

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b. Predictors: (constant), spending, savings and investment

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Beta	Coefficients study error	Standardized coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	.174	.036		4.792	.000
Investment	-.710	.034	.721	21.103	.000
Saving	.110	.030	.121	3.616	.000
Spending	.136	.027	.157	5.035	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Post retirement well-being

The result in Table 4.12 indicates joint influence of investment, savings and spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, with a joint contribution of R – value (coefficients of determination) of .971, F–value of 3478.325 and t – value of 21.103, 3.616 and 5.035 with D – value of .000, .000 and .000 respectively. This implied that investment savings and spending jointly accounted for 97.1% variation in the dependent variable (post retirement well-being). The result further revealed that the three explanatory variables such as investment, savings and spending are effective in predicting post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

More so, the F- value of 3478.325 shown that the model is fit in explaining the criteria variable (that is, post retirement well-being). This result is supported by Beta coefficient of .710, .110 and .135 which implied that one-unit increase of investment, savings and spending lead to 71.0%, 11.0% and 13.5 % increase in the standard deviation of post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The result indicated that t – statistic of 21.103, 3.616 and 5.035 are statistical significant with that P – value of .000, .000 and .000 ($P < 0.05$) at the degrees of freedom of 1 and 313 with the table of 3.84 significance level. Thus, based on the results, it can therefore be concluded that the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant joint influence of investment, savings and spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State is rejected and the alternatives accepted, meaning that investment, savings and spending have significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State

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4.3.2: Discussion of the Findings

Investment has significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

The finding from the test of hypothesis one indicated that there is significant positive influence of investment on post retirement well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, and the research question revealed that investment is effective in predicting post retirement well-being of Civil servants who were retired in Akwa Ibom State, with R^2 – value of .000 respectively. This is supported by Mohamed (2014) who posited that investment has significant positive effect on economic growth among the labour union in Ethiopia, meaning that investment during the active work life of the retirees is a powerful tool that can help improve post retirement well-being of Civil servants in the state. The result is in agreement with the work of Oniye (2004) who opined that investment plan helps to make a proper decision on how best to invest individual money to realize the targeted goals of the family after retirement from active service. The author further stated that gratuity investment plan should not be over looked by any worker considering the fact that labour wage in Nigeria is far from being a living wage. Okechuku and Ugwu (2011) supported the finding by maintaining that the goal and investment option one chooses will go a long way to determine the success of such plan.

Savings has significant positive influence on post retirement well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State

The finding from the test of hypothesis two shown that there is significant positive influence of savings on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, and that savings is effective in explaining post retirement wellbeing of civil servants in Akwa state, with R^2 - value of – 762, f- value of 1003.434, t-value of 311.677 and a corresponding p-value of .000 respectively. This implies that savings has a predictive power to explain the link between savings and post retirement well-being of Civil servants. This result was supported by the work of Verma and Wilson (2005) who stated that savings has significant positive effect on economic growth. The result indicated that household savings and investment improved individual well- being both in the short run and long run effect. The result also correlates the work of Alan *et al* (2015) who maintained that the retirement planning involved long term savings affected by level of income, meaning that individuals investment level to a greater extent is dependent on savings levels, and also dependent on the level of individual income. The finding was supported by Alan *et al* (2015) who stated that employee active savings represent either Net Income which is after tax minus capital gain and then divided by current income themselves as net household earnings and

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income after taxes. This may be salaries and wages incomes, self employment earnings, government transfer payment and income from other resources that may come from savings and investment in the long run.

There is significant positive influence of spending on post retirement well-being on post retirement well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

The finding from the test of hypothesis three revealed that there is significant positive influence of spending on post retirement well-being of Civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, and the research question shows that spending is effective in predicting post retirement well-being with R^2 value of .787, t -value of 34.055 and F -value of 1129.712 with a corresponding P -value of .000 respectively. This implies that the interaction between spending and post retirement well-being is positively linked together, meaning that proper spending approach would help the retirees to live well even after leaving the active service. This result is supported by the work of Lingard (2015) who stated that spending has significant influence on individual household. The author maintained that there is possibility of running out of money before the death of the retirees hence the issue of longevity risk could be determined by the ability of the individual to continue in spending. The number of years in which the retiree lives may determine the quality of life enjoyed while in retirement. Some unforeseen need of family members may arise which may demand that the retiree must need to spend if he/she will continue to keep the family.

5.1 Summary of the Findings

The main focus of this study was to investigate the influence of retirement planning on post retirement wellbeing of civil servants in Akwa Ibom state. Therefore, the findings revealed that: There is significant and positive influence of investment on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, and that investment has the predictive power to explain post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Also, the finding of hypothesis two indicated that Savings has significant and positive influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. This implied that savings has the explanatory power to explain the symbiotic linkage between independent and the dependent variables. It further indicated that adequate savings influences the well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Consequently, the finding showed that Spending has a positive and significant influence on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. The coefficient of determination also revealed that the result is effective in explaining the relationship between spending and post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. In the same vein, the finding revealed that investment, savings and spending have significant and positive influence on post

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retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. This suggested that the three indicators have the explanatory power to predict the post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Conclusions

The study was developed to examine the influence of retirement planning on post retirement wellbeing of retirees in Akwa Ibom State. The objectives were to examine the influence of investment, savings and spending on post retirement well-being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, it was concluded on holding all other factors constant that investment, savings and spending have significant positive influence on post retirement well- being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State, and that effort should be tailored towards improving retirement planning to enhance post retirement well- being of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i The retirees should invest in assets and financial ventures to supplement their pension income. Also, they should plan and set up new businesses to ensure steady in-flow of income and enhance their post retirement well-being.
- ii The retirees should be encouraged to participate in the contributory pension scheme to ensure that they conserve adequate savings that will help to sustain their post retirement well-being.
- iii They should moderate spending patterns according to their needs at different stages of lives so as to improve their post retirement well-being.
- iv Managers of pension scheme should adopt the three indicators of retirement planning such as investment, savings and spending to ensure operational efficiency in the management of pension funds and programmes.

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IMPACT OF INSURANCE OPERATIONS ON MANUFACTURING SECTOR

IMPACT OF INSURANCE OPERATIONS ON MANUFACTURING SECTOR ACTIVITIES IN NIGERIA 1990-2022

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This study assessed the impact of insurance operations on manufacturing sector activities in Nigeria 1990-2022, Insurance basically provides financial guarantees to the insuring public. In addition to its traditional role of managing risk, insurance market development promote growth by allowing different risks to be managed more efficiently through promoting long term savings, encouraging the accumulation of capital, serving as a conduit pipe to channeling funds from policy holders to investment opportunities as well as mobilizing domestic savings into productive investment. This study examined the effect of insurance claims paid by insurance companies, total insurance penetration, insurance density rate and total insurance premium income on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

Methodology: The model's parameters were processed using the ordinary least square (OLS) regression model.

Research Findings: The result indicates that total insurance penetration, insurance density and total insurance premium income had positive and significant impact on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria, while insurance claims paid by insurance companies has negative but non-significant impact on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria and collectively, insurance operations have positive and significant impact on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

Recommendations: The study therefore recommends among others, that for the insurance industry in Nigeria to exert more positive effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria, government policies concerning insurance should focus more on attracting active low-income earners, micro or small scale manufacturers into the insurance market. This will increase penetration and density rate as well as the premium income. Insurance awareness and confidents must be established through payment of genuine claims and loss minimization methods established in manufacturing sector.

Keywords: Insurance Operations, Manufacturing Sector, Insurance Market Development

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1. 0 INTRODUCTION

Insurance is design to protect the financial well-being of an individual, companies or other entity in the case of unexpected loss. Insurance is a risk transfer mechanism where individual or commercial enterprise shifts some of its uncertainty embedded in everyday life, to the shoulders of another, in return for a certain amount of money called premium. It is essentially arrangement by which a party, called the 'insurer', promises to pay another party called the "Insured", a sum of money in the event of a loss occurring. The global positive impact of insurance cannot be overemphasized as it is essential for sustainable economic development and supportive of the poverty alleviation aspirations of many developing nations

Akinlo (2013) posit that insurance is the corner stone of modern day financial services. In the manufacturing sector all activities are carried out stage by stage and from the production of the products to the distribution of these products so it is almost impossible to prevent losses from occurring. Every manufacturer depends on the wealth of assets such as equipment, inventories and supplies to keep its business running also, the premises the company and manufacturers use for their productions as well as a warehouses for the storage of manufacturing companies go on with their finished products, manufacturer could be liable for the damages caused as a result of the consumption or usage of their product, they can also be liable for bodily injury or death to one of their employees as a result of production activities provided that the accident occurred at the place of work and also during working hours.

The combination of risk is unique to the manufacturing companies therefore each loss exposure needs different policies in other to get appropriate protection. Most manufacturer depend on people and equipment's to produce their goods ignoring the fact that they prone to unforeseen circumstances. Companies must work to prevent risk at every stage of their operation. From design and pre-fabrication to shipment of the final product, attention to detail and safety are of utmost importance. Companies must acknowledge the high demands they face, and implement risk control processes.

Obi (2010) stated that insurance is a means of protection from financial loss. It is a form of risk management primarily used to hedge against the risk of a contingent or uncertain loss. An entity which provides insurance is known as an insurer, an insurance company, an insurance carrier or an underwriter.

Capacity building has been promoted by the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM), Chartered Insurance Institute of Nigeria and some tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Regular

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conferences have been organized by various insurance market associations such as Nigerian Insurers' Association. A number of insurance laws and regulations have been enacted, amended and updated; the regulatory body has consistently championed innovations to deepen the activities of the industry through yearly directives and reorganization of her structure to ensure supervision and regulatory performance in line with the global best practices.

The Nigerian insurance industry has achieved a lot in its human capital development, while insurance penetration rate seems growing deeper every day. Many persons are taking insurance covers to protect their insurable interests, and with the current level of public awareness about insurance, insurance will soon become a household name in Nigeria. The challenge is that the older generation of Nigerians is more honest than the citizens of nowadays who are obviously more desperate to make money by hook or by crook (Adeda, 2014). However, the positive effects of financial development are tailored by the macro policies, laws, regulations, financial infrastructures and enforcement norms applied across countries and time.

It becomes apparent at this point to study the non-bank financial institutions with particular reference to the insurance industry with a view to ascertaining the extent to which the development of the insurance market has affected the productive sector of the Nigerian economy i.e. the manufacturing sector. This is necessary so as to make meaningful findings and advance useful recommendations that will aid firms in the manufacturing sector to build financial capacity towards a sustainable economic growth.

The importance of the insurance industry as an aspect of the financial system in growing the manufacturing sector in Nigeria has been obviously neglected over the years. Evidently, most studies have focused attention on the interaction between the non-bank financial institutions and economic growth (Akinlo, 2013; Mojekwu, Agwuegbo&Olowokudejo, 2011; Etale, 2019; Nwosa& Mustapha, 2018 etc.). However, recently, growing attention has shifted to the interaction between the banking financial intermediaries such as deposit money banks and its impact on the manufacturing sector. There appears to be little or non-existent up-to-date literature on the nexus between insurance market and the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. This problems call for serious attention and it is based on this premise that this study is being carried out.

The Nigerian government and the insurance industry have made attempts to promote insurance market development including the enactment of local content act, enforcement of compulsory insurance, circulating micro insurance guidelines and recapitalization exercises. The aim of these government interventions is to enhance insurance market penetration rate, increase insurance

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density and promote more premium income earned by the insurance industry. However, it appears that these the desired results seem not coming forth as the effect on the manufacturing sector still remains relatively unknown hence this study. The assured safety of live and property which enhance trade, transportation and capital lending in manufacturing sector are not heavily reliant on insurance services hence low insurance density, penetration, premium and poor claims settlement in manufacturing sector.

However, this study seeks to examine the impact of insurance market operations on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria 1990-2022. The broad objective of the study is to assess the impact of insurance operations on the growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study were, to: Assess the impact of insurance total claims on the growth of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Examine the impact of total insurance penetration on growth of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Investigate the impact of total insurance premium on growth of manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Insurance Premium and Manufacturing Sector

The insurance premium is the price a person pays for the insurance protection. It is the price payable by the insureds to the insurers for the financial guarantees. The amount of premium charged for an insurance cover is expected to make economic sense. In other words, it should be high enough to cover future claims on the pool of risks and expenses including commissions to the insurance intermediaries while still making a profit. It ought to be an amount the insured is willing to pay and must be substantially below the sum insured (Okonkwo, 2002; Okonkwo,2004). Irukwu (1990) defined insurance premium as the consideration which the insured pays to the insurer in return for the insurer's promise to pay the sum insured (or its equivalent) in the event of a loss or damage within the terms of the insurance contract. It, therefore, represents the monetary value paid by the insured for the financial guarantee accepted by the insurer. The insurance premium can be described as gross or net premium income.

Insurance Penetration Rate and the Manufacturing Sector

Penetration rate shows the level of development of insurance sector in a country. Penetration rate is measured as the ratio of premium underwritten in a particular year to the GDP. Insurance Penetration - refers to a product's sales volume relative to the sales volume of competing

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products. Within insurance, there is life insurance penetration which considers premiums from life insurance policies only as a percentage of GDP and non-life insurance penetration which considers premium from other than life insurance policies like auto insurance, health insurance, etc.

Insurance Industry and Claims Payment in the Manufacturing Sector

An insurance claim is a formal request to an insurance company asking for a payment based on the terms of the insurance policy. The insurance company reviews the claim for its validity and then pays out to the insured or requesting party (on behalf of the insured) once approved. The non-life insurance industry is witnessing shifting trends across policy administration, and claims—the two core functions in insurance. The claims process is the defining moment in a non-life insurance customer relationship. To retain and grow market share and improve customer acquisition and retention rates, insurers are focused on enhancing customers' claims experience (Bekeris, 2012).

Manufacturing Sector Growth

According to Daniel (2012), manufacturing sector growth is a measure of manufacturing output as share of a country's economy. Manufacturing is broadly defined as the "physical or chemical transformation of materials into new products," regardless of the process (by machines or by hand), location (factory or home), or sale method (wholesale or retail). The value added is the net output of the manufacturing sector, calculated after adding up all the outputs and subtracting the intermediate inputs. It is determined by the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) revision and calculated without deducting the depreciation of the fabricated assets, or the depletion and degradation of any natural resources. Manufacturing sector, as defined by the U.S. government, "comprises establishments components into new products," as well as those engaged in "assembling of component parts of manufactured products" for purposes other than construction.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Financial Intermediation Theory propounded by Schumpeter, 1911 and Mckinnon and Shaw, 1973

The theory is based on studies establishing the relationship that exists between financial intermediation and economic growth by Schumpeter (1934), Goldsmith (1969), McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973). Schumpeter (1911), a well-functioning financial sector is necessary to

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facilitate growth in the real sector which resultantly leads to economic growth. In other words, economic growth is reliant on how well the financial sector is deepened or developed. As the financial sector deepens, there is increase in the supply of financial services. The route through which financial deepening promotes economic growth is explained in the supply-leading hypothesis. The hypothesis is alternatively referred to as “finance-led growth hypothesis”.

The central argument underlying supply-leading hypothesis is that financial deepening is a determining cause of economic growth. It posits that optimal allocation of resources is an outcome of financial sector development (Hurlin and Venet, 2018). The supply-leading hypothesis suggests that causality flows from finance to economic growth with no feedback response from economic growth. A well-developed financial sector is a pre-condition for economic growth. Mckinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) cited in Adeyeye et al (2015) argue that a well-developed financial sector minimises transaction and monitoring costs and asymmetric information; thus there is improvement in financial intermediation. The existence of well-developed financial sector enhances the creation of financial services as well as accessibility to them in anticipation to their demand by participants in the real sector of the economy. The supply-leading hypothesis presumes that the economy responds to growth in the real sector facilitated by financial development.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Chau, Khin and Teng (2013) investigated the link between life and general insurance consumption and economic growth in Malaysia using secondary data from 1970 to 2012. The study adopted capital stock, total employment, life and general insurance premium as the independent variables, regressed against GDP (proxy for economic development). cointegration test, Granger causality test and Error Correction Method (ECM) as the statistical tools for data analysis. Their findings showed that total employment and life insurance premium had short run significant positive impact on economic growth, while capital stock and general insurance had positive significant effect on economic growth in the long run.

Akinlo (2013) examined the link between insurance business and economic growth in Nigeria using secondary data obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics for the period 1986 to 2010. The study adopted GDP (proxy for economic growth and the response variable), while insurance premium was used as the explanatory variable. Two macroeconomic indicators (inflation rate and interest rate) were introduced as moderating variables. He employed descriptive statistics, ADF unit root test, Johansen-Juselius cointegration test and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) as the statistical tools for the

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analysis of data. The results of the study established that insurance sector development had positive impact on GDP (proxy for economic growth).

Eze and Okoye (2013) carried out an analysis of the effect of insurance practices on economic growth of the Nigerian Economy from 1980 to 2011. They employed unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and error correction model in data analysis and they observed that insurance premium capital has significantly impacted on economic growth. Also, the level of total insurance investment has significantly affected economic growth. Moreover, there was a causal relationship between insurance sector development and economic growth in Nigeria. They concluded that there was a significant positive effect of insurance practice on the growth of the Nigerian economy.

Akinlo (2015) conducted an empirical investigation of the relationship between insurance business and economic growth using annual data of 30 SubSaharan African countries for the period 1995 to 2011. The study adopted gross domestic product as proxy for economic growth and the dependent variable, while insurance premium, interest rate, inflation and openness (representing insurance development) were used as the independent variables. He employed ADF unit root test, co-integration test and Granger causality test as the statistical techniques for the analysis of data. The results established that GDP granger cause insurance and insurance granger cause GDP. This means that insurance sector development exerted considerable impact on economic growth.

Oyedotun and Adesina (2015) examined the impact of insurance business on economic growth in Nigeria using secondary time series data obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics for the period 1980 to 2011. The study adopted GDP as proxy for economic growth and the response variable, while insurance investment was used as the explanatory variable. the OLS regression technique for the analysis of data, and found that insurance business made strong contribution to economic growth.

Gabriel (2015) investigated the effect of insurance sector development on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin for the period 1981 to 2013. The study adopted GDP (proxy for economic growth) as the response variable, while insurance sector development indicators such as total insurance payment, total insurance premium, total insurance investment and total insurance returns were used as the predictive variables. co-integration test and Granger causality test were the statistical tools employed for the analysis of data. The results revealed that total insurance investment and total insurance premium

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had significant positive link with GDP, while total insurance claims had significant negative effect on GDP.

Angappan, & Baker (2017) investigated the relationship between insurance and economic growth for USA, UK, China, India, Malaysia and Pakistan using Pooled Mean Group (PMG/ARDL). They reported a positive and significant relationship between aggregate insurance, measured by net premiums and economic growth for all six countries. In addition, at disaggregate level; non-life insurance is also significantly associated with economic growth for all six countries. However, life insurance is only promoting economic growth for UK, India and Pakistan while the reverse is true for USA, China and Malaysia.

Ul Din, Abu-Bakar and Regupathi (2017) examined the link between insurance business and economic growth in 20 countries for the period 2006 to 2015. In their study model economic growth was represented by GDP, while insurance activity was represented by net insurance written premium, insurance penetration and insurance density as dependent variables. The Hausman test statistics they employed for data analysis confirmed that insurance activities had positive significant effect on economic growth. However, non-life insurance business was more predominant than life insurance practice.

Arena (2018) worked on the empirical study and causal relationship between insurance market activity and economic growth which covers 56 countries (both developed and developing ones) in the period 1976 to 2004. He used the generalized method of moment for dynamic models of panel data and his results showed a positive and significant effect of total, life and non-life insurance market activity on economic growth.

Ouedraogo, Guerineau and Sawadogo (2018) investigated the association between the development of the life insurance sector and economic growth in 86 developing countries using data spanning 1996 to 2011. They adopted total life insurance premium as the explanatory variable and GDP (proxy for economic growth) as the response variable. The study employed descriptive statistics, generalized moments method (GMM) for the analysis of data. The results indicated that insurance sector development had positive effect on economic growth, but it varies from country to country according to the structural characteristics of different countries.

Gap in Empirical Gap in Literature: Evidently, the review of past empirical studies shows clearly that there is paucity of related reviewed on this topic “the effect of insurance market development on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria”. In both local and international journals, this area of research has remained less researched. Most of the studies such as Arena

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(2013) & Chen Lee & Lee (2011) researched on impact of insurance market development (or activity) on economic growth. Thus, there is a gap observed in the study of insurance market development and growth of the manufacturing sector. Content gap : Also, previous studies used both life and non-life insurance premium income as the main variables of insurance market development or insurance market activity. There is an obvious gap in the exploration of new variables that proxy insurance market development. This study intends to close this gap identified by using insurance penetration rate, insurance density rate and insurance claims paid

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopted the ex-post facto research design. Onwumere (2005) posits that the ex-post facto research design establishes a causal link between them. Based on the nature of this study which is to examine the effects of insurance market development on the growth of manufacturing sector in Nigeria which is a cause-effect study as well the use of data which the researcher cannot manipulate, the ex-post facto research design suites this study. Data was sourced from secondary sources. Secondary data is data which has been collected by individuals or agencies for purposes other than those of our particular research study (Onwumere, 2005). Time series secondary data for the study variables covering the period 1990 to 2019 were collected from various annual reports from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletins and Nigerian Insurance Digest (NAICOM) and National Bureau of Statistics data. The justification for the use of secondary data in this research is that; it is available, entirely appropriate and wholly adequate to draw conclusions and answer the question or solve the problem.

Model Specification

A model, according to Onwumere (2009), is a mathematical expression of reality though it can exist in other forms. The functional relationship between the response variable and the predictive variables were expressed in the following model which is an adaptation of a model that has been widely used in previous studies such as (Eze et al, 2013 & Igbodika et al, 2016). The research topics are effect of insurance market development on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria, 1990 to 2019. This research was carried out in Nigeria. The model used is formulated in form of Y as function of X; where Y is the dependent variables and X the independent variables. Put in mathematical form ($Y=f(X)$), in econometric pattern; Ordinary Least Square Regression Method was used

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$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X$ Y as a function of X

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \mu \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$MGR = \alpha + \beta ICP + \mu \dots\dots\dots (iI)$$

$$MGR = \alpha + \beta TIP + \mu \dots\dots\dots (iii)$$

$$MGR = \alpha + \beta IDR + \mu \dots\dots\dots (iv)$$

Where;

MGR = Manufacturing sector Growth rate

TPI=Total Insurance Premium Income

TIP = Total Insurance Penetration

ICP = Insurance Claims Paid by Insurance Companies

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Data are presented in line with the objectives and models of the study. The data used to test the hypotheses are presented in table 4.1.1.

Table 4.1 Manufacturing Growth Rate, Insurance Claims Paid, Insurance Penetration Rate, Insurance Density Rate and Total Insurance Premium, 1990-2021

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Year	Manufacturing Sector Growth (MSG/RGDP)	Total Insurance Claims Paid (N'000b)	Total Insurance Penetration Rate (total insurance premium/RGDP)	Insurance Density Rate (Total Premium Income/Population)(%)	Total Insurance Premium (N'000b)_
1990	8.65	306.5	0.0054	0.12	1.0484
1991	9.53	386.9	0.0069	0.14	1.3342
1992	8.96	613.9	0.0132	0.28	2.5179
1993	8.56	2684.1	0.0301	0.66	5.9013
1994	8.36	1315.3	0.0736	1.65	14.6717
1995	7.82	1508.9	0.0717	1.21	14.5876
1996	7.55	1654.1	0.0621	1.09	13.1506
1997	7.39	1677.3	0.0758	0.14	16.519
1998	6.32	1956.2	0.0799	1.48	17.8465
1999	6.5	5923.2	0.0652	1.22	14.6439
2000	6.36	5629.5	0.0951	1.87	22.5315
2001	6.6	6110.5	0.1147	2.41	28.9813
2002	6.26	6856.1	0.1304	2.7	37.7659
2003	6.05	9415.2	0.1386	3.12	43.9447
2004	6.12	12084	0.1442	3.61	50.4959
2005	6.27	12407.4	0.1808	4.84	67.7463

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2006	6.44	76276.1	0.2059	5.88	82.3619
2007	6.58	15843.7	0.2255	6.99	105.3793
2008	6.69	25864.9	0.3417	10.43	157.206
2009	6.67	49498.9	0.381	12.61	189.9605
2010	6.55	37589.6	0.3669	13.3	200.376
2011	7.33	39389.2	0.4064	15.51	233.7529
2012	7.98	32641.3	0.4738	18.85	283.9438
2013	9.22	6124.9	0.5026	17.59	317.7667
2014	9.95	28936.3	0.527	19.6	353.9004
2015	9.95	26323.1	0.5426	20.73	374.4937
2016	9.28	23506.4	0.5949	22.37	404.1422
2017	9.18	21222.7	0.6621	25.1	453.4807
2018	9.2	24997.1	0.692	26.74	483.0456
2019	9.08	73251.47	0.7034	27.75	501.3902
2020	9.2	24997.1	0.692	26.74	483.0456
2021	9.08	73251.47	0.7034	27.75	501.3902
2022	9.08	73251.47	0.7034	27.75	501.3902

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2021,2022; ICP computed from the source data

As indicated from Table 4.1, the value of manufacturing sector growth within the period of this study was 9.53% in 1991, but after the following year, there was a decline in the manufacturing sector output growth in Nigeria starting from 1992 till 1998. Nigeria manufacturing sector growth recorded the least rate of 6.05% in 2003. Nigeria's manufacturing sector recorded highest

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growth rate in 2014 and 2015 when the rate was 9.95% respectively. The table revealed that there was a constant decrease in manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 2015 to 2019.while insurance claims paid by industries rises from N306.5billion to N2,684.1billion between 1990 to 1993 within the period of this study. The amount fell to N1315.3billion in 1994, was later rise again. Insurance claims paid by industries recorded the highest amount of N76276.1billion in 2006.since then there is a constant fluctuation in the figures. Insurance claims paid by industries figures was not accounted for the period 2014 to 2018. In 2019. Insurance claims paid by industries was N73251.47billion within the period of this study.

Data Analysis

Table 4.2.1 UNIT ROOT TEST

Table 4.5: Unit root tests summary results: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test

Variable VALUE	ADF test statistic	P-	Test critical value (5%)	Decision	Order of Interpretation
1ST DIFFERENCE					
MGR	-3.845823	0.0069	-2.971853	Stationary	1 (1)
ICP	-6.3358	0.0000	-2.971853	Stationary	1 (1)
TIP	-2.080155	0.2536	-2.981038	Non-Stationary	1 (1)
IDR	-4.413326	0.0017	-2.971853	Stationary	
TPI	-0.933966	0.7608	-2.981038	Non-stationary	
2ND DIFFERENCE;					
TIP	-8.133357	0.0000	-2.981038	Stationary	1 (2)
TPI	-7.715346	0.0000		Stationary	1 (2)

Source: Extracted from e-view output data on the ADF tests, 2022.

DECISION: The preliminary tests conducted showed stationarity of the variables as indicated summary results extracted from the e-view output data depicted in Table 3. The result above shows that the absolute value of ADF statistic of Manufacturing growth rate(MGR), Insurance Claims paid by companies(ICP) & Insurance Density rate(IDR) becomes stationary at first difference at 5%, while the absolute value of Total Insurance Penetration(TIP) & Total Premium Income(TPI) becomes stationary at 2ND differences at 5%. We conclude that The p-values are less than 0.005, therefore there are no unit roots in the variables.

Table 4.8 Step Two: Presentation and Analysis of Result

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Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.948893	0.286119	27.78177	0.0000
ICP	-1.65E-05	1.13E-05	-1.462612	0.1547
R-squared	0.580978	Mean dependent var		7.713333
Adjusted R-squared	0.537799	S.D. dependent var		1.320484
S.E. of regression	1.295287	Akaike info criterion		3.419682
Sum squared resid	46.97753	Schwarz criterion		3.513096
Log likelihood	-49.29524	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.449566
F-statistic	2.139234	Durbin-Watson stat		0.198204
Prob(F-statistic)	0.154709			

Source: E-view version 8 output data, 2022.

$$\text{MGR} = \alpha + \beta \text{ICP} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Table 4.8 shows the result of the regression analysis of the Insurance claims paid by companies does not have a positive and insignificant effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2021. The result reveals that the model for our study is (F-statistic= 2.139234). The coefficient of determination (R-square), which measures the moderate fit of the model, indicates that 58.1% of the variations observed in the dependent variable were explained by the independent variables. This was moderated by the Adjusted R-squared to 54. %, indicating that there are other variables other than our explanatory variables that might also impact on the dependent variable. The result shows that ICP had Negative and non-significant effect on the MGR of Nigerian (ICP coefficient = -1.65, $p = 0.1547 > 0.05$, $t\text{-value} = -1.462612$). since the p-value is greater than p-table, we therefore Accept the null hypothesis and Reject the alternative hypothesis.

Decision: From the analysis above we accept the null hypothesis but reject the alternative hypothesis, which indicates that the Insurance claims paid by companies does not has positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

Table 4.9 Step Two: Presentation and Analysis of Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.014501	0.335145	20.92975	0.0000

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TIP	2.649265	0.965612	2.743612	0.0105
R-squared	0.711876	Mean dependent var		7.713333
Adjusted R-squared	0.683729	S.D. dependent var		1.320484
S.E. of regression	1.193027	Akaike info criterion		3.255206
Sum squared resid	39.85280	Schwarz criterion		3.348619
Log likelihood	-46.82809	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.285089
F-statistic	7.527407	Durbin-Watson stat		0.165913
Prob(F-statistic)	0.010481			

Source: E-view version 8 output data, 2022.

$$\text{MGR} = \alpha + \beta\text{TIP} + \mu \dots \dots \dots \text{(ii)}$$

Table 4.9 shows the result of the regression analysis of the Total Insurance penetration does not have positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022. The result reveals that the model for our study is (F-statistic=7.527407). The coefficient of determination (R-square), which measures the moderate fit of the model, indicates that 71% of the variations observed in the dependent variable were explained by the independent variables. This was moderated by the Adjusted R-squared to 68.4 %, indicating that there are other variables other than our explanatory variables that might also impact on the dependent variable. The result shows that TIP had Positive and significant effect on the MGR of Nigerian (TIP coefficient =2.649265, $p = 0.0105 < 0.05$, $t\text{-value} = 2.743512$). since the p-value is less than p-table, we therefore Reject the null hypothesis and Accept the alternative hypothesis.

Decision:From the analysis above we Reject the null hypothesis but Accept the alternative hypothesis, which indicates that the Total Insurance penetration has positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

Table 4.11. Step Two: Presentation and Analysis of Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.053962	0.275137	25.63799	0.0000
TPI	0.004401	0.001236	3.561726	0.0013
R-squared	0.811801	Mean dependent var		7.713333
Adjusted R -squared	0.787222	S.D. dependent var		1.320484

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S.E. of regression	1.114834	Akaike info criterion	3.119629
Sum square d resid	34.79994	Schwarz criterion	3.213042
Log likeliho od	-44.79443	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.149512
F-statistic	12.68590	Durbin-Watson stat	0.177738
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001342		

Source: E-view version 8 output data, 2022.

$$\text{MGR} = \alpha + \beta\text{TPI} + \mu \dots \dots \dots \text{(iv)}$$

Table 4.11 shows the result of the regression analysis of the Total insurance premium Income does has positive and significant Influence on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2021. The result reveals that the model for our study is (F-statistic=12.68590). The coefficient of determination (R-square), which measures the Goodness fit of the model, indicates that 81% of the variations observed in the dependent variable were explained by the independent variables. This was moderated by the Adjusted R-squared to 78.7%, indicating that there are other variables other than our explanatory variables that might also impact on the dependent variable. The result shows that TPI had Positive and significant effect on the MGR of Nigerian (TPI coefficient =0.004401, p = 0.0013 < 0.05, t-value =3.561726). since the p-value is less than p-table, we therefore Reject the null hypothesis and Accept the alternative hypothesis.

Decision: From the analysis above we Reject the null hypothesis but Accept the alternative hypothesis, which indicates that the Total insurance premium Income has positive and significant Influence on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

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5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

Based on the specific objectives and hypotheses tested, the findings emanating from the study are summarized as follows: The Insurance claims paid by companies to the manufacturing sector had negative and no significant effect on growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Decreasing manufacturing growth rate by 1.65% annually. There was a positive and significant effect of total insurance penetration on the growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. In other words, insurance penetration rate increased manufacturing sector growth significantly by 2.65% over the period studied. Total insurance premium income increased growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria significantly by 0.0044% annually.

Conclusion

The research concluded that the level of insurance market development which should be commensurate with Nigeria's huge potentials has not been attained. The demand for insurance protection against losses of life, property, crime, natural disaster, violence, accidents, fire etc are not so demanded by manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Insurance market development had positive effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

This study recommended amongst others that:

Individual persons distrust modern insurance practice in Nigeria. The industry should work indirectly to regain trust by promoting group insurance schemes especially among the rural populace and market associations that make up the manufacturing units. This will further deepen insurance penetration rate in the country. Government agencies like National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) and National Pension Commission (PENCOM) should strictly enforce the implementation of compulsory group life insurance cover under the Pension Reform Act, 2004 for manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Also, NAICOM and the insurance industry should leverage on the micro-insurance programme to ensure that insurance is entrenched among the local manufacturing firms to increase insurance awareness, volume of business, and invariably increased premium income.

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IMPACT OF MARKET RISK ON INVESTMENTS

IMPACT OF MARKET RISK ON INVESTMENTS OF CONSOLIDATED HALLMARK INSURANCE PLC

By

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IMPACT OF MARKET RISK ON INVESTMENTS

Abstract

Research Purpose: The study investigated the impact of market risk on the investments of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. The specific objectives were to analyse the impact of interest rate on investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. to evaluate the impact of inflation rate on the investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. and to examine the impact of exchange rate on the investment income of consolidated Hallmark insurance plc.

Methodology: Ex-post factor research design was adopted. Three hypotheses formulated were tested using multiple regression statistical techniques.

Research Findings: It was discovered that interest rate had no significant impact on investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc, foreign exchange rate had no significant impact on investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc, while inflation rate had significant impact on investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. Based on these findings of the study, it was concluded that interest rate and exchange rate had no significant impact on the investment income of consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc.

Recommendations: In line with the result, it was recommended that insurers should diversify/spread their investments over different channels and not relying unnecessarily on a single class of investment. They should also ensure that they run their business well as to ensure profitability which will eventually sustain their business.

Key words: Interest rate, Exchange rate, Inflation rate and Insurance investments.

IMPACT OF MARKET RISK ON INVESTMENTS

Introduction

Customers who purchase insurance policies from insurers pay premiums in exchange for risk protection. Insurance companies spend premiums in the economy and seek investment returns, which is a fundamental component of insurance products in order to preserve the value of the premiums received, ensuring that claims can be paid when necessary, and combat inflation (Association of British Insurers, 2023). In some circumstances, such as life insurance, it may take years or even decades from the moment an insurer receives premium payments until claims are paid. Insurers are expected to invest premiums in the economy and seek investment returns in order to protect the value of the premiums received, make sure that claims can be paid when necessary, and combat inflation. Insurance companies may opt for various investing methods depending on the duration and predictability of their liabilities. As a result of the long-term nature of many insurance products (such as annuities and life insurance), insurers are able to invest in long-term assets to match their long-term responsibilities, providing a crucial source of long-term funding for organizations and governments.

Several factors pose a challenge to the probability of an insurance company's investment. For most life insurers, market risk is a significant risk as they have to manage guarantees on unstable portfolios of assets. In the case of general insurers, the significance of market risk varies based on the business's tail, but investment income is a crucial profitability driver, and market risk encompasses fluctuations in this income (Kelliher, 2016). In Nigeria, life insurers are exposed to guarantees under "with-profits" policies, where a portion of the assets is invested in equities, effectively creating an unusual put option position. Life insurers' unit-linked funds are a crucial investment choice for pensions. These funds usually do not contain any guarantees, and the policyholder bears the market risk, but the life insurer is exposed to variations in fund-related fees. Until recently, pension funds had to be converted into an annuity for life, and Nigerian life insurers have substantial liabilities to this type of business, typically supported by corporate bonds to avail themselves of the liquidity premium on these (as there is little need for liquidity as the annuities cannot be cashed), but this gives rise to exposure to movements in credit spreads

The frequent swings in the economy's exchange rate, bank rate, and inflation rate are of particular concern to Nigerian insurance businesses. Given that companies are constrained by legal requirements to certain investment portfolios, these variances place various degrees of pressure on insurers' investments. On the liability side, higher-than-expected claim expenses lead to unanticipated policy premiums because of increasing inflation rates (SLC Management, 2023). When interest rates fluctuate, the insurance sector's investment behaviour changes significantly. This can have a big impact on market financing conditions and may even have an impact on

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financial stability as insurers rebalance their investment portfolios (Kaufmann, Leyva, and Storz, 2022). Foreign exchange risks are a concern for insurers with operations across borders and in different currencies. This risk primarily entails the potential for a change in the exchange rate between the insurer's "home" currency and the foreign currency in which the insurer conducts business or makes investments. This change could have either a positive or negative impact on the company's financial position, accounting cash flows, and asset/liability values (Gorvett, 2012).

It is important to understand the amount to which a risk can negatively affect an insurance organisation because a company's ability to engage in competitive activities depends, in part, on its capacity to handle the risks it confronts effectively and efficiently. Therefore, the purpose of this inquiry is to determine how big of a problem market risk variables are for the investment of Nigeria's insurance business.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to assess the impact of market risk on investment of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To analyse the impact of interest rate on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc
2. To evaluate the impact effect of inflation rate on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc
3. To examine the impact effect of exchange rate on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc

Empirical Review

In order to investigate the impact of market risk on the equity return of financial institutions listed in Sri Lanka between 2007 and 2011, Nimalathasan and Puwanenthiren (2012) used financial leverage as a metric. The financial performance of the companies and market risk were shown to be significantly and positively correlated. Berends, McMenemy, Plestis, and Rosen (2013) looked at how vulnerable life insurance companies were to interest rate changes. According to the study, prolonged low interest rates might be problematic for some economic sectors, including life insurance, even though they can encourage borrowing and investment. Using cross-country European aggregate data, Dorofiti and Jakubik conducted a study in 2013 to look into the connection between insurer profitability and interest rates in the macroeconomic context. The Generalised Method of Moments was the statistical analysis method employed. The study's

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conclusions imply that low interest rates negatively affect insurance profitability together with sluggish economic development, subpar stock market performance, and high inflation. Doreen analysed the relationship between macroeconomic variables and the financial performance of Kenyan insurance companies in 2014. The study adopted a descriptive correlation research design and employed SPSS descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and multiple regression analysis to analyse the data. The study found that Interest rate, Gross Domestic Product, Claim ratio, and Expense ratio were statistically significant, whereas Inflation rate, Exchange rate, Money Supply, and Asset size were not statistically significant with significance levels greater than 5%. In 2017, Ehiogu and Orga investigated the influence of exchange rate on insurance premiums in the Nigerian insurance sector. To test the hypothesis, the researchers employed the Ordinary Least Square Regression analysis technique, and the significance level of the result was 5%. The study found that the exchange rate had a negative but insignificant impact on insurance premiums in the Nigerian insurance industry. In 2018, Ehiogu and Nnamocha examined the impact of interest rate on profit within the Nigerian insurance industry. The research employed the technique of Ordinary Least Square Regression to verify the hypothesis. The study discovered that the interest rate had a positive but insignificant effect on the total profit of the Nigerian insurance industry. Cafasso, Chela, and Kimura (2018) investigated market risk-based capital for Brazilian insurance companies using a stochastic methodology. In the Brazilian insurance industry, the probabilistic approach led to potential loss estimates that were four times greater than those derived from the deterministic regulatory model. Market risk assessment was the topic of Kokoris, Archontakis, and Grose's (2020) study: evidence from bundled retail and insurance-based investment products. Calculating CFVaR by ESAs demonstrates that, in general, CF is a more robust risk model than the simpler historical ones. However, when CFES is implemented, significant insights are obtained. First, the CF expansion can only be regarded a reliable method 50% of the time. Second, the CFES is a more coherent measure of risk than the CFVaR. When excessively fat-tailed or non-symmetrical distributions are present, we conclude that the CF expansion is unable to accurately estimate the market risk of UL products. Kassi, Rathnayake, Louembe, and Ding (2019) analysed the market risk and financial performance of 31 non-financial Moroccan Stock Exchange-listed companies. The results indicate that the various measures of market risk have negative effects on the financial performance of companies. In comparison to the book-to-market ratio and the gearing ratio, the degree of financial leverage has a greater effect on the elasticity of the firm's assets. In the majority of instances, the firm's age, the cash holdings ratio, the firm's size, the debt-to-assets ratio, and the tangibility ratio have positive effects on financial performance, whereas the debt-to-income ratio and stock turnover have negative effects. Okeke and Nwafor (2020) examined the economic impact of inflation and interest rate on the Nigerian life annuity industry. The data were analysed using the statistical procedure of ordinary least square (OLS). Results indicate that a

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rising rate of inflation did not pose a significant challenge to the life annuity industry in Nigeria, whereas unstable interest rates did pose a significant challenge. Okparaka and Makwe (2019) investigated the impact of inflation rate, interest rate, and savings rate on the development of the insurance industry in Nigeria. Ordinary least square was the method of analysis employed. It was determined that inflation rate had a positive but insignificant effect on the insurance density of the Nigerian insurance industry, that interest rate had a positive but insignificant effect on total profit, and that savings rate had a negative but insignificant effect on insurance density. Offiong et al. (2020) analysed Nigeria's exchange rate volatility and insurance industry performance. This study analysed the long-term effects of exchange rate volatility on insurance performance in Nigeria using insurance penetration and insurance density as performance measures. This study covers the years between 1986 and 2018. The findings indicated that exchange rate volatility has a significant and positive long-term effect on insurance performance in Nigeria. With this finding, the study recommended the implementation of a defined and unified exchange rate regime to prevent the insurance sector from making abnormal gains from currency variations/mispricing, as this is necessary to build a sector that can absorb any future exchange rate volatility. Offiong et al. (2020) examined exchange fee volatility and insurers performance in Nigeria. Using penetration of insurance and density of insurance as metrics of coverage overall performance in Nigeria, this test employed the vector errors correction model to analyse the long-term effects of exchange rate volatility on coverage performance. Findings indicated the existence of a substantial and remarkable long-term effect of exchange rate volatility on coverage performance in Nigeria.

Methodology

The research adopted *ex-post facto* research design. Secondary data were used in the study.

The functional model specification is given as:

$$\text{INVINC} = f(\text{INTR} + \text{EXCR} + \text{INFR}) \dots(i)$$

The model is specified as follows:

$$\text{INVINC} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INTR} + \beta_2 \text{EXCR} + \beta_3 \text{INFR} + \mu \dots(ii)$$

Where: INVINC = Investment income; INTR = Interest rate risk; EXCR = Exchange rate risk; INFR = Inflation rate risk; β_0 = Constant parameter; β_1 = Coefficient parameter of INTR; β_2 = Coefficient parameter of EXCR; β_3 = Coefficient parameter of INFR; μ = error term

Description of Variables

Dependent variable

Investment income: This refers to the revenue produced by payouts of dividends, interest earnings, and profits gained from the sale of any asset or security, as well as returns obtained from financial market investments.

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Independent Variables:

Interest rate risk = This is the change in interest rate from one year to another.

Foreign exchange risk = This is the change in foreign exchange value from one year to another.

Inflation rate risk = This is the change in inflation value from one year to another.

The model was estimated using multiple regression statistical techniques. This is at a 5 percent level of significance.

Unit root tests

The stationarity of the data was tested using the Philips-Perron test statistic. The summary of the test were displayed in Table 1

Table 4.3 Result of Unit root tests

Variable	Phillips-Perron test statistic	Critical value @ 5%	Order of Integration	P-value
EXCR	-7.424394	-3.144920	1(0)	0.0001
INFR	-8.135641	-3.144920	1(0)	0.0023
INTR	-4.212206	-3.144920	1(0)	0.0086
INVINC	-7.030151	-3.119910	1(0)	0.0001

Source: Researcher's calculation using the data in Appendix One

Table 1 reveals that all the time series were stationary at level.

Test of Hypotheses.

Table 2 Result of Hypothesis test

Dependent Variable: INVINC

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/19/23 Time: 19:14

Sample: 1 15

Included observations: 15

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.288051	0.623708	5.271778	0.0003

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INTR	0.338358	0.237192	1.426514	0.1815
INFR	-1.423974	0.441118	-3.228102	0.0080
EXCR	2.732079	0.326815	8.359722	0.0000
Mean dependent				8.34025
R-squared	0.884273	var		1
Adjusted R-squared	0.852711	S.D. dependent var		3
Akaike info				0.53999
S.E. of regression	0.165212	criterion		5
Schwarz criterion				0.35118
Sum squared resid	0.300246	Hannan-Quinn		1
Hannan-Quinn				0.54200
Log likelihood	8.049959	criter.		6
Durbin-Watson stat				2.26342
F-statistic	28.01698	Durbin-Watson stat		5
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000019			

Source: Researcher's Eviews 10 Output, 2023

From Table 2 it is seen that probability of the F-Statistic was 0.000019 which is lower than the level of significance of 0.05.

Discussion of Findings

The coefficient of interest rate at 0.338358 showed it has a positive relationship with investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. It implies that a unit increase in investment income is dependent on 0.338358 basis points increase in interest rate. The coefficient of inflation rate at -1.423974 showed it has a positive relationship with investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. It implies that a unit increase in investment income is dependent on -1.423974 basis points decrease in inflation rate. The coefficient of exchange rate at 2.732079 showed it has a positive relationship with investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. It implies that a unit increase in investment income is dependent on 2.732079 basis points decrease in exchange rate.

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The Adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.852711 shows that in the model used interest rate, inflation rate and exchange rate can explain only 85.2711 percent variation in investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc.

The p-value of F-statistic at 0.000019 is less than the level of significance of 0.05 percent. It shows that the hypothesis test has statistical significance. In other words, the joint impact of interest rate, inflation rate and exchange rate on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc did not happen by chance.

To determine the individual impact of each variable the t-statistic was analysed. For interest rate, inflation rate and exchange rate t-calculated is 1.426514, -3.228102 and 8.359722 respectively. Using $t_{\alpha/2}(n-k)$:

Where:

$\alpha/2$ = level of significance divided by two

n = number of rows in data table

k = number of columns in data table

t-tabulated derived from Percentage points of t-distribution table is:

$$t(0.05/2)(15-2) = (0.025)(14) = 0.35$$

Given that t-calculated for interest rate and exchange rate at 1.426514 and 8.359722 are higher than t-tabulated at 0.35 it shows that it did fall in the critical region and not the acceptance region. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. It reveals that interest rate and exchange rate had no significant impact on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. On the other hand, t-calculated for inflation rate at -3.228102 is lower than t-tabulated at 0.35. It shows that inflation rate had significant impact on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc. The findings of the hypothesis test contradicted the findings of Okeke and Nwafor (2020), who discovered that interest rates influenced the development of the life annuity industry in Nigeria. However, it concurred with Ehiogu and Nnamocha's (2018) findings that interest rates had a negligible effect on the total profit of the Nigerian insurance industry.

Orga and Ehiogu (2018) discovered that any change in the exchange rate could potentially reduce the expected returns that the insurance industry anticipates on its investments. The outcome of the hypothesis test corroborated their findings. In addition, it was consistent with the findings of Muriithi, Muturi, and Waweru (2016), who found that market risk indicators, such as the degree of financial leverage, the foreign exchange exposure risk, and the net interest margin, had significant negative effects on return on equity.

In contrast, the results of the hypothesis test contradicted the findings of Daare (2016), which indicated that inflation had a statistically significant impact on the profitability of Indian

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insurance companies. Nonetheless, it supported the conclusion of Nyamu (2016) that there was a direct correlation between inflation and the financial performance of insurance firms in Kenya.

Summary of Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

1. Interest rate had no significant impact on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc.
2. Foreign exchange rate had no significant impact on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc.
3. Inflation rate had significant impact on investment income of Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc.

Conclusion

What do insurance companies do with the enormous sums generated by premium payments? A portion is set aside as reserves to assure sufficient funds for future claims, while the remainder is invested. Typically, underwriting income exceeds investment income, causing many insurers to adopt conservative investment strategies, such as investing in blue-chip equities or bonds. Regardless of their strategy, all insurance companies are exposed to a variety of risks, including market risk, which results from fluctuations in market factors such as interest rates, stock prices, foreign exchange rates, and commodity prices (First Bank, 2020). This study investigates the affect of interest rates, exchange rates, and inflation rates on Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc's investment income. The results indicate that neither interest rates nor exchange rates have a significant impact on Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc's investment income.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study it was recommended that while making investment, insurance companies should be guided by certain fundamental principles:

- Safety because the company is entrusted with the responsibility to pay claims as and when the need arises.
- Profitability ensures the company runs its business on a solvent basis, depending on how they have invested their fund.
- Liquidity, which represents convertibility of investments into cash without undue loss of capital for the company.

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- Diversification helps spread the investment over different channels, not relying unnecessarily on a single class of investment.

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ENTRY GRADES AND STUDY STRATEGIES ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE

**EFFECTS OF ENTRY GRADES AND STUDY STRATEGIES ON PERFORMANCE OF
ACCOUNTING STUDENTS IN FEDERAL POLYTECHNIC IN NORTHWEST ZONE,
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This study explores the impact of entry grades and study strategies on the academic performance of accounting students in Federal Polytechnic, Northwest Zone, Nigeria, with specific objectives in mind.

Methodology: Employing an Ex-post facto design, the research population comprised 328 N.DI students who took the Principle of Accounting course during the 2021/2022 academic session in Northwest Zone, Nigeria. The entire population served as the sample. Data collection involved three instruments: Entry Grades Record Sheet, the original Study Process Questionnaire (SPQ) developed by Biggs in 1987, and the Revised Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) modified in 2001 by Biggs, Kember, and Leung to categorize students into deep and surface study strategies. Additionally, a Financial Accounting Score Sheet was used.

Data Collection and Analysis: Four experts validated the instruments, and data were collected by the researcher with the assistance of four research assistants. The collected data were coded using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Hypotheses one, two, three, and four were tested using regression analysis, while hypotheses five and six were analyzed through t-test analysis. The significance level was set at 0.05.

Research Findings: The results revealed a positive relationship between entry grades, study strategies, and the academic performance of Federal Polytechnic students in Principle of Accounting. Notably, the study highlights that poor performance in Principle of Accounting can be attributed to students' entry requirements and the study strategies they adopt.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, it is recommended that accounting lecturers encourage students who achieved credit and above in Principle of Accounting to adopt deep study strategies, as these strategies have a significant positive impact on academic performance. Moreover, students seeking admission into the polytechnic with pass and below entry grades should be encouraged to embrace deep study strategies for improved outcomes.

Key words: Entry grades, Study strategies, Academic Performance

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1. Introduction

The right to seek a meaningful education is a universal right. However, for every individual to acquire meaningful knowledge, he/she must be engaged in teaching and learning process. Engagement in teaching and learning process has its result or expected outcome of every effective teaching and learning process is academic achievement and this is measured in grades after taking examination. Grades are academic performance or achievement of learners which translated into letters is based on the scores. These grades vary from A, B, C, D, E, and F. These passable grades serve as milestone or prerequisites that move the students from one level of education to another.

In Nigeria, candidate pursuing higher education must take the senior secondary exam NECO, WAEC and NABTEB, must obtain required grades. It is expected that the entry grades will facilitate teaching and learning that in turn enhance students' performance. Based on this applicant into Accountancy program must have credit in English and Mathematics and at least three (3) credits in commercial subjects, such as Economics, Accounting, Typewriting, Shorthand, Commerce, and Office practice. This is in line with recommendation of National Board of Technical Education, which stipulates that, any applicant into Accountancy must have at least three credits in commercial subject. (NBTE, 2004).

Student's background in principle of accounting is the requirement of entry grades in their major commercial subjects which are essential in higher institutions. It is expected that entry grades is the foundation needed by all students 'applying for course into tertiary institutions. A good foundation may provide a solid ground for the next level of study; it is believed that the knowledge and skills acquired at secondary school in this subject will help to develop in students' critical thinking, problem solving, team-work, time-management and writing skills.

Study strategies are specific actions taken by learners to make learning easier, faster and more transferable to new situations. It is also perceived as a particular form of observable behavior employed by the learner. Umar (2014) reported that study strategies to enable learner make the most efficient use of all strengths and limitations of their particular performance. There are two common approaches to study strategies such as surface and deep. There are several techniques that are used to classify students into surface or deep study strategy adopted in learning one of the most notable techniques is Revised study process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) (Tight, 2003).

A student that adopts a deep approach to learning is identified with intention to understand, intrinsic motivation, use of evidence, critical thinking and relating ideas to already known concepts and principles. This leads to understanding and long retention of concept that can be used for problem solving in unfamiliar contexts. While a student who adopts surface

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study strategies is identified with intention to reproduce, take a narrow view and concentrate on detail, stick closely to the course requirement, extrinsic motivation and literal memorization (Enswistle and Macune 2004). Surface strategy lead to superficial retention of material for examination, does not promote understanding or long-term retention of knowledge and information.

Academic performance refers to an achievement in a particular subject area of study in a given school by professional teachers. Students' academic is determining by students of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains, achievement in teaching and learning process. Rothesian in Hamza A.H (2021) defines accounting as a specialized area of instruction that deals directly with business facts, business understanding, economic understanding, business attitudes and appreciations necessary to understand and adjust to the economic and social institutions called "business" it seeks to achieve a number of objectives. Accounting is the means by which information about enterprise is communicated and, thus, is sometimes called the language of business. Many different users have need for accounting information in order to make important decisions. These users include investors, creditors, management, government agencies, labor unions, and others.

Entry grades in principle of Accounting is basic skills and knowledge gained at secondary school helps to develop in students the understanding, critical thinking and technical skills to meet the educational challenges at higher education. Entry grades have influence on overall academic success for college students (not necessarily accounting students)

All the variables discussed so far, constitute the background to the study on effect on entry grade and study strategies on academic performance in Colleges of Education students in financial accounting in, Northwest Zone, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problems

The discipline of accounting is concerned with systematic practice of identifying, recording, measuring, classifying, summarizing, interpreting and communicating the financial transactions (in term of money) of a business firm or an individual following a set of rules and regulations. Jubril (2011) found that to meet the demands and expectation of society on enhancing students' performance in Accounting, students required a range of regularly occurring competencies in principle of Accountings with potential to practice these skills in Principle Accounting in tertiary institutions. The overall performance of students in Accounting in polytechnic has to be extremely concern by the stakeholders' in education, because data collected by the researcher from N.D 1 2019/2020 session failed to score credit and above in Principle of Accounting. Generally (Drennan and Rhode in Hamza 2021), also observed that the performance in Principle of Accounting has not been impressive in higher institutions in Nigeria. It has been observed by

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the researcher through interaction with students that the performance students' especially Principal of accounting in polytechnic in Northwest Zone, Nigeria had been decline due to poor study strategies adopted by the students. This was also the observed by the researcher of poor entry requirement and admission strategies which stipulated by the institutions is another problem that lead to conduct this research and this process have negative effects the students' performance in accounting. Another issue is that has been of concern by researcher inability of ND students to obtain minimum of merit in their overall result which make difficult advance their studies for direct entry into university It follows therefore that a pass grade in Advanced Financial Accounting which is the accounting student core subject places the student in a difficult position in terms of his/her advancement of studies.

In line with above problems raised, the researcher intends to conduct a research on the Effects of entry grade and study strategies in academic performance in polytechnic students Northwest Zone, Nigeria with hope solution will be provided.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The major objective of this study is to determine the effects of entry grade and study strategies on performance of accounting students in Federal polytechnic in Northwest Geopolitical zone. The specific objectives bases on the scope of the study are to:

1. determine the effects of credit entry grades and above in O' Level principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria.
2. determine the effects of pass entry grades and below in O' Level principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone, Nigeria.
3. determine the effects of credit entry grades and above in O' Level principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria.
4. determine the effects of pass and entry grades and below in O' Level principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria.
5. determine the relative effects in the mean performance of accounting students with credit and above in O, Level principle of accounting that adopted surface over those that adopted deep study strategies in accounting in federal polytechnic in North-west zone, Nigeria.
6. Determine the relative effect in the mean performance of accounting students with pass and below in O' Level principle of accounting that adopted deep study strategies and those that

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adopted surface study strategies in financial accounting in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Entry Grades

In Hamza A.H (2021), Daniel Defined entry grade as the accomplishment demonstrated by students in their submissions for admission to postsecondary institutions at ordinary level. Additionally he came to the conclusion that students with credit and above entry grades in principles of accounting at O/L have the potentials of performing better their counterparts with pass entry grades in Principle of Accounting in Colleges.

Haruna (2011) Entry grade is the minimum academic criterion that an applicant must meet in order to be offered a place of study in a postsecondary institution. He suggested that students would benefit from having a strong foundation in higher education if they require the fundamental knowledge and skills at the secondary school level. Additionally he also recommended for a student to have good entry grades in secondary, orientation programs should be mounted to enlighten the secondary school students on the need to develop interest in principle of account, because it will provide them with the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities that will enable them to cope up with further educational challenges. also stated that the negative effects on students 'grades related to missing many classes in both secondary and tertiary and this has significant effect on their performance and the grades acquired.

2.2 Concept of Study Strategy

Study strategy is any action, set of instructions, or method used by students to help them acquire, store retrieve, and utilized information (Umar 2014). Learning (affective) strategy includes technique for more effective time management and stress management test anxiety reduction; and increased positive self-talk, self-monitoring and self-coaching activities (Doyle and Garland, 2001).The students Approach to learning (SAL) research has produced findings about a variety of factors that affects studying and students learning.

According to Biggs, surface approach to learning is when a student's simply learns what is necessary to pass an exam and meet the basic criteria of a higher learning program (Biggs and Tang 2007). He describes it is a situation "cuts corner" in order to use a low degree of cognitive effort, despite the fact that the learning task at hand requires a higher level of cognitive activity,

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and which is done in order to “get by” and appear acceptable”. This method is allegedly motivated by or connected to individual circumstances that have little to do with educational institution needs (Biggs and Tang 2007, 22). Biggs suggests that students using a surface approach to learning end up using the memorization of facts as a substitute for understanding, padding their writing with quotes and facts to make it seem more substantial than it is, listing points of theory instead of crafting arguments or relating these points to one another, and that they are unlikely to check original sources, relying instead on others’ interpretations of original sources (Biggs and Tang 2007, 23). Biggs suggests that there are many factors that encourage students to use a surface approach to learning. Chief amongst these are: an intention to only achieve minimal pass marks; allowing non-academic priorities to take precedence; lack of time, possibly due to a high workload; misunderstanding requirements of a course or course assessments; a cynical view of education, exemplified in statements such as that ‘It’s only a piece of paper’; high anxiety about passing and workload; and genuine inability (Biggs and Tang 2007, 23).

2.3 Concept of Academic Performance

Students’ academic performance refers to the ability of students to score high grade in a test or examination after teaching and learning have taken place by teachers or learners by giving the students test or examination which they pass very well. Academic performance according to Hamza A.H (2021) Rothstein refers to a successful accomplishment or performance in particular subject area of study in a given school by the professional teachers. Academic performance, also deal the students studies and how they cope with or accomplish different task given to them by their teachers in fixed time or academic year. Alade (2000) posit academic performance as successful accomplishment or performance in particular subject area. It is indicated by grades, mark score of descriptive commentaries. In their contribution, Kobaland and in Hamza A.H (2021) Musek explained that academic performance refers to a student’s ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate knowledge verbally or down on paper.

3.0 Methodology

The ex-post facto research design was employed in conducting the study. The population comprised Three twenty eight (328) ND I. students that offer principle of accounting students in 2021/2022 academic session in the Department of Accountancy, of the five (5) Federal polytechnic in Northwest, zone Nigeria, namely Federal Polytechnic Kauran Namode, zamfara (119), Federal Polytechnic Daura Katsina state (16), waziri umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi state (48), Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna state (105), Hussain Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure Jigawa state (40). The entire three hundred and twenty eight (328) were

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purposely used to serve as sample of the study. Three instruments are used for data collection in this research (Entry Grades Record Sheet, The original Study Process Questionnaire (SPQ and students semester result) was developed by Biggs in 1987. The Revised Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was modified in 2001 by Biggs, Kember, and Leung was adopted by the researcher in order to categorize the students into deep and surface study strategies. And Principal Accounting Score Sheet) was used for the data collection. The instrument validated by four experts. The data collected by researcher assisted by 4 research assistants. The data collected for this were coded into Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS). The package is use to answer research questions and run regression analysis in testing hypotheses one, two, three, and four while hypotheses five and six were tested using t-test analysis. All the null hypotheses tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

4.0 Result

Research Question One: *What is the effect of credit and above O'level entry grades in Principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal Polytechnic in North-west l zone Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of effect of credit entry grades and above on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategy

Category	N	Score Mean	Std. dev	Effect
Credits grade and deep study strategy	137	61.4	18.7	High

Source: *Field Work 2022*

The result of data used to determine the effect of credit entry grades and above on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategy revealed that the mean score stood at 61.4 with standard deviation value of 18.7. From the analysis, the mean score was high, hence it was concluded that in depended variable had high effect on performance of accounting students in secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of pass and below O'level entry grades in Principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal Polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria?*

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Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of effect of pass/below entry grades on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategy

Category	N	Score Mean	Std. dev	Effect
Pass/below grades and deep study strategy	18	53.8	16.6	Moderate

Source: Field Work 2022

The result of data used to answer research question two revealed the mean score of 53.8 and standard deviation of 16.6. The analysis therefore revealed that deep study strategy has moderate effect on performance of accounting students with pass and below O'level grades in principles of accounting.

Research Question Three: *What is the effect of credit and above O'level entry grades in Principle accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal Polytechnic in North-west one in Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of effect of credit entry grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Category	N	Score Mean	Std. dev	Effect
Credits/above grade and surface study strategy	159	66.2	19.9	Very high

Source: Field Work 2022

The result data of mean and standard deviation in the table 5: revealed the mean score of 66.2 and standard deviation of 19.9 in performance of financial accounting students. From the analysis, the mean score was very high, hence it was concluded that surface study strategy had very high effect on performance of accounting students with credit and above entry grades in principles of accounting.

Research Question Four: *What is the effect of pass and below O'level entry grades in Principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface strategies in federal Polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria?*

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of effect of pass/below entry grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Category	N	Score Mean	Std. Dev	Effect
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Pass grade/below on surface study strategy	14	49.8	12.7	Low
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Source: *Field Work 2022*

The result in Table 4: disclosed the mean of 49.8 and standard deviation of 12.7 for performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy. From the Table, the mean score of 49.8 was found to be less than average, hence it was concluded that surface study strategy had weak effect on performance of accounting students with pass and below O'level entry grades in principles of accounting.

Research Question Five: *What is the relative effect of credit and above O'level entry grades on the mean performance of accounting students that adopted surface strategy over those that adopted deed study strategy in federal Polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria?*

Table 5: Mean and standard deviation of effect of credit/above entry grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Category	N	Score Mean	Std. dev	Effect
Credit/above surface study strategy	169	66.2	19.9	Very high
Credit/above deep study strategy	147	61.4	18.7	High

Source: *Field Work 2022*

Mean difference in the performance of the two groups of students revealed the mean of 66.2 and standard deviation of 19.9 for accounting that adopts surface study strategy. Those that adopted deep study strategy had the mean score of 61.4 and standard deviation of 18.5. From the analysis the students that adopted deep study strategy had high effect and those that adopted surface study strategy had moderate effect. Hence those that adopted deep study strategy performed better in Principles of Accounting.

Research Question Six: *What is the relative effect of pass and below O'level entry grades on the mean performance of accounting students that adopted surface strategy over those that adopted deed study strategy in federal Polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria?*

Table 6: Mean and standard deviation of effect of pass/below entry grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Category	Score	Std.	Effect
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	N	Mean	dev	
Pass/below surface study strategy	28	49.3	12.7	Low
Pass/below deep study strategy	38	53.8	16.6	Moderate

Source: Field work 2022

The result of data in Table 8: revealed the mean of 49.3 and standard deviation of 12.7 for students with pass and below entry grades in principles of accounting and adopted surface study strategy. Those that adopted deep study strategy had the mean of 51.6 and standard deviation of 16.8. From the Table surface study strategy had weak effect while deep study strategy had moderate effect on financial accounting students with pass and below O'level grades in principles of accounting.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: *There is no significant effect of credit and above O'level entry grades in Principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria*

Table 7: Regression Analysis on test of effect of credit and above O'level grades on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategy

Credit and above O'level grades on performance of deep study strategy financial accounting students	Std.						
	B	Error	T	R-crit	R-cal	R ²	Adjusted R ²
	3.711	.614	6.035				
	1.545	.79	1.956	0.088	.641	.386	.204

Source: Field work 2022

The regression analysis used to determine null hypothesis one revealed the r- value of .621 with R² of .386 at $\alpha = 0.05$. The result indicates deep study strategy had 64.1% effect on performance of accounting students with credit entry grades and above in O'level principles of accounting. The observed effect (64.1%) was significant, this can also be seen in the R-cal greater than the R-crit (.641 > 0.088). the result therefore shows that deep study strategy have effect on performance of financial accounting with credit entry grades and above in O'level principles of accounting., hence the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two: *There is no significant effect of pass/ and below O'level entry grades in Principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that*

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adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria

Table 8: Regression Analysis on test of effect of pass and below O'level grades on performance of accounting students that adopted deep study strategy

Pass and below O'level grades on performance of deep study strategy financial accounting students	Std.			R-crit	R-cal	R ²	Adjusted R ²
	B	Error	T				
	2.023	.742	2.726				
	0.337	.83	0.406	0.088	.221	0.046	0.032

Source: Field work 2022

The analysis of data used to determine null hypothesis two shows that r-cal was greater than the r-crit (.221>0.088). The R² of 0.046 obtained signified that the deep study strategy had 0.045 effect on performance of accounting students with pass and below O'level entry grades in principles of accounting at $\alpha = 0.05$. The effect of 4.6% was significant, hence it was concluded that deep study strategy had significant effect on performance of financial accounting with pass entry grades and below in O'level principles of accounting, hence the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Three: *There is no significant effect of credit and above O'level entry grades in financial accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria*

Table 9: Regression Analysis on test of effect of credit and above O'level grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Credit and above O'level grades on performance of surface study strategy financial accounting students	Std.			R-crit	R-cal	R ²	Adjusted R ²
	B	Error	T				
	3.442	.613	5.615				
	1.427	.488	2.924	0.088	.444	.208	.081

Source: Field work 2022

The regression analysis used to determine null hypothesis three revealed the r-critvalue of .444 with R² f .197 and adjusted R² of .081 at $\alpha = 0.05$. The analysis revealed that surface study strategy had 20.8% effect of performance of accounting students with credit and above O'level grades in principles of accounting. The observed effect ($r^2=.444$) was significant. This can also be seen in the R-cal greater than the Rcrit (.444>0.088). The result therefore indicated

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that surface study strategy had effect on performance of accounting with credit and above entry O'level grades in accounting. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Four: *There is no significant effect of pass/ and below O'level entry grades in principle of accounting on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria*

Table 10: Regression Analysis on test of effect of pass and below O'level grades on performance of accounting students that adopted surface study strategy

Pass and below O'level grades on performance of surface study strategy principle of accounting students	Std.		T	R-crit	R-cal	R ²	Adjusted R ²
	B	Error					
	2.079	.789	2.636				
	0.688	.89	0.773	0.088	.081	0.011	0.0063

Source: Field work 2022

The regression analysis used to determine null hypothesis three revealed the r-critvalue of 0.81 with R² f 0.011 and adjusted R² of 0.0063 at $\alpha = 0.05$. The analysis revealed that surface study strategy had 11% effect of performance of accounting students with pass and below O'level grades in principles of accounting. The observed effect ($r^2=.0.007$) was not significant. This can also be seen in the R-cal less than the Rcrit (.081<0.088). The result therefore indicated that surface study strategy had weak effect on performance of accounting with pass and below entry O'level grades in accounting. The null hypothesis was therefore retained.

Hypothesis Five: *There is no relative effect of credit and above O'level entry grades on the mean performance of accounting students that adopted surface strategy over those that adopted deed study strategy in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria*

Table 11:t-test analysis on difference in the performance of students with credit and above entry grades due to study strategy

Study strategy	N	X	SD	t-cal	t-value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Surface	169	66.4	19.9	2.61	1.96	22	
Deep	147	61.4	18.7				.001

Source: Field work 2022

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Result of data used to determine null hypothesis five revealed the mean score of 66.4 and 61.4 with standard deviation of 19.9 and 18.7 for students in surface study strategy and those in deep study strategy respectively. The cal value of 2.61 was greater than the table value of 1.96. The alpha value of .001 indicated that there was difference in the mean performance of accounting students based on the study strategy adopted. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Six: *There is no relative effect of pass and below O'level entry grades on the mean performance of accounting students that adopted surface strategy over those that adopted deed study strategy in federal polytechnic in North-west zone in Nigeria*

Table12: t-test analysis on difference in the performance of students with pass and below entry grades due to study strategy

Study strategy	N	X	SD	t-cal	t-value	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Surface	28	49.3	12.7	1.99	1.96	64	.000
Deep	38	53.6	16.6				

Source: Field work 2022

Result of data used to determine null hypothesis six presented in Table 4.13 revealed mean score of 49.3 with standard deviation of 12.7 for students in surface study strategy. Those in deep study strategy had mean score of 53.6 with standard deviation of 16.8. The t-cal was greater than the t-crit ($1.99 > 1.96$). The alpha value of .000 obtained showed that difference exist between mean performance of students with pass and below entry grades in principles of accounting and adopted surface study strategy and those that adopted deep study strategy. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

5.0 Discussion of Major Findings

The results in Table 1 and 7 revealed that, credit entry grades and above in O' Level Principles of accounting has very high effects on performances of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone. This is evident in the analysis of research question and null hypothesis one which revealed mean score of 61.4 and calculated p-value of .641. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of .614 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. This finding agrees with the report of

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Ibrahim and Usman (2015) who reported that entry grades especially credit and above have influence on overall academic success of college students irrespective of the learning strategy used. It is also reported that credit and above entry grades at ordinary level in Principles of Accounting significantly influenced students' academic performance in Advanced Financial Accounting (Daniel, 2014). It is also reported by A.H Hamza, Abdullahi A.H and Adamu I (2021) who's conducted a researcher on influence of entry grades and study strategies on performance of accounting students in federal college of education in north-west zone and concludes that there is a significance influence on entry grade in principle of accounting and students' performance. This finding also agreed with report of Saljo and Marton in Umar (2014), deep learning is seen as the most productive and most suitable study learning approach in academic success. It was also reported by Ladan, Adeshina, and Udoh, (2015) which revealed that, students' accounting entry grades of credit had significant relationship with their performance in Principles of Accounts.

The results of Table 2 and 8 showed that Pass entry grades and below in O' Level Principles of accounting has moderate effects on performances of accounting students that adopted deep study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone. This is so because in the analysis of research question and null hypothesis two which revealed mean score of 53.8 and calculated p-value of .221. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of .221 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. This finding agreed with the finding of Dujkova in Umar, (2014) who reported students who secured admission into tertiary institutions with pass entry grades and below are likely to perform moderate even they adopt deep or surface learning strategy for their studies. Entwistle, in Umar 2014) found that there is positive relation between the deep approach to learning and quality of learning or academic success. The findings also agreed with report of Ladan, Adeshina, & Udoh, (2015) revealed that there was no significant relationship between students' accounting entry grades of ordinary pass and their performance in Principles of Accounts. The study also revealed that there was no significant relationship between students' accounting entry grade of fail and their performance in Principles of Accounts.

The results in Table 3 and 9 revealed that, credit entry grades and above in O' Level Principles of accounting has moderate effects on performances of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal colleges of education in North-west geo-political zone. This is evident in the analysis of research question and null hypothesis three which revealed mean score of 66.2 and calculated p-value of .444. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of .444 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. This finding also agrees with the report of Ibrahim and Usman (2015) who reported that entry grades especially credit and above have influence on overall academic success of college students irrespective of the learning strategy used. It was also reported by Ladan, Adeshina, & Udoh.

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(2015) which revealed that, students' accounting entry grades of credit had significant relationship with their performance in Principles of Accounts. It is also reported that credit and above entry grades at ordinary level in Principles of Accounting significantly influenced students' academic performance in Advanced Financial Accounting (Daniel, 2014).

The results of Table 4 and 10 showed that Pass entry grades and below in O' Level Principles of accounting has low effects on performances of accounting students that adopted surface study strategies in federal polytechnic in North-west zone. This is so because in the analysis of research question and null hypothesis four which revealed mean score of 49.8 and calculated p-value of .081. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of .081 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. This finding agreed with the finding of Enswistle and Macune (2004) who reported that students who adopts surface study strategies is identified with intention to reproduce, take a narrow view and concentrate on detail, stick closely to the course requirement, extrinsic motivation and literal memorization Surface strategy lead to superficial retention of material for examination, does not promote understanding or long term retention of knowledge and information. The findings also agreed with report of Ladan, ;Adeshina, .&Udoh, (2015) revealed that there was no significant relationship between students' accounting entry grades of ordinary pass and their performance in Principles of Accounts. The study also revealed that there was no significant relationship between students' accounting entry grade of fail and their performance in Principles of Accounts.

Table 5 and 11 showed that deep study strategy has very high effects while surface study strategy has moderate effects on performance of accounting students with credit and above in O' Level Principles of accounting. This is evident in the analysis of research question and null hypothesis five which revealed mean score of 66.2 for students who adopted deep study strategy and mean score of 61.4 for those who adopted surface study strategy. The calculated p-value was also found to be 1.96. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of 1.96 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. The report of Marton and Saljo (2005) affirmed this by reporting that students who adopt a deep study approach to learning perform very well in class compare to those who adopt surface study approach. The latter memorize facts but not try to fit them into a larger context, and they follow routing solution procedures with trying to understand their origin and limitations. The finding also agreed with report in Umar (2014) which revealed that the students who adopted deep study strategy performed significantly better than those that adopted surface study strategy in Financial Accounting.

In addition, the result in Table 6 and 12 indicated that deep and surface study strategies have no relative effects on performance of accounting students with pass and below in O' Level Principles of accounting. This is so because the analysis of research question and null hypothesis six revealed mean score of 53.8 for students who adopted deep study strategy and mean score of

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.211 for those who adopted surface study strategy. The calculated p-value was also found to be .081. The null hypothesis was rejected because the calculated p-value of 1.96 was less than alpha value of .05 significant levels. The finding concord with the report of Biggs and Tang (2007) who opined that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of students that adopt a surface approach to learning and those that adopt deep learning strategy provided they are admitted into higher institutions of learning with pass entry grades and below.

6.0 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that, students with pass entry grades will perform well if they adopted deep learning strategies are used and vice versa. It implies that their performance in other subjects at the Polytechnic will be excellent. The study findings revealed that students who adopted deep study strategy outperformed better in Principle of Accounting than students who adopted surface study strategy.

7.0 Recommendations

This study purpose of this study effects of entry grade and study strategies on academic performance in Federal Polytechnic students in Principle of Accounting in North-west. the following recommendations were made based on the findings and conclusion of the study,

- i. The Accounting lecturer should motivate learners with credit and above entry grades in Financial Accounting to use deep study strategy because it has significant effects on their academic performance.
- ii. The students who seek admission in to polytechnic with pass or lower entry grades should be encouraged to pursue deep study strategy.
- iii. Students who had credit and above entry grades should encourage to use deep study strategy because it has very high a significant effects on students' academic performance.
- iv. Students who seek admission into colleges with pass and below entry grades should be provided with remedial class to remedy their deficiency before starting the NCE programmed proper
- v. The curriculum designers should diverse enough the school curriculum to accommodate the proper surface in teaching Financial Accounting.

Lecturers should acquire the basic knowledge of their students' study strategy so that they can adequately handle the students' base on their strategy and abilities in Financial Accounting.

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ASSET-LIABILITY MANAGEMENT AND PROFITABILITY OF FIRMS

ASSET-LIABILITY MANAGEMENT AND PROFITABILITY OF FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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ASSET-LIABILITY MANAGEMENT AND PROFITABILITY OF FIRMS**Abstract**

Research Purpose: This study investigates the link between asset-liability management and the profitability of firms in Nigeria from 2005 to 2019, focusing on the top five profitable banking firms in the country.

Methodology: The study utilizes proxies for asset-liability management, including the loan and advances-to-total asset ratio, bank deposit-to-total asset ratio, and loan and advances-to-total deposit ratio. Profit after tax is used as a measure of profitability. The data is analyzed using the pooled-effect panel data technique.

Research Findings: The findings reveal that the loan and advances-to-total asset ratio has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. In contrast, the bank deposit-to-total asset ratio has a negative and significant impact on profitability. Additionally, the study demonstrates that the loan and advances-to-total deposit ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on profitability.

Recommendations: The study suggests that the Central Bank of Nigeria should strengthen its surveillance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) to maintain the loan-to-total asset ratio at its current threshold, as this can lead to increased profitability for banking firms.

Key words: Asset liability management, loan and advances-to-total assets ratio, bank deposit-to-total asset ratio, loan and advances-to-total deposit ratio, profitability

ASSET-LIABILITY MANAGEMENT AND PROFITABILITY OF FIRMS

1.1 Introduction

Today's business environment is becoming more and more fraught with risks. These risks are not limited to interest rate risk but include foreign exchange rate risk and liquidity risk. Interest rate risk arises from the fluctuations in the interest rate payable by the firm over time for loans and advances obtained. Since the firm is expected to pay an interest on the loans obtained, its profitability is often affected by fluctuations in interest rate which the firm does not have control over (Ogbeifun & Akinola, 2018). Foreign exchange risk occurs because the firm is exposed to risks associated with sales, purchases and borrowings that are denominated in currencies other than the domestic currency of the country where the firm is domiciled.

On the other hand, liquidity risk is the risk associated with firm encountering difficulty in meeting its obligations with respect to financial liabilities which are settled by delivering cash or other financial assets (Ware, 2015). Among these risks, liquidity risk could be said to be endogenous to the firm since it is dependent on the managerial ability of a firm. To limit exposure to liquidity risk, it becomes imperative for firms to continuously seek to strike a balance between their asset and liability components (Onalapo & Adegoke, 2020). This remains the only way to ensure that firms remain liquid and possess the ability to effectively and efficiently carry out their operations (Evans, 2017). This is what asset-liability management stands for.

Given the spate of bank failures especially in Nigeria, it was argued that bank failures resulted from internal and external factors. The internal factors are those factors which individual banks have control over while external factors are those factors outside the control of the banks (Olukotun, Olusegun & Olorunfemi, 2013). Chief among the internal factors is poor risk management procedures which is purely associated with assets-liability mismatch. The external factors include instability in monetary policy of government and global financial developments (Kama, 2010). Even though the effects of the external factors on banks' profitability cannot be ignored, but it has been argued that the internal factors mostly hinder profitability given that they adversely influence the banks' day-to-day operations (Olaniyi, 2006).

The banking sector in Nigeria has experienced its share of failures and distress owing to exposure to poor asset-liability management. First case of bank failure in Nigeria was experienced in 1930. In 1954 alone, sixteen (16) banks in Nigeria failed. Between 1930 and 1959, twenty one (21) banks had failed. In the 1960s, the Muslim Bank, the Lagos Bank and the Berini Bank failed and as at 1998 bank failures had become more rampant in Nigeria with the liquidation of about 26 commercial/merchant banks (Ogunleye, 2000). In 2006, African Express

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Bank Ltd, Assurance Bank of Nigeria Plc, City Express Bank Plc, Gulf Bank Ltd, Hallmark Bank Plc, Lead Bank Plc and Eagle Bank Plc got liquidated (Olutokun, Olusegun & Olorunfemi, 2013).

Despite the collapse of many Nigerian banks due to exposure to liquidity risk, the profitability of banks in Nigeria has remained impressive. For instance, in 2019, First Bank of Nigeria declared a whopping ₦73.8 billion in profit after tax. Similarly, Zenith Bank declared an impressive profit after tax amounting to ₦103.8 billion in 2019 (FBN Annual Report, 2020; Zenith Bank Annual Report, 2020). With such monumental profits, one wonders whether asset-liability management has contributed to this. To investigate the relationship between asset-liability management and banking firms' profitability necessitated this study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Although loans and advances remain an asset to banking firms but if mismanaged it could lead to dire consequences on the profitability of the banks. To ensure that there is profitability, banking firms strive to strike a balance between loans/advances and total assets; bank deposit and total assets; and loans/advances and deposits. Loan-to-deposit ratio is a measure of banks' liquidity. A high loan-to-deposit ratio indicates that the banks' may not have enough liquidity to cover any unforeseen fund requirements while a low loan-to-deposit ratio means that the banks might not be earning as much as it should be. With the loan-to-deposit ratio pegged at 65% (by the Central Bank of Nigeria) with the aim of improving lending to the real sector of the Nigerian economy, the problem is double-edged. First, the banks might be unduly exposed to liquidity risk given that those who borrow may be unwilling to pay back thereby undermining profitability. Second, the banks might not be able to achieve increased profitability at that rate given that it might be low. Overall, it becomes very challenging for the banks to manage the loan-to-deposit threshold so as to achieve enhanced liquidity and at the same time achieve profitability.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to determine the nexus between asset liability management and profitability of firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were:

- (i) To investigate the effect of total loans and advances /total assets ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- (ii) To determine the effect of total bank deposits/total assets ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- (iii) To determine the effect of total loans and advances/total bank deposits ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

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1.4 Research Questions

This study aimed to provide an answer to the under-listed questions:

- (i) What is the effect of total loans and advances/total assets ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria?
- (ii) What is the effect of total bank deposits/total assets ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria?
- (iii) What is the effect of total loans and advances/total bank deposits ratio on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

Three hypotheses were tested in the study:

- (i) H_0 : Total loans and advances/total assets ratio has no significant effect on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- (ii) H_0 : Total bank deposits/total assets ratio has no significant effect on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- (iii) H_0 : Total loans and advances/total bank deposits ratio has no significant effect on profit after tax of selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study covered the period 2005-2019. Year 2005 was considered the base year for the study to capture post-consolidation banking era in Nigeria in which the asset-liability management of the banks were expected to have improved. Five (5) top performing commercial banks in Nigeria for the year 2020 were adopted as the sample size for the study. The deposit money banks are: First Bank, GTB, UBA, Zenith Bank and Ecobank.

2.1 Theoretical Review

Two theories of investment decisions were reviewed namely commercial loan theory and modern portfolio theory.

2.2.1 Commercial Loan Theory

This theory was propagated by Onoh (2002) and postulates that lending activities of banks should be on short term basis since most deposits made by bank customers are on short term. Thus, the theory emphasizes that the banks should always match short term profit motive of the banks with short term obligations of making depositors' funds available when needed. The crux of the commercial loan theory is that for the banks' to avoid becoming liquidated and in order to

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ensure that their profitability is enhanced, the tenor of the funds sourced from deposits and other sources (liabilities) must be matched with the tenor of their assets and in this way the assets-liability mismatch is eliminated .

2.2.2 Modern Portfolio Theory

Modern portfolio theory was propagated by Harry Markowitz in 1952 and it posited that risk-averse investors need to make investment decisions so that expected returns from investments are maximized given a level of market risk. In plotting the risk (on the X-axis) and returns (on the Y-axis), an investor could determine a desirable investment wherein his returns exceed the risk. On the other hand, where the risk outweighs the returns, such investment would not be continued. This theory is particularly important given that the business environment is overwhelmed with risk which firms must overcome if they must enhance their profitability. The only way this could be achieved is through asset-liability management. This theory supports the study because it encourages asset-liability management as the way to choose the best investment from multiple asset channels.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Okwo, Ugwunta and Nweze (2012) assessed how investment in fixed assets influenced firm profitability in Nigerian brewery industry. The study covered the period 1995 to 2009 using operating margin as proxy for firm profitability. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique was employed to analyze the data. It was revealed that total fixed assets and interest rate had positive and insignificant influence on profitability while foreign exchange rate had negative and insignificant influence on profitability of Nigerian brewery industry. The study further showed that inventory had positive and significant influence on firm profitability.

In Ethiopia, Belete (2013) examined asset liability management and commercial banks profitability. Eight (8) commercial banks were used as sample size in the study. Panel data pooled effect regression technique was employed as analytical tool. Findings showed that deposit in other banks and other investments had positive and insignificant effect on profitability. Fixed assets, demand deposits and inflation rate had negative and insignificant effect on profitability. The study further showed that savings and fixed deposits, GDP growth rate and other liabilities negatively and significantly affected profitability.

Sokefun (2014) analyzed the link between liquidity risk and profitability of Nigerian banks using domestic banks and foreign banks in Nigeria as a case study. The study made use of primary data and secondary data for the period 2006 to 2010. Panel data technique was employed to analyze

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the data. Findings showed that liquidity risk had positive and significant effect on profitability of both domestic and foreign banks in Nigeria.

In a different study carried out on liquidity management and its effect on profitability in a tough economy for the period 2005 to 2009, Ware (2015) made use of data from 32 companies. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple regression technique was employed in analyzing the data. Findings showed that cash conversion cycle, creditors' payment period and debtors' collection period had negative and insignificant effect on the different measures of profitability in the countries studied.

Influence of asset liability management on financial performance of commercial banks in Rwanda was studied by Mukasinayobye and Mulyungi (2016) using eleven (11) commercial banks. Capital adequacy, income diversification and operating efficiency were adopted as measures of assets liability management. Spearman correlation analysis was conducted on the data. Findings revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between income diversification, capital adequacy, operating efficiency and financial performance

Ajibola (2016) investigated the effects of assets and liability management on financial performance of selected Nigerian banks. The study covered the period 2009 to 2014 and made use of 10 deposit money banks as sample size. Panel data analytical technique was employed in analyzing the data. Findings showed that loans and advances had positive and significant effect on financial performance while demand deposit had negative and significant effect on financial performance of the deposit money banks.

Evaluating the relationship between asset growth rate and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, Inyama, Ugbor and Chukwuani (2017) made use of six (6) manufacturing firms within the period 2006 to 2015. Pearson Moment Correlation Matrix (PPMC) technique was used in analyzing the data. Evidence showed that non-current assets and net assets growth rate had positive and significant relationship with financial performance while current assets growth rate had positive and weak significant relationship with financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Evans (2017) studied asset liability management and the profitability of listed banks in Ghana for the period 2008 to 2012 using seven (7) banks. Panel data regression technique was employed to analyze the data in the study. It was shown that assets had positive and significant effect on profitability while liability and inflation rate had negative and significant effect on profitability.

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The study also showed that interest rate had positive and insignificant effect on profitability of listed banks in Ghana.

In the study carried out by Ibrahim, Olumuyiwa and Bamidele (2018), the emphasis was on investigating the determinants of firm profitability in Nigeria. The study covered the period 1998 to 2012 and earnings before interest and taxes were adopted as proxy for profitability. Panel Generalized Methods of Moments (GMM) was employed as analytical tool. Findings revealed that long term leverage ratio and asset tangibility had negative and insignificant effect on firm profitability in Nigeria while firm age, firm size and growth opportunities had positive and insignificant effect on firm profitability.

Undertaking a study on effects of working capital management on profitability of quoted bottling companies in Nigeria, Musa and Adamu (2018) covered the period 2001 to 2014 using seven (7) quoted bottling companies as a sample size. Panel data regression technique was employed to analyze the data. Findings showed that inventory turnover days and firm size had positive and significant effect on profitability while account receivable days had negative and significant effect on profitability. The study further showed that cash conversion cycle had positive and insignificant effect on profitability of quoted bottling companies in Nigeria.

Onaolapo and Adegoke (2020) investigated the link between asset liability management and performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period 2005 to 2018. Fourteen (14) deposit money banks were used as sample size in the study. Panel data regression technique was employed to analyze the data. Findings showed that total loan to total assets ratio had positive and significant effect on performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. On the other hand, the study showed that non-performing loans to total loan ratio had negative and significant effect on performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria.

3.1 Methodology

The study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design. The study made use of secondary data which was collected from annual reports of selected deposit money banks (DMBs). The study employed the panel data pooled-effect technique in order to determine the effect of asset liability management variables on profit after tax (proxy for profitability) of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria.

3.2 Model Specification

The study anchored on the modern portfolio theory which brings to the fore the fact that the business environment is overwhelmed with risk which firms must overcome if they must enhance their profitability and argued that the only way this could be achieved is through asset-

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liability management. Onaolapo and Adegoke (2020) specified the link between asset liability management and performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria with the models:

$$ROA = f(\text{LOA, NPL, BSZ}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$ROI = f(\text{DDA, BTA, BSZ}) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where;

ROI = Return on investment (proxy for performance)

ROA = Return on assets (proxy for performance)

DDA = Ratio of demand deposit to total assets

BTA = Ratio of borrowing to total assets

LOA = Loan and advances(proxyed by ratio of total loan to total asset)

NPL = Non-performing loans (proxied by non-performing loan to total loan)

BSZ = Bank size

In line with Onaolapo and Adegoke (2020), the model for the study is modified and specified as:

$$PAT = f(\text{LATA, BDTA, LABD}) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Transforming equation (3) into its panel econometric form, we obtain

$$\text{LnPAT}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{LATA}_{it} + \beta_2\text{BDTA}_{it} + \beta_3\text{LABD}_{it} + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where;

PAT = Profit after tax (measure for profitability)

LATA = Ratio of loans and advances to total assets (proxy for asset management)

BDTA = Ratio of bank deposit to total assets (proxy for liability management)

LABD = Ratio of loans and advances to bank deposit (proxy for asset-liability management)

Ln = Natural logarithm

β_0 = Constant (intercept) term

β_1, β_2 and β_3 = Coefficient parameters of the explanatory variables

e = Stochastic error term

t = time specific effect (t = 2005 to 2019 = 15 years)

i = firm-specific effect (i = 5 DMBs)

By a priori, $\beta_0 > 0$, $\beta_1 < 0$, $\beta_2 < 0$ and $\beta_3 < 0$

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Unit Root Test Result

Table 2: Levin-Lin-Chu (LLC) Panel Unit Root Result

Variable	t-statistic	p-value	Order of Integration
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LNPAT	-4.3379	0.0327	I(0)
LATA	-7.4201	0.0001	I(0)
BDA	-8.0921	0.0000	I(0)
LATD	-6.7646	0.0029	I(0)

Source: Author's computation from STATA 13 software package

The study carried out unit root test to determine the stationarity of the variables. Levin-Lin-Chu unit root test was employed. At level, it was shown that all the variables were stationary given that their probability values (0.0327), (0.0001), (0.0000) and (0.0029) for LNPAT, LATA, BDA and LATD respectively were less than the test significant level (0.005). Thus, the variables were integrated of order zero (i.e. I(0)).

4.2 Panel Regression Result and Interpretations

Table 3: Pooled-effect Regression Result

Dependent Variable: LNPAT

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob.
LATA	0.3414351	0.1242785	2.75	0.008
BDA	-0.2117511	0.0783772	-2.70	0.009
LABD	-0.1388691	0.884631	-1.57	0.121
C	21.93814	5.560905	3.95	0.000

R-squared = 0.6247

Adjusted R-squared = 0.5920

Prob. (F-statistic) = 0.0004

Source: Author's computation from STATA 13 software package

The result showed that there was a positive relationship between loan and advances – total assets ratio and profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. From the result, 1 percent increase in loan and advances – total assets led to 34.14 percent increase in profit after tax in Nigeria. The probability value of LATA (0.008) was less than the 0.05 test significant level ($p < 0.05$). This finding corroborates Onalopa and Adegoke (2020) which found a positive and significant relationship between total loans – total assets ratio and performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. This outcome could be attributed to the measures put in place by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) which has ensured that banking firms in Nigeria operate within profit-maximizing loans – total assets ratio.

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Evidence showed that there was a negative relationship between bank deposit –total assets ratio and profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. From the result, 1 percent increase in bank deposit – total assets ratio led to 21.18 percent decrease in profit after tax in Nigeria. The probability value of BDTA (0.009) less than the 0.05 test significant level ($p < 0.05$). This finding contradicts Mwangi, Muturi and Ombuki (2015) which found that deposit-to-total asset ratio had positive and significant effect on financial performance of deposit taking microfinance institutions in Kenya.

Empirical result showed that there was a negative relationship between loans and advances – bank deposit ratio and profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. From the result, 1 percent increase in loans and advances – bank deposit ratio led to 13.89 percent decrease in profit after tax in Nigeria. The probability value of LABD (0.121) was greater than the 0.05 test significant level ($p > 0.05$). This outcome may be attributed to the high appetite of the Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) towards taken unnecessary risk (especially when managers grant loans to themselves, their friends, relatives and cronies) which often reduces their profitability instead of increasing it. If the loan-to-deposit ratio is too high, the bank becomes vulnerable to any sudden changes in its deposit base. This finding corroborates Ndukwe (2013) which argued that the loan-to-deposit ought not to be too low or too high in order to sufficiently create interest bearing assets and in order to have sufficient liquidity, respectively.

The coefficient of determination of 0.62 showed that 62 percent of variations in profitability of banking firms in Nigeria are due to changes in loans and advances – total assets ratio, bank deposits – total assets ratio and loans and advances – bank deposits ratio. The remaining 38 percent variations in profitability of banking firms in Nigeria are attributed to other factors not included in the model.

The probability F-statistic of 0.0004 was less than the test significant level (0.05) and this indicates that the model adopted in the study was reliable, significant and appropriate for policymaking.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The major findings of the study are summarized as follows:

- (i) Loans and advances – total assets ratio had positive and significant effect on profitability of banking firms in Nigeria.
- (ii) Bank deposits – total assets ratio had negative and significant effect on profitability of banking firms in Nigeria.

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- (iii) Loans and advances – total deposits ratio had negative and insignificant effect on profitability of banking firms in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The study investigated the link between asset liability management and profitability of firms in Nigeria. Given the importance of banking firms to the growth of the Nigerian economy, this study made use of selected deposit money banks as sample size. Loan and advances-to-total asset ratio, bank deposit-to-total asset ratio, and loan and advances-to-total deposit ratio were adopted as measures of asset liability management while profit after tax was used as measure of profitability. Using the pooled-effect panel data technique to analyze the data, empirical results showed that loan and advances-to-total asset ratio had positive and significant effect on profitability while bank deposit-to-total asset ratio had negative and significant effect on profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study showed that loan and advances-to-total deposit ratio had negative and insignificant effect on profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. In conclusion, the study argued that asset liability management determines the profitability of banking firms in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made in the study:

- (i) Central Bank of Nigeria should strengthen its surveillance on the Deposit Money Banks to ensure that the loan-to-total asset ratio remains unchanged given that at the current threshold it increases banking firms' profitability.
- (ii) Deposit Money Banks' management should embrace innovations that would shore-up and retain bank deposits in the banks as a way of enhancing liability management and increasing profitability.
- (iii) Deposit Money Banks' management should adopt more conservative lending procedure so as to enthrone more effective asset-liability management.

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BOARD TRAITS AND EARNINGS CONSERVATISM

DO BOARD TRAITS INFLUENCE EARNINGS CONSERVATISM?

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Abstract

Research Purpose: This study's goal is to investigate how the board's effectiveness affects the earnings conservatism of Nigeria's publicly traded consumer goods companies.

Methodology: The impacts of board independence, board competency, board size, and board meetings on the earnings conservatism of listed consumer products corporations in Nigeria were investigated using an expo facto research approach. Twenty (20) consumer goods companies in Nigeria that were publicly traded as of December 6, 2022 make up the research population. For five (5) years of financial periods from 2017 to 2021, a filter criterion was used to sample seventeen (17) consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange due to a lack of data. For the five-year financial periods from 2017 to 2021, the secondary data were gathered from the annual reports and financial statements of seventeen (17) carefully selected consumer products companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. To analyze the data, the study used robust generalized least squares.

Research Findings: According to the study's findings, board independence and board size are significantly positively correlated with the earnings conservatism of Nigerian listed consumer goods companies. Board meeting frequency and board competency, however, do not significantly influence the earnings conservatism of Nigerian listed consumer goods companies.

Recommendations: The study recommends that management of listed consumer products companies in Nigeria have more independent members on their boards, as this might result in the necessary confidence for stronger financial reporting. It is also recommended that publicly listed consumer goods businesses maintain an adequate board size in order to promote conservative reporting.

Keywords: Earnings Conservatism, Board Quality, Board Meeting, Board Size, Board Independence.

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1. Introduction

The collapse of renowned companies like Enron and WorldCom in the US, HIH, One-Tel, and Harris Scarfed in Australia, as well as several enterprises in Nigeria including AIB Plc and AP Oil, has been connected to an increase in accounting scandals in recent years. Therefore, improving corporate governance and accounting quality is a top priority for authorities, investors, academics, and the public. Empirical evidence indicates that inadequate corporate governance and profit manipulation were the main contributors to these collapses (Oyedokun & Salisu, 2018). Although financial statement frauds and the amount of earnings management are important features of earnings quality, there are other criteria that are as important (Beekes, Pope, & Young 2004). One of these dimensions is consistency in profitability (Basu, 1997). The propensity of accounting, via the application of rules and practices, to understate the value of net assets in relation to their net economic worth (Ruch & Taylor, 2015). Excellent financial reporting includes conservative accounting because it minimizes agency conflicts by requiring managers to report negative news sooner than favourable news, which limits their potential to distort the financial reporting. To prevent plans for excessive compensation for managers, accounting conservatism is crucial. Managers frequently overcompensate due to the information gap and the separation between management and shareholders (Watts, 2003).

However, the governance framework of a company may be crucial in influencing the quality of its profitability (Ahmed & Duellman 2007). Because of their proclivity for increased oversight, boards with more independent directors are more likely to expect higher-quality results, as seen by their earlier detection of poor financial news (i.e. greater earnings conservatism). Studies show that board quality might increase the amount of earnings conservatism (Ahmed& Henry 2012; Elshandidy & Hassanein, 2014). Additional research has shown that board independence and board characteristics like board size might lessen accounting conservatism (Lim, 2011). While earlier research has emphasized how an effective board may limit a manager's opportunity seeking and encourage them to be more cautious in their financial reporting. As a result, various institutional contexts have distinct relationships between board quality and earnings conservatism.

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Many studies have looked at the connection between board effectiveness and profit conservatism, and some of their conclusions have generated controversy. For instance, a study conducted in 2014 by Amran and Abdul Manaf on the connection between board independence and conservative accounting methods in Malaysian corporations showed no such connection. Al-Sraheen, Fadzil, and Ismail (2014) found that foreign ownership, board independence, audit committee, and accounting conservatism were all positively correlated with each other in their study of Jordanian listed enterprises. However, there was only a weak and insignificant correlation between board size and conservatism.

Most empirical studies looking at the connection between board quality and earnings conservatism have taken place in industrialized nations rather than emerging nations like Nigeria (Ahmed & Duellman, 2007; Cullinan et al. 2012). Numerous research on the topic of earnings quality have been done in Nigeria, just as in other nations. The profitability of listed food and beverage companies in Nigeria was explored by Bala and Gugong (2015) in their study of the influence of audit committee characteristics. Hasan and Farouk also looked into how corporate characteristics and the profitability standards of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria related (2014). Gberegbe looked at the effect of the book-tax ratio on the profitability of Nigerian listed businesses (2019). Bello, Jacob and Mamman (2019) examined the moderating effect of audit quality on the relationship between firm characteristics and earnings quality of listed oil marketing companies in Nigeria. Salawu investigated the profitability and quality trend investigation across Nigerian listed firms in 2017. The profitability of Nigeria's listed deposit money institutions was also studied by Yahaya, Tanko, and Muhammad (2017) in relation to corporate features. Listed manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria were also the subject of Egbunike and Odum's (2018) investigation of the effect of leadership structure on profitability. In a study published in 2019, Adegbe, Salawu, and Shiyanbola looked into how corporate governance affected the financial and non-financial performance of listed Nigerian companies. The same researchers in 2019 investigated the connection between corporate governance and reported earning quality in Nigerian deposit money organizations. As well as Okunade, Siyanbola, Ogbebor, and Obiajulu. Also, Ugoh and Bello (2021) examined the effect

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of market - based earning quality properties on market price per share of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Although there has been research done on how board features affect earnings quality in Nigeria, as far as the researcher is aware, there hasn't been much research done on how board quality affects earnings conservatism, which is a significant aspect of earnings quality in Nigeria. By adding to the body of research about the connection between board quality and earnings conservatism, this study will make a significant contribution. In order to better understand this relationship, this study looks at the impact of board quality on listed consumer goods businesses in Nigeria. This study's main goal is to look at how the board composition affects how conservatively listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria report their earnings. Examining how board independence, board competency, board size, and board meetings affect listed consumer goods businesses in Nigeria's earnings conservatism is one of the study's secondary goals.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptualization and Development of Hypotheses

In this part, four hypotheses were established and statistically tested.

2.1.1 Board Independence and Earnings Conservatism

The most successful internal corporate governance procedures are thought to be independent (outside) directors (Lim, 2011; Haque & Ntim, 2017). Due to their propensity for effective supervision, independent directors are likely to reduce managers' tendency to misrepresent earnings in order to overcompensate themselves (Lim, 2011). Furthermore, External directors have expertise of the financial reporting process through working as top managers in other firms, increasing accounting quality, and appreciating the necessity of implementing conservative via reporting, according to Hazarika et al. (2012). There are two types of empirical data relating to board independence and accounting conservatism. The first asserts that a high

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share of outside directors benefits accounting conservatism. According to Beekes et al., the share of non-executive directors is associated with conservatism (2004). In order to bolster their argument, they pointed out how having more non-executive directors allowed them to have a greater effect over conservatism and a better ability to supervise management activities. Kukah et al. (2016) offered support for Beekes' findings using a sample of Ghanaian firms by demonstrating how board independence limits managers' ability to manipulate earnings and forces them to be more cautious. These findings offer credence to the agency hypothesis. The second group, on the other hand, claims that board independence and accounting conservatism have no substantial relationship. Lim (2011) observed that in 1998 and 2002, the number of independent directors was very weakly related to the frequency of conservative accounting in a sample of 644 and 774 Australian firms, respectively. This finding was attributed to the impact of various institutional frameworks between Australian and non-Australian firms. Conversely, in a sample of Spanish enterprises, Garca-Lara et al. (2007) revealed no evidence of a substantial impact of board independence on the amount of accounting conservatism. As a consequence of previous studies' inconsistencies, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H1: Board independence and earnings conservatism don't significantly correlate.

2.1.2 Board Competency and Earnings Conservatism

Agrawal and Chadha discovered in their 2005 research of US organizations that having outside directors with financial competence influenced the likelihood that businesses would be obliged to restate their financial accounts. In their 2008 study, Guner, Malmendier, and Tate looked at a variety of financial experts, such as bank executives, financial executives, and academics. Even though businesses' investment alternatives were limited, only one of the three types of expertise encouraged better governance because they resulted in fewer acquisitions that decreased shareholder value or increased debt. Previous studies found that audit committees with financial expertise utilized more conservative accounting practices, experienced less earnings management, and made fewer restatement of results (Bedard, Chtourou, & Courteau, 2004). (Krishnan & Visvanathan, 2008). Due to the fact that users of financial statements

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depend on directors' expertise to oversee the financial reporting process, it is more likely that financial experts would exercise greater caution in supporting directors in their governance responsibilities. The following hypothesis was developed in light of these findings:

H2: Competence of the board and earnings conservatism are unrelated.

2.1.3 Board Size and Earnings Conservatism

In governance literature, the size of the board is a typical board structure variable. Several studies have been conducted to investigate the relationship between board size and accounting conservatism. Ahmed and Henry (2012); Kukah and colleagues (2016). There are two competing hypotheses about board size (Ntim, 2016). As per agency theory, a limited directors is preferable because a big board is connected with communication difficulties, member disagreements, and decision-making delays (Lipton & Lorsch 1992; Jensen, 1993). Large boards have "free rider" issues since each member depends on the others to supervise management when there are many members (Hermalin & Weibach, 2003). However, because of the greater range of skills on the board, a large board may boost the efficacy of the monitoring process and the prevalence of cautious accounting (Ebrahim & Fattah, 2015). According to Ahmed and Duellman's 2007 thesis, a manager's choices are reportedly more carefully evaluated by more directors on a big board. Ahmed and Henry (2012) discovered that a bigger board size increases the amount of profits and book value understatement, resulting in more cautious accounting. Over an 11-year span, they performed their research with 120 publicly traded Australian firms. According to a different line of empirical study, board size has no impact on accounting conservatism. Ahmed and Duellman (2007) demonstrated the absence of a statistically relevant association using a sample of 200 publicly listed US corporations during a three-year accounting period. Elshandidy and Hassanein discovered a similar lack of a substantial relationship between board number and accounting conservatism among some of the 100 UK businesses that comprised the FTSE index over a six-year period in 2014. As a consequence of the analysis, the following assertion is supported:

H3: The size of the board and earnings conservatism do not significantly correlate.

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2.1.4 Board Meeting and Earnings Conservatism

There are numerous points of view on the frequency of board meetings as a tool for corporate governance. Board meetings, according to one viewpoint, provide effective management supervision, strategy discussion and implementation, and the ability for directors to interact and exchange ideas (Vafeas, 1999). According to Conger et al. (1998), board meetings are an important instrument for boosting the board's efficacy. One of the biggest challenges that directors face, according to Lipton and Lorsch, is a lack of time to accomplish their obligations (1992). According to earlier publications, directors who hold too many directorships interfere with their ability to attend meetings on a regular basis and complicate their function in successfully managing management (Byrne, 1996). Based on this notion, members on boards with much more regular meetings are more liable to discharge their obligations in a way that benefits shareholders (Vafeas, 1999). An inverse of this is that meetings of board may be ineffective if the time is not used for an informative exchange of viewpoints among the directors. The CEO presumably determines the topic for board meetings on a regular basis, which is the source of this issue (Jensen, 1993; Vafeas, 1999). Meetings are mostly used for routine business, which reduces the chance for outside directors to exercise meaningful managerial supervision (Vafeas, 1999). In reality, boards should be relatively inactive, and the frequency of their meetings may indicate problems, according to Jensen (1993). Therefore, greater board participation is often a business reaction to below-par performance. The hypothesis is constructed as follows:

H4: Board meetings and earnings conservatism do not significantly correlate.

2.2 Empirical Review

In their 2004 study, Beekes, Pope, and Young looked at the connection between the board of directors' makeup and the level of accounting quality as measured by conservative and timely

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profits. The study's findings indicate that companies with more outside board members are more likely to identify declining earnings trends quickly. However, when it comes to detecting good news, companies with boards that are predominately made up of foreigners do not exhibit more cautious reporting.

In 2007, Ahmed and Duellman explored the association among board of director qualifications and accounting conservatism. Over the fiscal years 1999-2001, 306 companies from the S&P 500 were sampled for the study. The Lexis-Nexis database contained proxy statements, from which the research gathered governance data for the years 1999 and 2000. The study used three different measures of conservatism; (a) there is a negative association between conservatism with the proportion of inside directors; and (b) there is a positive correlation between conservatism and the proportion of shares held by outside directors. The study's findings demonstrate that conservatism is positively linked with the percentage of outside directors who hold stock in a company, but negatively correlated with the number of insiders on a board.

In 2014, Amran and Abdul Manaf published research on the impact of board independence on accounting conservatism in Malaysian enterprises. The study discovered no relationship between a person's conservatism and the board's independence. Rather, despite their claim to "independence," the independent non-executive directors lack the authority to control and advise the board of directors.

In their study of Jordanian listed businesses, Al-Sraheen, Fadzil, and Ismail (2014) looked at how corporate governance matters affected the practices of accounting conservatism. Utilizing multiple regression analysis, secondary data were acquired from 113 Jordanian companies' 2011 annual reports. It was observed that there is a positive and significant association between foreign ownership, board independence, audit committee, and accounting conservatism. Furthermore, the research found a weak and negative link between conservatism and board size.

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Abdul Wahab, Madah, and Haron (2016) explored how Malaysian governance procedures and incomes conservatism interact. The sample for this study was built using 3,183 firm-year data from 2004 through 2009. Market- and accrual-based metrics of conservatism were also utilized in the study. The 2007 modification to Malaysia's Code on Corporate Governance, according to the report, increased earnings conservatism. The findings of the study demonstrated that the competence and financial independence of the audit committee enhance earnings conservative. The study was unable to establish a relationship between conservatism and the mix of financial board competence.

Adegbie, Salawu, and Shiyanbola (2019) looked at listed financial and non-financial firms in Nigeria to determine the impact of corporate governance on profits quality. The inquiry employed ex post facto research design. 30 quoted financial and non-financial entities were specifically chosen as the study's sample from the research population of 161 listed companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2017. The secondary data obtained from the sample companies' annual reports and accounts for the years 2003 to 2017. Multiple regression was utilized to analyze the data collected for the investigation. According to the study's findings, corporate governance (CG) and earnings quality (EQ) of listed financial firms in Nigeria significantly correlated with one another. Board meetings significantly lowered the quality of revenues while board size significantly increased it. The earnings quality of Nigeria's listed non-financial enterprises is significantly influenced by corporate governance. The level of profitability is significantly impacted by board meetings.

On the impact of corporate governance on reported profit quality in Nigerian deposit money institutions, Siyanbola, Ogbemor, Obiajulu, and Okunade conducted study in 2019. Over a ten-year period, the study gathered cross-sectional data from ten (10) Nigerian Stock Exchange-listed deposit money institutions (2008-2017). Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the analysis of the data. The results of the study show that firm size has a negative but insignificant relationship with earnings quality, board size has a positive but significant relationship with earnings quality, board independence has a negative but insignificant

relationship with earnings quality, and foreign directors on the board have a positive but significant relationship with earnings quality.

3. Methodology

In this work, ex-post facto research design has been used to address the research difficulty. As of December 6, 2022, there were twenty (20) consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian stock market, making up the research's population. The sample size for this investigation was decided upon in accordance with the following filtering standards; (i) the company was required to list on the Nigerian stock exchange beginning in January 2017 and continuing until December 2021. (ii) From December 2017 to December 2021, the firm shall keep continuous data for the duration of the five-year research period. Based on the aforementioned standards, seventeen (17) listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria are chosen that have thorough annual reports and accounts for the study's time period and therefore satisfy all the prerequisites. An analysis of seventeen consumer goods companies that were listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for five (5) years, from 2017 to 2021, was done using secondary data that was taken from their annual reports and financial statements. The link between board characteristics and earnings conservatism was examined using Robust Generalized Least Squares because it is often created to give an ideal unbiased estimator of for the case with heterogeneous variance, Robust Generalized Least Squares (RGLS) is seen to be acceptable. It aids in reducing the impact of individual variability and offers additional degrees of freedom and increased effectiveness (Baltagi, 2008).

3.1 Measurement of Variables

Earnings conservatism is a dependent variable, whereas board independence, board competency, board size, and board meetings are independent factors.

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3.1.1 Dependent Variable

Earnings conservatism is the dependent variable in this investigation. According to Akintoye, Adegbe, Nwaobia, and Kwarbai's (2019) study, the degree of conservatism in this study was measured as follows:

$$ECONSV = \frac{BVS}{MPS}$$

Where:

BVS = Book value per share

BVS = $\frac{\text{Net Asset value}}{\text{Total Outstanding Ordinary Share Capital}}$

Total Outstanding Ordinary Share Capital

MPS = the share price on the stock market at the end of a financial institution's fiscal year.

3.1.2 Independent Variables

Board independence, board competency, board size, and board meetings serve as the study's independent variables.

Table 1: Measurements and a summary of independent variables

Variables	Measurements	Authority	Priori/Expectation
Board Independence	Non-executive directors as a percentage of the total number of board directors.	Oyedokun and Salisu (2018)	+ve
Board Competency	Percentage of the board's members with accounting or finance degrees compared to the entire board.	Kankanamage, (2015)	+ve
Board Size	Overall amount of board members for.	Oyedokun and Salisu (2018)	+ve

Board Meeting The number of times the board meets Li, 2014 +ve
 during the financial year.

Source: Computation of the Author, 2022.

3.2 Model Specification

Egbunike and Odum (2019) used the multiple regression model. The model definition for this study was later amended as follows:

$$ECONSV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BINDP_{it} + \beta_2 BCOMP_{it} + \beta_3 BSZ_{it} + \beta_4 BMTG_{it} + \epsilon_i$$

Where:

β_0 =Coefficient of the constant variable

$ECONSV_{it}$ =Earnings conservatism for company in i year t

$BINDP_{it}$ =Board Independence for company in i year t

$BCOMP_{it}$ =Board Composition for company in i year t

BSZ_{it} =Board Size for company in i year t

$BMTG_{it}$ =Board Meeting for company in i year t

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ =Regression coefficients of independent variables

ϵ_i =error term.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The mean, standard deviation, lowest and maximum values of the study's variables are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Summary

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Maximum	Minimum
ECONSV	0.3063514	0.0572084	0.49	0.21
BINDP	0.3806306	0.1629033	0.6666667	0.1666667
BCOMP	0.5777027	0.1331128	0.8	0.3333333
BSZ	5.608108	0.6152751	6	4

BMTG	4.540541	0.8942616	6	3
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Source: Output from STATA 14.

The mean value of earnings conservatism (ECONSV), according to table 2, is 0.3063514, with a standard deviation of 0.0572084, and the highest and minimum values, respectively, are 0.49 and 0.21. The sample firms' board independence (BINDP) ranges from 0.1666667 to 0.6666667, with a standard deviation of 0.1629033, and the mean value being 0.3806306. The sampled businesses' average board competence (BCOMP) score is 0.5777027 with a standard deviation of 0.1331128. The highest and lowest scores are 0.8 and 0.3333333, respectively. The data, however, revealed that the sampled businesses' average board size (BSZ) is 5.608108 with a standard deviation of 0.6152751 and that the greatest and minimum percentage values are 6 and 4, respectively. According to table 4.1's findings, the average board meeting (BMTG) has a mean value of 4.540541 and a standard deviation of 0.8942616, with maximum and minimum values of 6 and 3, respectively.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

The Pearson correlation analysis matrix in Table 3 shows the degree to which the study's dependent and independent variables are associated with one another as well as the independent variables themselves. It assists in identifying the degree or depth of correlations between all independent variables since excessive levels of correlation can lead to multicollinearity, which can lead to incorrect findings and conclusions.

Table 3: Dependent and independent variable correlation matrix

	ECONSV	BINDP	BCOMP	BSZ	BMTG
ECONSV	1				
BINDP	0.3836	1			
BCOMP	-0.1781	-0.1358	1		
BSZ	0.2196	-0.0631	-0.5151	1	

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BMTG	-0.1885	-0.5540	0.1698	0.2658	1
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Source: Output from STATA 14.

The correlation matrix of the dependent and independent variables in Table 3 shows that two explanatory factors, board independence (BINDP) and board size (BSZ), are positively related to earnings conservatism (ECONSV). Although there is a substantial negative correlation between the board's competence (BCOMP) and board meetings (BMTG) and the earnings conservatism of Nigeria's listed consumer goods companies. The greatest association (0.51) was found between the independent variables, board meeting (BMTG) and board competency (BCOMP). Judge, Griffiths, Hill, Luthepohl, and Lee (1985) argue that simple correlation between unrelated variables should not be interpreted negatively until it reaches 0.8 or 0.9.

4.3 Robust Generalized Least Square (RGLS) Results Summary

In the following table 4, the reliable generalized least squares findings for each sampled listed consumer products company are presented::

Table 4: RGLS Estimators

Variables	Coefficients	Robust Std. Error	Z-Values	P-Values
BINDP	0.1418447	0.045032	3.15	0.002
BCOMP	0.0192005	0.0488228	0.39	0.694
BSZ	0.021278	0.009409	2.26	0.024
BMTG	-0.0031719	0.006337	-0.50	0.617
(Constant)	0.1355782	0.0788126	1.72	0.085

Source: Output from STATA 14.

5. DISCUSSIONS

Board independence (BINDP) has a coefficient of 0.1418447, a Z-value of 3.15, a p-value of 0.002, and is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance, according to Table 4. This suggests that a large number of outside directors has a beneficial effect on the conservative

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accounting methods of the tested Nigerian listed consumer goods enterprises. According to our estimate, for every unit rise in board independence for consumer goods, the earnings conservatism of publicly traded consumer goods firms in Nigeria would increase by 0.1418447. As a consequence, the study disproves null hypothesis one (H01), which claims that board independence has little to no impact on the conservatism of Nigeria's listed consumer goods firms. The findings complement the findings of Beekes et al. (2004), who discovered a link between conservatism and the share of outside directors. According to the research, Garcia Lara et al. (2007) found a minor connection between board independence and profitability conservatism.

The robust generalized least square findings in Table 4 show that board competency has a coefficient of 0.0192005, a Z-value of 0.39, and a p-value of 0.694, which is more than 5% level of significant. This result shows that the board competency of listed consumer goods businesses in Nigeria does not seem to have a significant link with earnings conservatism, which is supported by the fact that the p-value is higher than the 5% level of significance. The study's null hypothesis 2 (H02), which states that board competency has no impact on the earnings conservatism of listed consumer goods businesses in Nigeria, is adopted as a consequence of this finding. The study's findings concur with those of Abdul Wahab, Madah, and Haron (2016) but are in sharp contrast to those of Guner, Malmendier, and Tate (2008), who discovered a strong correlation between board competency and earnings conservatism.

In accordance with the information presented in table 4, board size (BSZ) has a coefficient of 0.021278, a Z-value of 2.26, and a p-value of 0.024, which is less significant than the 5% level of significance. The board size (BSZ) and earnings conservatism of Nigerian listed consumer goods businesses may be deduced to have a high association. According to this, for every unit increase in board size, the earnings conservatism of Nigerian consumer goods enterprises listed on the local stock exchange rises by 0.024. The analysis refutes null hypothesis 3 (H03), which states that there is no discernible association between the board size of publicly traded consumer goods businesses in Nigeria and their profitability conservatism. The results of this investigation and those of Ebrahim and Fattah are congruent (2015). The results of this study

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disagree with those of Elshandidy and Hassanein's (2014) study, which found no connection between board size and earnings conservatism.

Despite the initial indication that board meetings may have a negative impact on earnings conservatism, further analysis revealed that this relationship is not statistically significant. The p-value of 0.617, being above the commonly accepted threshold of 0.05, suggests that the negative coefficient and Z-value observed in Table 4 can be attributed to chance alone. This finding is consistent with previous studies, such as those conducted by Yunos, Ahmad, and Suleiman (2014), which also found no conclusive link between board size and profitability conservatism in the Nigerian consumer goods industry.

6. Conclusions

The study also concludes that the number of board members does not affect the level of earnings conservatism among Nigeria's listed consumer goods companies. This finding suggests that while having a larger board may not necessarily lead to more conservative reporting, the independence of the board members plays a crucial role in promoting earnings conservatism. As such, it is recommended that publicly traded Nigerian consumer products businesses consider appointing more independent directors to their boards. This will not only enhance the level of trust and accuracy in their financial reporting but also increase the level of earnings conservatism and improve the overall financial performance of the company. The study also concludes that the number of board members affects how conservatively the listed Nigerian consumer products business views its earnings. According to the study's concluding findings, there is no relationship between the volume of board meetings and the level of earnings conservatism among Nigeria's listed consumer goods companies. Since a consequence of the study's results, it is suggested that more independent directors be appointed to the boards of Nigerian consumer products businesses that are publicly traded, as this will assist to boost the level of trust required for more accurate financial reporting. In order to increase their level of conservative reporting, listed consumer goods businesses are also urged to retain a suitable number of board members.

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Appendix

1A. Data Output

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

```
tabstat econsv bindp bcomp bsz bmtg, statistics( mean max min sd )
```

stats	econsv	bindp	bcomp	bsz	bmtg
mean	.3022353	.3568628	.5794118	5.588235	4.411765
max	.49	.6666667	.8	6	6
min	.21	.1666667	.3333333	4	3
sd	.0563445	.1648772	.1277514	.6034448	.9166985

CORRELATION TEST

```
. correlate econsv bindp bcomp bsz bmtg
(obs=85)
```

	econsv	bindp	bcomp	bsz	bmtg
econsv	1.0000				
bindp	0.4174	1.0000			
bcomp	-0.1366	-0.1204	1.0000		
bsz	0.1709	-0.0411	-0.5488	1.0000	
bmtg	-0.1125	-0.3274	0.0987	0.3102	1.0000

ROBUST GENERALISED LEAST SQUARE RESULTS

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```
glm econsv bindp bcomp bsz bmtg, family(gaussian) link(identity) vce(robust)
```

Iteration 0: log pseudolikelihood = 134.50504

```
Generalized linear models          No. of obs      =      85
Optimization      : ML              Residual df    =      80
                                      Scale parameter = .0026266
Deviance          = .2101254909      (1/df) Deviance = .0026266
Pearson           = .2101254909      (1/df) Pearson  = .0026266
```

```
Variance function: V(u) = 1          [Gaussian]
Link function      : g(u) = u        [Identity]
```

```
Log pseudolikelihood = 134.505043    AIC              = -3.047177
                                      BIC              = -355.202
```

econsv	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
bindp	.1418447	.045032	3.15	0.002	.0535837	.2301057
bcomp	.0192005	.0488228	0.39	0.694	-.0764905	.1148914
bsz	.021278	.009409	2.26	0.024	.0028366	.0397194
bmtg	-.0031719	.006337	-0.50	0.617	-.0155921	.0092484
_cons	.1355782	.0788126	1.72	0.085	-.0188916	.2900481

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**MEASURING THE SHORT AND LONG RUN RELATIONSHIP EXISTING BETWEEN
INSURANCE BUSINESS OPERATIONS AND NIGERIAN ECONOMY, 1997-2022**

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: The study measured the short and long run relationship existing between insurance business operations and Nigeria economy, 1997-2022. The broad objective of this study is to measure the relationship that exists between insurance business operations and economy of Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to measure the impact of Insurance total premium on Nigeria economy, to determine the impact of Insurance investment on Nigeria. Investigate the long run relationship existing between insurance business operations and Nigerian economy, 1997-2022.

Methodology: The study employed the Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) and Johansen co-integration models in the analysis of three main hypotheses that were formulated.

Findings: The result revealed that insurance premium has a significant short run relationship in Nigerian economy, while insurance investment shows non-significant short run relationship with Nigeria economy. There is a long run relationship existing between insurance business operations and Nigerian economy, 1997-2022.

Conclusion: In conclusion, insurance business operations and Nigeria economy had a short and long run relationship.

Recommendations: We recommend that premium charged on various insurance businesses should be reviewed, the regulatory authority should use policy actions to protect both the insured and the insurer, this will go a long way to encourage people to patronize insurance companies as well as encourage insurance companies to always pay genuine claims. This will also encourage more people to buy insurance, thereby increase premium income and provide investible funds which can be channeled into viable investments.

Key words: Insurance Premium, Insurance Investment, Economic Growth, ARDL

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The insurance business operations in Nigeria were introduced by British colonial government in 1910. Before the arrival of the colonial masters, some forms of traditional social insurance had been in existence in every part of Nigeria. This was in the form of mutual and social scheme which evolved through the extended family system, age grades and clan union of African cultures (Beck & Webb, 2012). Out of twenty-five insurance companies that existed in 1960, only seven were indigenous and their total market share was far below 10% (Chung & Frees, 2007). The fallout from this was the drain on Nigeria foreign exchange earnings. As a result of this, a parliamentary committee was therefore set up in 1964 under the chairmanship of honorable Obadan to look into foreign dominance of insurance sector. In the end, Obadan committee recommendation could not go beyond sensitization of government over the danger inherent in the foreign dominance of insurance industry (Beenstock, Dickinson and Khajuria, 2012). There was a tremendous increase in the number of insurance companies in Nigeria financial market following the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in mid-1986. Nwite (2005), opined that increased trade in Nigeria led to increased activities in shipping and banking, and it soon became necessary for foreign firms to handle some of their risks locally. Until 2007, Nigeria had a total of one hundred and four (104) insurance companies and four (4) reinsurance companies (NAICOM 2007). Insurance recapitalization was introduced by Section 9(4) of Insurance Act 2003 with a further recapitalization in 2005 which led to a capital base of N2billion for Life Insurance, N3billion for General Insurance (non-life), 5billion naira for composite insurance, and N10billion for Reinsurance. This recapitalization was affected through mergers and acquisitions which results to the reduction of insurance and reinsurance companies from 104 to 49, and from 4 to 2 respectively (Acha, 2007). And presently there are 58 insurance companies and 3 reinsurance companies operating in Nigeria insurance sector. However, the major developments of the insurance system include the promulgation of the Nigerian Insurance Decree, 1976; establishment of the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) in 1997 and the 2003/2005 Insurance Recapitalizations. (Fatula, 2007; Eze and Okoye, 2013; Akpan and Acha, 2011). Ward and Zurbruegg (2000) are of the notion that

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insurance not only facilitates economic transactions through risk transfer and indemnification, but also promotes financial intermediation. Insurance is capable of promoting financial stability, mobilizing savings, facilitating trade and commerce and ensuring that risk is managed more efficiently with effective loss mitigation, efficient capital allocation and as a substitute and/or complement to government security program. It is believed that the practice and the activities of the insurance sub-sector in Nigeria has played a crucial role in the development of the economy and in managing the risks of households and firms through the issuance of insurance policies coupled with the mobilization and transfer of funds to the deficit unit for financing real sector investment. It is based on this premise that the study will be measuring the short and long run relationship existing between insurance business operations and Nigerian economy, 1997-2022. The broad objective of this study is to measure the relationship that exists between insurance business operations and economy of Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to measure the impact of Insurance total premium on Nigeria economy, to determine the impact of Insurance investment on Nigeria. Investigate the long run relationship existing between insurance business operations and Nigerian economy, 1997-2022.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Insurance business

Anyanwoncha (2008) defined insurance as an agreement or contract between two parties known as the insured and the insurer whereby the insured pays a smaller amount of money called premium to the insurer who agrees to indemnify him at the happening of the contingency insured based on the terms and conditions of the policy. Insurance is a contractual agreement between two parties, insured (buyer) and insurer (seller), whereby the insurer accepts to indemnify the insured in the event of assureds 'contingencies (uncertainties or losses) in exchange for a premium paid by the insured subject to the contract terms and conditions (Skipper and known, 2007).

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Investment

An investment is an asset or item acquired with the aim of generating income (Khan and Senhadji, 2011). In the field of economics, an investment is the purchase of goods that are not consumed today but are used in the future to create wealth, while in finance it was defined as monetary asset purchased with the aim that the asset will generate income in the future or will later be sold at a higher price for a profit (Itodo, Eche and Kamo 2012).

Ikinde and Alawode (2011), stated that economic growth can be encouraged through the use of sound investments at the business level. They are also of the opinion that when a company acquires a new piece of production equipment in order to raise the total output of goods within the facility, the increased production cause the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) to rise. This allows the economy to grow through increased production based on the previous equipment invested on.

The term investment from the point of view of an insurance manager is the conversation of money, the insurance funds and reserves into some specified property from which an income or profit is expected to be derived either immediately or at some future date in the normal course of business. (George and John Clendenin 1974) defined investment as any asset or property right acquired or held for the purpose of converting capital or earning an income.

Victor (2004) asserts that investment involves the allocation of monetary resources to assets that are expected to yield some positive returns over a given period which comprises of the sacrifice of the present consumption for the prospect of uncertain rewards, basically resulting to increase in future output. Linter (1965) concludes that investment can be defined as the act of which involves the choice by an individual or organization after some analysis to place money in investment of generating funds involves deployment of money in securities or assets issued by any financial institution with a view to obtaining the target returns over a specified period of time.

Insurance premium

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Ann, Enwereuzor, Hellen, Sunday and Sam, (2005) stated the premium is the monetary consideration passing from the insured to the insurer for their undertaking to pay the sum insured in the event of the risk insured against happening. It is a necessary element in the formation of an insurance contract. Premium is the monetary consideration paid to the insurer by the insured for him to be entitled to receive sum insured if the risk insured against occurs. It is the price paid for insurance protection by the insured which guaranteed him of compensation if he incurred loss (Uzor, 2014).

Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Gross Domestic Product is the broadest quantitative measure of a nations total economic activity, it represents the monetary value of all goods and services produced within a nations geographic borders over a specified period of time (Lipsey, 2012).

Theoretical framework

Economic Growth Theory

This work adopted economic growth theory. This theory model was developed by Roy F. Harrod and Evsey Domar in 1946. Harrod-Domar economic growth model stresses the importance of savings and investment as key determinants of growth. Harrod-Domar model is a growth model and not a growth strategy. A growth model helps to explain how growth has occurred and how it may occur again in the future. Growth strategies are the things a government might introduce to replicate the outcome suggested by the model. Basically, Harrod-Domar economic growth theory suggests that the economy rate of growth depends on; the level of national savings and the productivity of capital investment (known as the capital-output ratio). The basic Harrod-Domar model says: Rate of growth of GDP = savings ratio/capital output ratio. If the savings rate is 10% and the capital output ratio is 2, then a country's economy will grow at 5% per year.

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The choice of adopting Harrod-Domar theory was centered on its usefulness on the importance of savings and investment as key determinants of economy which insurance industry is one of the contributors to Nigeria economy.

Empirical Review

Ezema, Aroh, Okparaka and Uzor (2023), examined the impact of insurance premium on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022. The study employed ARDL regression for analyses. And the results from the analyses revealed that insurance premium had a positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Okparaka (2018), explore the impact of insurance investment on Nigerian capital market. The study use OLS regression for analyses. And found out that insurance industry investment in the capital market have positive and significant impact on the capital market.

Olayungbo (2015) investigated the effects of life and non-life insurance on economic growth in Nigeria from 1976 to 2013. Autoregressive Distributed lags (ARDL) was adopted given the different order of integration of the variables of interest. After estimating a growth model, the bound test shows a long run relationship exists among life, non-life insurance and economic growth in Nigeria over the period of study.

Taiwo and Olumuyiwa (2014), examined the effect of insurance on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa over the period 1986-2011. The study employed OLS, Generalized Method of Moment Panel Model in the estimation. The study found out that premium contributes to economic growth in sub-Sahara Africa.

Akinlo (2013), examined the causal relationship between insurance and economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1986-2010 using vector error correction model. The result revealed that insurance positively contributes to economy of Nigeria as they provide the necessary long-term funds for investment.

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Eze and Okoye (2013) carried out an analysis of the effect of insurance practices on economic growth of the Nigerian Economy from 1980 to 2011. They employed Johansen co-integration test and error correction model in data analysis and they observed that insurance premium capital has significantly impacted on economic growth. Also, the level of total insurance investment has significantly affected economic growth. Moreover, there is a causal relationship between insurance sector development and economic growth in Nigeria. They conclude that there is a significant positive effect of insurance practice on the growth of the Nigerian economy.

Mojekwu, Olowokudejo and Agwuegbo (2011), studied the impact of insurance contributions on the growth of Nigeria economy within the period of 1981 to 2008. Ordinary Least Square regression model was used in the study. The result indicated that the functional relationship between “the volume of insurance contribution and economic growth in Nigeria is a first order autoregressive model. This model observed that economic growth is positively correlated with insurance contributions. This implies that if insurance contribution increases, economic growth will as well increase.

Arena (2008) worked on the empirical study and causal relationship between insurance market activity and economic growth which covers 56 countries (both developed and developing ones) in the period 1976 to 2004. He used the generalized method of moment for dynamic models of panel data and his results showed a positive and significant effect of total, life and non-life insurance market activity on economic growth.

Haiss and Sumegi (2008) also applied a cross country panel data analysis from 29 European countries in the period 1992 to 2005 to study the relationship between insurance companies and economic growth in Europe. Using ordinary least squares estimates and time fixed effects, he observed that there is a positive impact of life insurance in GDP growth in 15 European countries; while general insurance has a larger impact in Central and Eastern Europe.

Wadlamannati (2008) examined the effects of insurance growth and reforms along other relevant control variables on economic development in India within the period 1980 to 2006. He used the

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penetration (life, general and total insurance) of insurance to measure the growth of insurance. Using ordinary least square, co-integration analysis and error correction models, the study showed that reforms in the insurance sector do not affect economic activities; but their growth has a positive impact on economic growth.

Peter and Kjell (2006) worked on the relationship between insurance and economic growth by applying a cross country panel data analysis using annual insurance premium data from 29 European countries over the 1992 to 2004 period. They observed a weak evidence for a growth-supporting role of life insurance and explained this with similarities to recent bank and stock sector findings.

Gap in Empirical Literature, The study focuses on the measuring the short and long-run relationship existing between insurance business operations and economy in Nigeria. Some of the work reviewed were focusing on effect of life and non life insurance on economic growth in Nigeria, relationship or link between insurance and economic development, insurance sector development and economic growth in Nigeria, impact of insurance practice on the growth of Nigerian economy, relationship between life insurance and economic growth, causal relationship between insurance and economic growth in India. In the above itemized empirical reviews, none of them measured the short and long run relationship existing between insurance operations and economy in Nigeria using total insurance premium and insurance investment. This is a gap that existed in the literature reviewed above in terms of geographical and subject scope of the study which the current work covered. From the above reviewed literature, the most current work done on effect of life and non life insurance on economic growth in Nigeria, by Olayungbo was carried out in 2015, but this work on measuring the short and long-run relationship existing between insurance business operations and economy in Nigeria, 1997-2022. This is another gap in literature based on currency. In the work of Eze and Okoye (2013) on impact of insurance practice on the growth of Nigerian economy made use of insurance premium income, total insurance investment and income of insurance development using Johansen co-integration and Error correction model. But the current work made use of ARDL and Johansen co-integration to

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measure the short and long-run relationship existing between insurance business operations using insurance premium and insurance investment on Nigerian economy. This is another gap in model variables that was covered by the current study.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research design

This research adopted the *ex-post facto* research design. *Ex-post facto* research design has to do with the type in which the investigation starts after the fact has occurred without alteration by the current researcher.

Model specification

The model for this study was specified in line with the works of Wadlamannati (2008) and Mfon and Ikechukwu was Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression model.

$$GDP = f(PTLIP, PTNLIP, INSD, \mu)$$

Where GDP –gross domestic product, PTLIP-total life insurance penetration, PTNLIP –Total non-life insurance penetration, INSD –insurance density, and μ - disturbance term.

It is believed that with these explanatory variables, we can successfully conduct a co-integration and causality test on insurance and Nigeria economy.

In recognition of this fact, our model is thus presented as:

$$LN\text{GDP}_t = b_0 + b_1LN\text{INSP}_t + b_2LN\text{INSINV}_t + b_3LN\text{INSD}_t + LN\text{SAVN}_t + \mu \dots 1$$

$$LN\text{GDP}_t = b_0 + b_1LN\text{TNLIP}_t + LN\text{SAVN}_t + e_t \dots 2$$

$$LN\text{GDP}_t = b_0 + b_1LN\text{TLP}_t + LN\text{SAVN}_t + e_t \dots 3$$

$$LN\text{GDP}_t = b_0 + b_1LN\text{INSD}_t + LN\text{SAVN}_t + e_t \dots 4$$

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This model is operational zed in a log-linear econometric construct to imbibe the coefficients of elasticity of the variables while lessening the probable effect that any outlier may have. Thus it is represented as:

$$\text{LN}GDP_t = b_0 + b_1 \text{LN}INSP_t + b_2 \text{LN}INSINV_t + b_3 \text{LN}INSD_t + \mu_t - -3$$

Where GDP - Gross Domestic Product, LNINSP –insurance premium,-Insurance investment, , μ - disturbance term, b_0 - is a constant parameter; b_1 , b_2 , b_3 are explanatory variables and t is the time trend. These are usually included in a standard time series specification to account for the omitted variables as well as unexplained random effects within the model.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1 The log transformed Variables of GDP and Insurance Business Operations in Nigeria, 1997-2022.

	LNGDP	LNINSINV	LNINSP
1997	8.3936	9.5187	8.3936
1998	8.4774	9.6586	8.4774
1999	8.6092	9.9796	8.6092
2000	8.8625	10.1343	8.8625
2001	9.0160	10.3783	9.0160
2002	9.3502	10.5170	9.3502
2003	9.5146	10.9085	9.5146
2004	9.8049	11.2197	9.8049
2005	10.0485	11.7104	10.0485
2006	10.3213		10.3213
2007	10.4538	12.7045	10.4538
2008	10.5954	12.7263	10.5954
2009	10.6796	12.7698	10.6796
2010	10.9235	12.7916	10.9235
2011	11.0623	9.6586	11.0623
2012	11.1927	10.1343	11.1927
2013	11.3023	10.5170	11.3023
2014	11.4090	11.2197	11.4090
2015	11.4635	12.2846	11.4635
2016	11.5383	12.7263	11.5383

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2017	11.6518	12.7916	11.6518
2018	11.7682	10.1343	11.7682
2019	11.8888	11.2197	11.8888
2020	11.9463	12.7263	11.9463
2021	12.0786	10.1343	12.0786
2022	12.0786	12.7263	12.0786

SOURCE: Authors computation from the CBN statistical bulletin (2018 and 2022)

The raw data was log transformed to reduce the data size and make sure that all form of autocorrelation is handled.

Test for Stationarity

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Statistic

Variables	ADF	Critical value@5%	Probability value	Inference
LNGDP	-5.235499	-3.612199	0.0016	i(1)
LNINSP	-3.233291	-2.986225	0.0298	i(0)
LNINSINV	-3.102445	-2.998064	0.0405	i(0)

Source: Authors computation using E-Views 9.0

From the table, ADF Statistic of all the variables are more negative and statistically significant than the critical value at various percentage level, and also the variables are all stationary at order i(1), i(0) and i(0), hence, considering these combination of the orders of integration, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was jettisoned in preference for the Autoregressive distributed Lag model which accepts such stationary property combination.

Basic Descriptive statistic/Standard test for Normality

	LNGDP	LNINSP	LNINSINV
Mean	10.56443	10.95091	11.25166
Median	10.92359	10.82179	11.21977
Maximum	12.07867	12.29589	12.79161
Minimum	8.393603	9.366339	9.518786

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Std. Dev.	1.229796	0.963890	1.221126	SOURCE: Author's E-view 9.0 output using data from table 4.1 Table above has to do with the
Skewness	-0.478948	0.015622	0.127764	
Kurtosis	1.841491	1.718285	1.425769	
Jarque-Bera	2.353861	2.712259	2.649478	
Probability	0.308223	0.424803	0.265872	
Sum	264.1108	273.7727	281.2916	
Sum Sq. Dev.	36.29755	22.29803	35.78756	
Observations	25	25	25	

measures of central tendency, spread and variations that was calculated on the various series of data set used in the study. The mean of the distribution measures aggregating tendency of the data. From the table above, the mean of LNGDP is 10.5, LNINSP 10.9, while that of LNINSINV is 11.2. Median measures the circulation or spread of the variables in the distribution. So, the LNGDP median is 10.9, LNINSP 10.8 and LNINSINV 11.2. The minimum of the distribution has to do with the measurement of variation tendency of the data. The minimum of LNGDP is 8.3, LNINSP 9.3 and LNINSINV 9.5. The Jarque Bera statistic is of particular interest which is a test for normality. The Jaque Bera statistic shows that the three variables, LNGDP, LNINSP and LNINSINV are tending to 3 which are sign of Mesokurtic.

Regression result

Dependent Variable: LNGDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 04/22/23 Time: 15:02

Sample (adjusted): 2001 2022

Included observations: 19 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): LNINSP LNINSINV

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 100

Selected Model: ARDL(4, 3, 2)

Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
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LNGDP(-1)	0.355804	0.548606	0.648561	0.5373
LNGDP(-2)	0.931110	0.367421	2.534175	0.0390
LNGDP(-3)	-0.243146	0.740450	-0.328375	0.7522
LNGDP(-4)	-0.122882	0.321133	-0.382653	0.7133
LNINSP	0.189694	0.135160	1.403480	0.0202
LNINSP(-1)	0.099665	0.175608	0.567543	0.5881
LNINSP(-2)	0.014334	0.024269	0.590642	0.5733
LNINSP(-3)	0.004354	0.023074	0.188717	0.8557
LNINSINV	-0.012386	0.017657	-0.701464	0.5057
LNINSINV(-1)	-0.129150	0.102249	-1.263099	0.2470
LNINSINV(-2)	-0.063804	0.131700	-0.484464	0.6428
C	-0.090260	0.640131	-0.141002	0.8918
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.798776	Mean dependent var	10.98519	
Adjusted R-squared	0.896852	S.D. dependent var	0.975641	
S.E. of regression	0.054743	Akaike info criterion	-2.707693	
Sum squared resid	0.020978	Schwarz criterion	-2.111205	
Log likelihood	37.72308	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.606744	
F-statistic	519.1171	Durbin-Watson stat	1.873319	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Source: Authors' E-view 9.0 output using, 2022.

From the Autoregressive distributed lag regression result shown above, we have R-square value of 79% which shows that the independent variables jointly explain about 79% of Gross domestic product (GDP). The adjusted R-squared which is 89% indicates that with inclusion of more variables, the R can reduce maximally to 80%. Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.87 indicates that there is no suspicion of autocorrelation in the model.

Cointegration Rank Test

Date: 04/24/23 Time: 04:56

Sample (adjusted): 1999 2022

Included observations: 21 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend (restricted)

Series: LNGDP LNINSINV LNINSP

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

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Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.809570	54.18994	42.91525	0.0026
At most 1	0.425269	19.36205	25.87211	0.2599
At most 2	0.307986	7.731129	12.51798	0.2744

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.809570	34.82789	25.82321	0.0025
At most 1	0.425269	11.63092	19.38704	0.4503
At most 2	0.307986	7.731129	12.51798	0.2744

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

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Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by $b'S11*b=I$):

LNGDP	LNINSINV	LNINSP	@TREND(98)
-0.867807	-5.196455	7.358990	-0.046389
1.656944	-2.654009	2.909695	-0.131889
0.837536	-0.247136	-1.432883	-0.056655

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(LNGDP)	0.048115	-0.034818	-0.003530
D(LNINSINV)	0.112100	0.113903	0.653431
D(LNINSP)	-0.098600	-0.069930	0.014099

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 17.64801

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNGDP	LNINSINV	LNINSP	@TREND(98)
1.000000	5.988034	-8.479989	0.053456
	(0.81743)	(1.11133)	(0.03168)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(LNGDP)	-0.041755	(0.01272)
D(LNINSINV)	-0.097281	(0.25851)
D(LNINSP)	0.085566	(0.02606)

2 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 23.46348

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNGDP	LNINSINV	LNINSP	@TREND(98)

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1.000000	0.000000	-0.404157 (0.24200)	-0.051518 (0.02942)
0.000000	1.000000	-1.348662 (0.05053)	0.017531 (0.00614)
Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)			
D(LNGDP)	-0.099446 (0.02205)	-0.157621 (0.06878)	
D(LNINSINV)	0.091450 (0.55463)	-0.884821 (1.73021)	
D(LNINSP)	-0.030304 (0.04568)	0.697965 (0.14249)	

Source: Author's E-View 9.0 output using data from table 4.1

5.0 Result

Based on the analyses of data and test of hypotheses done in section four above, the following findings were summarized as follows: Insurance total premium has a significant short run relationship with economy in Nigeria. Given the probability value of t-statistic which is significant i.e $0.0203 < 0.05$ which is significant. Insurance investment did not have short run relationship existing with economy in Nigeria. Given the probability value of t-statistic which is non-significant i.e $0.5057 > 0.05$ which is non-significant. Insurance total premium and insurance investment have a long run relationship existing with economy in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of the study we therefore draw a conclusion that insurance total premium has significant short run relationship with economy in Nigeria, while insurance investment had non-significant short run relationship with economy in Nigeria for the selected period examined, which is 1997-2022.

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

The premium charged on the various life insurance should be reduced, so that it can encourage more individuals and companies in insuring their property. The federal government should use

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policy actions to protect both the insurers and the insured in the country; encourage people to patronize insurance companies as well as encourage insurance companies to always pay genuine claims promptly at the occurrence of the event insured against. This will encourage more people to buy insurance, thereby increase premium income and provide investible funds which can be directed into lucrative investments. Insurance investment had non- significant short run relationship with economy in Nigeria economy. The federal government should use regulations to put under check the excesses of managers of insurance companies in the country to ensure that the pooled funds are not pocketed or personally used but objectively directed into investments that would better the lot of the entire stakeholders of the insurance companies and as well to Nigeria economy.

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**INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED QUALITY ON NURSING MOTHERS' BRAND
LOYALTY FOR DIAPERS IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: The importance of brand loyalty in the marketing world can never be overemphasized. This is because it directly influences corporate performance and sustainability, as the more customer return the higher the performance of the company. This study was designed to assess the influence of perceived product quality and loyalty of nursing mothers towards diaper brands in Nigeria.

Methodology: 180 valid responses were gathered across Enugu State of Nigeria.

Findings: The findings from the study revealed that product quality has significant positive influence on the loyalty of nursing mothers towards diapers brands.

Recommendations: Therefore, companies that are in this sector are expected to integrate measures designed to improve their product quality if they are to be sustainable. However, since the study was limited in scope, it was further suggested that related studies should be conducted with more variables and across more states of Nigeria to ensure applicability of the findings from this present study.

Key words: Baby Diapers, Brands, Customers, Loyalty, Nursing Mothers, Products, Quality

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1. Introduction

Brand loyalty serves as the driving force behind a consumer's belief that a particular product possesses the essential attributes, laying the foundation for their future purchasing patterns. According to Holt (2004), brand loyalty represents a consumer's willingness to stick with a brand, even in the face of compelling offerings from competitors, offerings that would be equally appealing if the consumer and the brand did not share a history together. Kabiraj and Shanmugan (2011) define brand loyalty as a conscious or subconscious decision made by consumers, expressed through their intentions or actions, to consistently choose a specific brand for repurchase. Thiele and Bennett (2001) further highlight that consumers exhibit distinct attitudes when it comes to durable goods versus consumption goods.

In the words of Son (2010), brand loyalty is characterized by a strong commitment to continue purchasing or patronizing a favored product in the future. Mokhtar, Amjad, and Husain (2000) contend that brand loyalty not only yields profits but also contributes to the future growth of an organization. Jacopy and Kyner (1973) define brand loyalty as observable behavioral responses toward a brand, signifying that it entails customers repeatedly buying a particular product over time. Aawan and Rehman (2014) emphasize that brand loyalty results in customers consistently choosing their preferred brand for purchase. It is a scenario where consumers hesitate to buy and consume products from brands they do not trust.

The global baby diaper industry is experiencing rapid expansion, as indicated by Shrestha in 2018. A significant driving factor behind this growth is the increasing baby population in developing countries, coinciding with a notable rise in the disposable income of parents in these regions. Furthermore, the influx of women into the mainstream workforce has contributed to the expansion of the baby care market, as it has led to a growth in the average family disposable income. Notably, the baby care market is also witnessing a surge in specialized products designed specifically for babies, such as baby cosmetics and diapers. These products are formulated with ingredients that pose no harm to the health of infants.

Over time, there has been a significant transition among nursing mothers worldwide, shifting from using cloth napkins to opting for disposable diapers for their babies. This transformation is primarily driven by concerns about hygiene and the convenience it offers, particularly for modern women, including those who work outside the home. The inception of disposable diapers can be traced back to 1942 when Paulistróm introduced the first version, crafted from paper. In 1947, Valerie Gordon invented the Paddi, constructed from materials like nylon, parachute fabric, and wool. Subsequently, in 1948, Johnson & Johnson joined the ranks of producers manufacturing disposable diapers (Mohammed, 2022). These three pioneering producers dominated the market until Pampers made history with the launch of their initial diaper in 1961.

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The global baby diaper market is projected to reach an estimated value of approximately 70.2 billion U.S. dollars by 2028. This represents an increase of nearly 20 billion U.S. dollars over a 12-year forecast period. The leading product category within this industry is disposable baby diapers, which accounts for roughly 65 percent of the global market share. In contrast, biodegradable diapers hold the smallest market share, at approximately 3.5 percent (Mohammed, 2022).

In Nigeria, the ideal annual diaper market size is estimated at approximately 2.07 billion pieces, but current consumption stands at around 1.75 billion pieces. Prominent brands driving diaper consumption in Nigeria include Pampers by Procter & Gamble, Huggies by Kimberly Clark, Molfix by Hayat Kimya, and Kiss Kids by Bordargroup. Additionally, there are local brands such as Dr. Brown by Wemy Nigeria Limited, Huggies produced by Huggies Nigeria, and several others. Low-end players, including Cuddsies diaper by Rainbow Fame Industries, Nut-Meg, pull-up, True Love, Fit-Night, Mario & Juliet, Tena, Bebem, Angel, and others, also contribute to the market (Mohammed, 2022). However, the most significant challenge in achieving growth in the diaper category is pricing. Consequently, there is a growing demand for quality mid-priced disposable diapers and smaller pack sizes, which are appealing to middle and lower-income consumers (Mohammed, 2022).

Just two years after its introduction to the Nigerian market, the high-quality diaper label, Molfix, has emerged as the dominant player in the diaper segment, commanding 44.3% of the overall market share. This data is sourced from a report by Brand Communicator, which relies on A.C. Nielsen data. The same report also reveals that Pampers, which previously held the top position in this category, now holds a 37.3% market share, placing it behind Molfix. Meanwhile, other brands like Huggies, Nice Baby, Dr. Brown, Dry Love, Little Angel, and additional brands collectively account for the remaining 18.4% of the total market share (Nonwovens-industry, 2023) Based on Statista (2023), the revenue for baby diapers segment in the Nigerian market accounts for US\$0.81bn in 2023, and it is expected that the market will experience an annual growth rate of 12.34% (CAGR 2023-2027).

While a significant number of studies have focused on assessing factors that influence nursing mothers' loyalty toward baby diapers, a review of literature shows that studies focused on the Nigerian market are lacking. In view of this, this present study is designed to fill this gap by focusing on how perception of quality influences the decision of nursing mothers to become loyal to a particular diaper brand.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Concept of Product Quality

The concept of quality represents a comprehensive and widespread philosophy that can exert a substantial influence on a company's competitiveness (Powell, 1995; Sousa & Voss, 2002). Numerous organizations have embraced strategies intended to bring about a shift in their

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overall approach to quality. These strategies encompass various approaches such as total quality management (TQM), Six Sigma, just-in-time (JIT), and other systems with the aim of either reducing costs or increasing revenue. However, according to a survey featured in *The Economist* magazine, conducted by Arthur D. Little, only 36 percent of the survey participants expressed confidence in the idea that their TQM initiatives had a positive impact on enhancing their competitive position (Hendricks & Singhal, 2000).

The literature on quality has extensively explored various quality management systems and philosophies (Crosby, 1979, 1996; Deming, 1986; Garvin, 1987; Juran, 1988), as well as the factors and practices that underpin these systems (Krafcik, 1988; Saraph et al., 1989; Dean & Bowen, 1994; Flynn et al., 1994; Hackman & Wageman, 1995; Powell, 1995; Ahire et al., 1996). Garvin (1984) was among the early proponents of the idea that the sole path for a company to attain a competitive edge through quality is by aligning the significance that markets attribute to individual quality aspects with the organization's performance in those very dimensions.

According to Shasharudin et al. (2010), competitive advantage in the realm of marketing can be attained through a sequence of intermediate goals, including aspects such as perceived quality, the achievement of customer satisfaction, fostering stronger commitment and confidence among customers, ultimately culminating in the overarching objective of enhancing customer loyalty. Moreover, to expand its base of brand-loyal customers, an organization should focus on creating awareness, building reputation, shaping its image, pursuing brand extension, fostering innovation, and enhancing the perceived quality of its products.

2.2. Dimensions of Product Quality

Garvin (1987) underscores that quality holds a paramount position in strategic considerations, exerting influence over product design and the selection of features and options. It also establishes the criteria for choosing suppliers and materials. Adam (1992) contends that numerous companies outline strategic goals aimed at elevating the quality of products, processes, and services as a means to achieve world-class performance. Hill (1994) highlights the pivotal role of product quality in crafting a company's enduring competitive advantage. According to Garvin (1987), customer perceptions of a company's products are shaped by their past interactions with the company and its offerings. He further observes that management requires a conceptual bridge to align with the customer's perspective to achieve genuine quality, succinctly stating that "high quality" means not just shielding consumers from inconveniences but also pleasing them.

To assist management in gaining a deeper understanding of how to attain quality, Garvin (1987) introduces eight dimensions for product development: performance, features, reliability, conformance, durability, serviceability, aesthetics, and perceived quality. The author suggests that, concerning quality management and the design of products or services, management must

adopt a strategic approach to quality and concentrate on those dimensions that align with their strategic goals. Moreover, he posits that these dimensions are interconnected, meaning that enhancements in one dimension may come at the expense of another.

From the customer's viewpoint, the decision to purchase a product begins with the desire to fulfil a specific need. Consequently, the product must possess distinct performance attributes or capabilities. These performance characteristics are accompanied by the features that enable them. Typically, having more features is perceived as leading to better performance. Nevertheless, there are exceptions, such as fighter aircraft designed to fulfill multiple missions like dogfighting, bombing, and providing close air support to ground troops. Incorporating designs to accomplish these various tasks often results in the plane achieving a lower ranking in each individual mission than it would if optimized for one.

Customers also place significance on the reliability of a product's performance each time they use it. Additionally, they expect the product to exhibit durability, ensuring it lasts throughout its anticipated lifespan. The ultimate decision to purchase the product frequently hinges on its aesthetics. If the product is cumbersome, unattractive, or otherwise challenging to handle or use, customers may choose not to buy it.

Consumers tend to form expectations regarding these dimensions through both direct and indirect information from external sources. Thus, the extent to which the product's actual performance, reliability, and durability align with consumer expectations or ideal standards influences perceptions of the product's quality. A wider gap between expectations and actual performance leads to stronger perceptions of quality. In other words, when performance falls below expectations, perceived quality decreases, while exceeding expectations boosts perceived quality.

Over time, the ease of maintaining and servicing the product shapes the customer's perception of its quality. Products that prove difficult or costly to maintain or service tend to receive lower quality ratings. Conversely, perceptions of quality for products that are simple and cost-effective to maintain are likely to improve over time.

Numerous studies offer empirical support for Garvin's dimensions. Stone-Romero et al. (1997) present empirical evidence supporting the multi-dimensional nature of product quality. Similarly, Paulson-Gjerde and Slotnick (1997) adopt a multi-dimensional approach to investigate the factors influencing manufacturing quality. Ahire and Dreyfus (2000) find that managing product design is just as crucial as managing process quality. Sousa and Voss (2002) suggest that future research should delve into the fundamental nature of an organization's products and employ measures that capture the relevant dimensions for those products. They also propose the need to aggregate or disaggregate some of Garvin's original quality dimensions as our understanding of the foundations of product quality evolves.

2.3. Concept of Customer Loyalty

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Scholars have put forth various definitions of customer loyalty (Ali et al., 2016; Oliver, 1999; Schiffman & Kanuk, 2003). In the field of marketing, loyalty denotes a customer's commitment to consistently repurchase their preferred products in the future (Amin et al., 2013; Kursunluoglu, 2014). Loyalty also encompasses a customer's inclination towards a specific brand (Rooij, 2015). Oliver (1999) provides a crucial definition of customer loyalty as "a deeply ingrained commitment to repeatedly repurchase or revisit a favored product or service in the future, leading to repetitive purchases of the same brand or brand set, even in the face of situational influences and marketing efforts that may prompt switching behavior". This definition has garnered broad acceptance among marketing scholars (Chou et al., 2015) as it encapsulates both attitudinal and behavioral aspects of loyalty (Felix, 2014).

Marketing literature reveals diverse descriptions of customer loyalty, with researchers presenting several loyalty models rooted in various perspectives and dimensions (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2003). An examination of the literature underscores that marketing scholars define customer loyalty based on their research objectives and contexts. Chou et al. (2015) assert that loyalty has been explored from various angles, including attitudinal loyalty (e.g., Casidy & Wymer, 2016), behavioral loyalty (e.g., Thaichon & Jebarajakirthy, 2016), and composite loyalty (e.g., Prentice & Wong, 2016), depending on the research objectives.

Customer loyalty holds great significance for companies as it plays a vital role in establishing sustainable competitive advantages (Jiang & Zhang, 2016; Kursunluoglu, 2014; Murtiasih et al., 2014; Wu & Ai, 2016). There are two types of customer loyalty, namely active loyalty and passive loyalty (Kandampully et al., 2015). In the market, companies can have both active and passive loyal customers, with active loyalty (involving the sharing of information and experiences with others) appearing more crucial in the age of widespread internet and social media use (Kandampully et al., 2015). The importance of word-of-mouth (WOM) cannot be underestimated, as customers give more credibility to personal recommendations (Bowen & Chen, 2001). Contemporary customers heavily rely on online reviews when making purchasing decisions (Kandampully et al., 2015). Positive WOM can enhance a company's credibility and reduce a customer's perceived risk (Bowen & Chen, 2001). According to Kandampully et al. (2015), modern companies have shifted from the traditional view by considering customers as "co-creators of value" due to their capacity to support brands. Loyal customers are often likened to a part-time sales force (Bowen & Chen, 2001) and can also serve as effective brand ambassadors through social networks and channels (Kandampully et al., 2015).

2.4. Perceived Quality and Customer Loyalty

Establishing a loyal customer base is a fundamental strategic pillar for retail establishments. Retailers must explore tactics to meet the needs of their existing customers, which may involve creating products that are not only more appealing but also competitively priced compared to offerings from rivals (Loureiro & González, 2008). Babakus et al. (2004) elaborated on how the concept of product quality contributes to increased profits and a larger market share.

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Customers typically assess a product's quality in comparison to what competitors provide, ultimately selecting the most advantageous option. Enhancing product quality, whether in terms of product design or service processes, is key to attracting new customers, retaining current ones, and outperforming competitors offering lower quality goods. When customers perceive products as high-quality, they are more likely to be content and, consequently, willing to pay a premium (up to a certain point). Consequently, customer perceptions of quality significantly impact a retail store's revenue and market expansion (Ryu et al., 2012).

Additionally, Ryu et al. (2012) noted that customers' perceptions of product quality exert a significant influence on a store's image, which in turn affects how customers perceive product value and satisfaction. As customers increasingly associate satisfaction with the perception of high product value, their loyalty to the store deepens. Chen and Chen (2010) highlighted that the three variables of quality, perceived value, and satisfaction play pivotal roles in predicting customers' purchasing intentions.

Perception is a fundamental construct in understanding consumer behavior, as exemplified in classic research on service quality by Zeithaml (1988). The perception of value varies depending on the specific context, such as heritage tourism or community-based homestay visits. Marketing literature has explored how the quality of products and the limitations of purchased items (like souvenirs) relate to perceived value, which can progressively increase. Nevertheless, the role of souvenir purchasing behavior has received less attention in the literature compared to the consumption of travel and tourism experiences. Some studies have alluded to rational perception and multi-dimensional aspects. Perceived value is perceived across different contexts, including tourism, hospitality, and retail sectors. When analyzed, research has identified four dimensions of perceived value: functional value, emotional value, social value, and monetary value. Souvenir value and spiritual value, in particular, have emerged as two dimensions of perceived value related to souvenirs.

Perceived value is a concept in which customers compare what they receive to what they give (Zeithaml, 1988). Pham et al. (2018) have argued that perceived value is a superior predictor of repurchase intention than quality or satisfaction. They have also outlined the process through which customers develop repurchase intentions in the context of online shopping. Customer perceptions of product value can occur at various stages, including before, during, and after purchase. The higher the perceived value of products, the greater the customer satisfaction and their likelihood of becoming loyal customers. Previous research has also found that customer loyalty is influenced by perceived value and the service quality experienced in retail stores (Kusumawati & Rahayu, 2020). Therefore, customer perceptions of product value and satisfaction play a significant role in shaping repurchase intentions. Behavioral intention reflects consumers' desired actions, offering insight into expectations, settings, and loyalty.

Retailers aim to cultivate loyalty and encourage repeat business. Customer loyalty can be assessed through customers' attitudes and behaviors, including word-of-mouth

recommendations to friends and repurchasing products (Chen & Chen, 2010). Prior studies have consistently demonstrated a strong link between quality, perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty across various domains, including retail stores (Babakus et al., 2004), tourist destinations (Jeong & Kim, 2019; Suhartanto et al., 2020), online shopping (Pham et al., 2018), and airline services (Chen, 2008). This underscores the importance of quality, perceived value, and satisfaction as reliable predictors of customer loyalty. Furthermore, past research has revealed that quality significantly influences perceived value (Chen et al., 2020; De Leon et al., 2020) and satisfaction (Loureiro & González, 2008). Additionally, perceived value and satisfaction play pivotal roles in predicting customer loyalty (Pham et al., 2018). Loyal customers are more likely to revisit and engage in positive word-of-mouth promotion (Asghar Ali et al., 2021). In view of these discussions, it is hypothesized that:

Hypothesis: *Perceived quality yields significant positive influence on nursing mothers' loyalty to diaper brands.*

3. Research Method

Cross-sectional research design was used in this case, and data was gathered using structured questionnaire. A total of 221 questionnaire were distributed using convenience-based sampling method across Enugu State in Nigeria, and 218 of the distributed questionnaires were returned. 38 of the returned questionnaires were excluded from analysis due to some of them having incomplete responses of more than single response for a given question. The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula. Questionnaire were distributed across major shopping malls and special stores that sale mainly baby products. Requirement for participation was that the respondents must be a mom with a child aged 4 years or below as the study focused on baby diapers. Prior to data analysis, Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of gathered data. All the alpha values obtained for the variables are above 80%, indicating a high level of reliability for both the data and the data instrument (Song & Sun, 2020).

A total of 180 valid surveys were successfully filled out, with a majority of 66.0% coming from female respondents, while 34.0% were from male respondents. The age distribution of the participants varied, with the largest group being in the 26 to 35 years old category, accounting for 39.0% of the respondents. This was followed by the 18 to 25 years old group at 26.2%, and the 36 to 45 years old group at 14.2%. A significant portion of the respondents, totaling 52.4%, possessed a bachelor's degree or higher in terms of education, while 37.6% had educational qualifications below a bachelor's degree, such as a high school diploma.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis: *Perceived quality yields significant positive influence on nursing mothers' loyalty to diaper brands.*

Regression model: $Y = \alpha + \beta X + \mu \dots$ (For all observations $i, = 1, 2 \dots n$)

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.639 ^a	.556	.552	57.91131

a. Predictors: (Constant), documentary production

Table 2: ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16221.117	1	19110.019	6.103	.004 ^a
	Residual	7711.221	509	3131.060		
	Total	23932.338	510			

a. Predictors: (Constant), documentary production

b. Dependent Variable: membership growth

Table 3: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	14.112	42.533		1.117	.028
	Documentary production	.667	.312	.819	3.710	.019

a. Dependent Variable: membership growth

Tables 1, 2 and 3 reveal the existence of significant relationship between the variables ($R^2_{\text{calc}} = .556, F = 6.103 >$ at $p < 0.05$). The significant level was found to be 0.04, and due to this we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate one which states *that perceived product quality has significant positive influence on loyalty of nursing mothers towards baby diaper brands in Nigeria.*

5. Summary of Findings, Limitations, Conclusion and Recommendations

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of perceived product quality on the loyalty of nursing mothers to specific baby diaper brands in Nigeria. To achieve this goal, we analyzed 180 valid responses collected through a convenience-based sampling method in Enugu State, Nigeria.

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The hypothesis testing, conducted through regression analysis, demonstrated that product quality has a positive and significant influence on nursing mothers' decision to remain loyal to a particular diaper brand in Nigeria. This outcome aligns with findings from other studies (such as Kusumawati & Rahayu, 2020; Pham et al., 2018; Jeong & Kim, 2019; Suhartanto et al., 2020), which also emphasized the significant impact of product quality on customer loyalty to specific brands.

It's important to note that this study has certain limitations. Primarily, it focuses solely on product quality as a determinant of customer loyalty, while there are numerous other factors at play. Additionally, the study was confined to a single state, Enugu, which limits the geographical diversity of the respondents. However, this approach was deliberate, aiming to provide a more focused and clear examination of a specific variable within a particular state.

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the quality of baby diapers does influence the loyalty of nursing mothers towards particular brands in Nigeria. Therefore, companies looking to maintain brand loyalty in this sector should prioritize the production of high-quality products. Nonetheless, future research should consider expanding the scope of variables under assessment (beyond product quality) and broadening the geographical area of study (beyond one state) to enhance our understanding of the factors influencing customer loyalty and ensure more comprehensive findings applicable across the entirety of Nigeria.

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Evaluating The Impacts of Externalities on Organisational Growth and Survival

(A Study of Selected Firms in Nigeria)

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: The study investigated the impact of externalities on organizational growth and survival in Nigeria.

Methodology: The externalities as the predictor variables were operationalized using competitors, legal environment and survival was operationalized using high market share, shareholders' wealth. The sample size was determined using Yamane formula. The data used for this study was generated from 90 selected senior and junior staff in the managerial cadre of three firms in Nigeria, West Africa. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design. The alternate hypotheses were tested with 0.05% level of significance using structural equation modeling (SEM) in order to evaluate the significance of the relationship between the dimension of externalities and organizational growth and survival. The analysis was done using SMART-PLS 3.0.

Findings: The findings shows that high level of: (i) competitors have a significant influence on high market shares, (ii) legal environment have a significant influence on shareholders wealth.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the adoption of environmental scanning and SWOT analysis are imperative tool to understanding the external environment and enabling organizations to set up strategies for survival and growth.

Recommendations: It was recommended that, (i) organizations should adopt healthy competitive strategy that is dynamic to respond to environmental changes and competitor strategies. (ii) Organization should not only place more emphasis on the legal environment but should set up legal department that can come up with the best internal legal mechanism that will guide the operations of the organization.

Keywords: *Competitors, Market Share, Growth and Externalities.*

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1.1 Introduction

Organizations operate in a dynamic business environment; they do not operate in a vacuum. The external environment includes all the factors outside the organization which provide opportunities or pose threats to the organization (AzharKazmi, 2008). These externalities have direct impact on the decision and actions of managers and are directly important to the achievement of the organizational goals.

Iguisi (2021) stated that the external environment includes these broad external conditions that may affect the organization: economic, political/legal, socio-cultural, demographic, technological and global conditions. Organizations don't have control over the external environmental factors that affect businesses, and these factors not only that it is beyond the control of management, but it also changes constantly. Thus, for an organization to remain competitive in business, they must continuously study the environment, build competitive strategy, and adapt their businesses accordingly.

Every business environment comes with an innovative way of thinking about the business environment and new methods of acting (Belohla,1996). Hence, in evaluating the impacts of externalities on organizational survival and growth, the story will be different in developing economies like Nigeria, Ghana, Togo and some other West African countries when compared to developed economies like USA, UK, France and other countries of the west. The negative impact of these externalities has made only a few African brands to grow into multinational brands. This has made Africa businesses to have slow growth rate in international business. Economic growth in most developing economies, such as Nigeria is always slow or stagnant; this is because of several environmental factors and of whom one is inadequate infrastructure (Glover, 2012). Thus, Government lacks the political will to invest funds in providing the needed basic infrastructure for businesses to thrive, most African countries especially Nigeria has been operating a mono-economy and efforts to diversify the economy by creating the enabling environment for other sectors to grow has been suffering setbacks. In Nigeria, the biggest sector that generates 70% of her revenue is the oil sector and this has been the case for over 20 years. Crude oil makes up 70% of Nigeria's export and all efforts to diversify the economy and grow other sectors has been a struggling one. Experiences of losses of industrial activities by Nigeria has been the order of the day; this is due to the poor state of the country's economic environment, such as, foreign exchange rate, high interest rate and also the poor power generation capacity of electricity with over 60% percent of the population having no access to electricity (Gboyega, 2013). This has not only affected the production capacity of business organization but has increased their overhead cost, thus, reducing the amount of profit that would have been generated. Nigerian banks' lending rates are above 20 percent which is described as too high (Sokefun, 2013). Local investors have been subjected to experiencing difficulties with the current rates of interest. The high interest rates have continued to discourage existing and prospective investors from approaching banks for loans which is to be used for either business starts up or expansion of the organization.

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Technology has a significant impact on organization productivity in terms of high market share, increase sales and quality products/services. Technological advancements not only connect the world at incredible speed but also aid in the increased quality of products, information gathering and R&D (Fred & Jonathan, 2012). Developing economies have not yet experienced technological freedom unlike the developed economies, this has made countries like Nigeria, Ghana, Togo, all in West Africa to depend on technological imports from China and some countries of the West like USA. Apart from the high cost of technological inputs that the organization needs, the organization sometimes might spend more in paying foreigners to maintain some of those technological inputs, this is due to lack of or insufficient indigenous manpower that are available to maintain and operate such innovative technology. The cost of maintenance and importing technology from technologically advanced countries affects the competitiveness of the importing organization in global market. So many organizations in Africa have liquidated because of inability to be technologically advanced.

Domestic and International political environment has continued to influence organization growth. The war in Ukraine and Russia has continued to affect business organization all over the world. The political unrest between both nations has led to the increase in the prices of crude oil and shortage of supply in gas to most European nations. This has affected the production abilities of firms in Europe and other parts of the world. Countries all over the world have always clamored for political stability as this brings economic development. The political unrest between Ukraine and Russia is having negative impacts on some organizations all around the world.

The legal and regulatory environment affects how organizations carry out businesses; this also has a significant impact on the productivity, market share and profit maximization of any organization. Both domestic and international laws have direct impact on business growth. This law ranges from labor law, tax law, and treaties and conventions. Organizations operate within the ambit of the law. Organizational growth has continued to also be influenced by social/cultural environment. This includes social factors like customs, traditions, values, literacy, life expectancy etc. The value and social structure that a society holds have immense influence on the functioning of the organization. Due to the impacts of Externalities on organizational survival and growth, organizations are encouraged to continuously carry out Environmental Scanning. Environmental scanning is a process by which the environment is monitored by organization to identify opportunities and threats affecting their business for the purpose of taking strategic decisions (Azhar, 2008). Organizations that want to remain afloat in business and grow make use of the SWOT Analysis. SWOT stands for strengths, weakness, opportunities, and threats. The strengths and weaknesses exist within the organization, and opportunities and threats exist in the external business environment. A good organizational strategy is using the opportunities and strengths to neutralize the threats and weaknesses, by doing this, the impacts of Externalities on organization survival and growth will be a positive one.

It is against this background, that this study seeks to evaluate the impacts of Externalities on organization survival and growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The impacts of Externalities on organizational growth and survival are supposed to bring about organizational survival and growth, but due to the dynamic nature of the business environment only a few organizations in the developing economies have been able to survive both in the domestic and the international business arena. Those who have managed to survive were able to build up strategy to adapt to the ever-changing business environment.

Unfortunately, in the developing economies like Nigeria, the economy has a great level of infrastructural deficit, and this has an effect in the economic growth and human capital development in Nigeria (Ajayi, 2010). According to (Bello, 2012) the infrastructural decay is the major constraint that has made the vision of Nigeria in becoming one of the largest economies by 2020 to suffer challenges. Most developing economies are suffering from instability in foreign exchange rate, political instability, poor legal and regulatory framework, global competition, among others; these have hindered the survival and growth of most existing businesses and have discouraged prospective investors from investing in such economies.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the impacts of externalities on organization survival and growth and come up with better strategies and framework that will aid organizations to survive the dynamic business environment and experience growth in terms of profit maximization, increase sales, high market shares, among others.

1.3 Objective/Purpose of the Study

- i. Ascertain the relationship between competitors and high market share
- ii. Determine the relationship between the legal environment and maximization of shareholders' wealth.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between competitors and high market share?
- ii. What is the relationship between the legal environment and maximization of shareholders' wealth?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

- i. There is a significant relationship between competitors and high market share.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between the legal environment and maximization of shareholders' wealth

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 The Concept of Externalities

Iguisi (2021) noted that organizational factors that are most important that are affected by changes in the external environment are jobs and employment. A typical illustration is the, economic decline that can result to higher unemployment and place challenges on staffing and production quotas for managers. External environment does not only have an effect on the

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numbers of jobs available, but it has an impact on the determinant of job creation, how such jobs are managed and the survival and growth of the organization.

Azhar (2008) in trying to explain how complex an environment is, he stated that, the environment is made up of numbers of factors, events, conditions and influences arising from various sources. All these factors do not exist in solitude, but interact with each other to create entirely new sets of influences. To have an understanding at a glimpse on what factors comprises a given environment is difficult. An environment is complex and can be easily understood in parts but difficult to grasp in its totality. Due to the complex nature of the environment, its dynamic nature, its multifaceted nature and its far-reaching impact, dividing it into external and internal components enables us to understand it better (Azhar, 2008). For the sake of this study, externalities comprise of competitors, legal environment, economic environment, technological environment and global environment.

Other researchers (Adagba&Shakespande, 2017) opined that external environment factors bear more relevance to business strategic management. Specifically, the analysis has shown that organizations don't have direct control or influences over their external environment, unlike their internal environment. Thus, the need for strategic management skills and expertise in analyzing the business environment in order to successfully harness the opportunities provided by the business environment in order to achieve the organization goals in the face of threats in the environment will always be relevant to the survival and growth of the organization.

2.1.2 Dimension of Externalities

Competitors: The first dimension of externalities examined in this study is competitors. Business exists among other factors simply to make profit. For an organization to make profits they should be able hold a sizeable share of the market and to achieve this, they must scan the environment to lookout for strengths and weaknesses of their competitors in order to outsmart their competitors in the battle for increased market share (Ugiagbe&Irechukwu, 2017). In a capitalist driven economy, any organization that is not ready to compete will be said to suffer stagnant or slow growth, such organization will be knocked off the market due to competition. In a study by researchers in the banking sector that was aimed at investigating competition-fragility, it was discovered that, the competition-stability view indicated that competition leads to lower loan interest rate and consequently lower moral hazard and adverse selection problems and less risky loan portfolios. The result from the study showed that, the overall relationship between competition and financial performance of banks is negative. The study therefore concluded that competition has a negative effect on the financial performance of banks in Nigeria (Onipe, Lamidi, Musa, Isah, BKU, 2015).

Legal Environment: the changes in Policy formulation can lead to opportunities for some firms, and threats to others (Urieto, 1999). Some of the factors in the legal environment that can pose as threats or opportunities to business are consumer law, environment law, discrimination law, employment and labor law, health and safety law. The operations of an organization, its cost, and demand for its products can be affected by these factors in the legal environment.

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Ugiagbe and Irechukwu (2012), they stated that Government functions as regulatory body that makes regulatory laws which affect businesses either negatively or positively. In Africa and Nigeria in particular, majority of the organizations sponsor political parties and their candidates during electioneering period, and this pushes the organization risk facing stringent regulatory laws and monitoring if their sponsored political party and candidates' losses or be favored with waivers and unmerited contracts if their candidates' wins. The Government of Nigeria requires by law that all foreign and local enterprises, wishing to do business must get registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC). The CAC acts a registry for all companies' activities and has the power to carry out investigations into the affairs of any company as required by law.

They carry out regulatory and supervisory functions on any organization/company operating within the country, without registration of the company with CAC, a company cannot operate. The tax laws and other economic policies set by the country is one that is fair and encouraging to prospective investors.

Legal environment influences organization and its activities in regards to having competition laws, environmental law, laws related to monopoly discrimination laws, intellectual property and copyright law, data protection law, health and safety laws, employment law, data protection law, health and safety law (Pulaj&Kume, 2013). The government of any country plays a role in defining the legal environment creates a regulatory framework to protect consumer, investors and competitors and organization. The legal environment has gone a long way to maintain healthy competition.

2.1.3 Organization Survival and Growth

Scholars have used variety of models to examine growth and also conceptualize it. For the sake of this study, the researcher decided to measure growth using the following variables, high market share, maximization of shareholders' wealth, increase sales, branch network and profit maximization. Any organization that experiences positive report in the above variables has the likely hood to survive and grow in the dynamic business environment.

The growth and survival of an organization is one of most frequent topics being studied in recent time. There have been several arguments about it and this has shown how important this topic is. The growth of any organization is related closely to its survival. Thus, the growth of an organization will give a higher stake of its survival in the market. Organizational growth and survival is one of the most analyzed fields in economics and management. Its effect on industry concentration, employment, organizational survival and economic activity has made it enough reasons for it to be seen as an issue of crucial interest.

According to Coad (2007), the neoclassical perspective indicates that competitive pressure will make organizations to go after some optimal rate or size, a proportion for which there is little or no empirical support. Hence, past research on organizational growth has often been directed at quantitative models which were not based on any theory of organizational behavior but rather aim to capture the random element in organizational growth.

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An interesting part in the dynamics of organizations and their growth lies in the organization's ability to learn and respond to their changeable environment. Thus, the growth and survival of any new and existing organization depends on their ability to learn about their environment, and to link changes in their strategy choices to the changing configuration of that environment. The learning and adapting ability of an organization to their environment is crucial to the organizations growth and it is highly correlated with the firm's age or experience. The growth path of organizations has always shown considerably heterogeneity. The opportunities confronting organizations and their capacity to respond to them and shaped by the idiosyncratic and nature of past decision making within each firm, the resources and prowess which accumulated and the developed organization routines of the organization. Teece (2007) suggested that, when seeking to respond to competitive market pressures and opportunities, firms are each typically starting from very different places in terms of the firm-specific knowledge, operational capabilities and dynamic or change capabilities which they have accumulated.

The learning process which an organization needs to go through in order to go pass beyond survival to the success stage of growth, has helped to explain why Coad (2007) study shows, standard regression analysis of firm employment, growth rates based on observable factors such as size, sector, location, foreign ownership or export status often have very frail explanatory power. This is due to drivers of organizational performance that includes unobservable or hard to measure intangible assets such as skills, management capability and different aspects of organizational capital (business practices, designs, and processes). Thus, once the growth of the firm goes beyond the survival phase to reach a stage of successful operations, the question of how to grow further or whether to seek to grow at all comes up.

2.1.4 Dimensions of Organizations Survival and Growth

High Market Share: Every organization wants a high market share, for this will guarantee high profitability. Market share can be analyzed and measured in terms of the unit of monetary terms (sales revenue), the service offered (brands in various forms); the market outreach (market service in terms of geographic area, customer segments, channels, and usage occasions); the time (long versus short-term); and the competitive frame nature (Brown and Mawson, 2016). Yannopoulos (2007) states that, for decades, managers have obtained knowledge from professors, consultants, and superiors that high market share is associated with high profitability. With clear practical facts of the advantages of economies of scale and experience from successful organization, a firm cost position depends on its market share. The bigger the market share, the lower the organizations unit's when compared to the competition and the higher the profitability margin. The contributions of the Boson Consulting Group, added to the belief that using relative market share as a measure of business strength is a good measurement.

According to Brown and Mawson (2016), strategies centered on high quality, may strategically increase the potential market share that a firm can gain. The risk of high overhead cost or

operating cost may affect the competitive advantage of an organization as this may affect the price premium that customers are willing to pay.

Maximization of shareholders' wealth: Shareholders are individuals who have invested their funds into an organization, and they expect such funds to be properly utilized to yield high return on investment. According to Rosemary (2021), when managers of business organizations try to maximize the wealth of their firm, they are trying to increase the company's stock price. As the stock price goes up, the value of the firm goes up, as well as the shareholder's wealth. Shareholders wealth maximization states that business organizations should engage in activities that increase its value and value of its shareholders (Joshua, 2022). Different objectives abound for the advocacy of shareholders' wealth maximization, they are: (i) it focuses on long-term growth and development of the organization; (ii) the interest of various stakeholders is taken into consideration, (iii) risk and uncertainty of cash flows are considered.

2. 1. 5 Externalities and Organizational Growth and Survival

In a free market economy competition has remained to be inevitable force, there is high possibility to have competitions in the industry and such competitors strategies has a way of affecting the strategic plan of players in the industry. The growth and survival of any business is dependent on how well the organization sets up strategies and policies to compete favorably. According to Voigt (2009) the gain secured from competition does not materialize spontaneously, it requires the assistance of the state to set up and implement appropriate competition policy. A healthy competitive environment gives room for the possibility of high market share of an organization that is competitive. The economic performance of countries that have implemented the competition policies in respect to whether they are performing better than those yet to adopt cannot yet be ascertained (Dube, 2008). The inability to ascertain whether or not economies of countries that have implemented competition policies are performing better or not might be as a result of the intricacies between market competition and economic growth.

The legal environment defines a safe and secured place for investment by prospective investor. It defines the rules of engagement. Investors cannot risk investing and growing their funds in a country where the rules of engagement is not well defined. This is because the probability of losing such money is really very high. Thus, the legal environment should be one that reduces the risk of investing. The relatedness between effectiveness of legal institution and corporate performance has been established empirically (Beck, Demirguc – Kunt&Maksimovic, 2006). Nigeria has been trying hard to set policies that will attract more foreign direct investments (FDI) to the country and this has started yielding results.

2.2 Empirical Review

In conducting the empirical literature for this study, this research work assessed the models and results presented by previous scholars that have examined either the impact of Externalities on organizational survival and growth or other similar empirical studies. Guo, Wang & Chen (2017) conducted an empirical study on the effect of environmental factors on Enterprise Growth-Comparative Analysis of Chinese large-scale Industrial Enterprises. They selected

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large-scale industrial enterprises and small/medium industrial enterprises from 2007-2011 with five years of data from 29 provinces and cities in China to perform a comparative analysis. A correlation analysis shows that (1) natural resource and infrastructure environment, business environment, human resource environment, social & cultural environment, science & technology environment, Political environment have an influence on enterprise growth but show some differences; and that (2) partial correlation and regression analysis show that natural resources and infrastructure and business environment have a very significant impact on the results for the two types of enterprises. The human, resource and the socio-cultural environment have no significant impact on the results for the two types of enterprises. Science & technology environment in large-scale industrial enterprises have a better positive impact than in small medium industrial enterprises. In contrast, political environment in small/medium industrial enterprises have a better impact than in large scale industrial enterprises. Akpoviro, Owoturu & Akanmu (2018) examined the impact of external business environment on organizational performance of frozen fish companies in Nigeria. It also reveals literature on business environment, organizational performance and Nigeria business environment. Questionnaire was developed to collect information from the respondents based on a sample of 3 companies with 120 sample size. The Data collected were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The study concluded that the external business environment, political, economic, technology and socio-cultural, etc. have impact on organizational performance. Thus, it was revealed that organizations should understand the implications of organizational performance of their business activities in order to identify opportunities and threats to their business and organizations.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 North Institutional Theory

According to Douglas C. North (1990) the institutional theory is an analytical framework that explains ways in which institutions and institutional change affect the performance of economies. This theory stated that, the consequences for economic performance has made institutions vary, a good few economies develop institutions that produce growth and development, while other economies develop institutions that produce stagnation.

Boliari and College (2007) stated that, Douglas C North argument was because “institutions affect the performance of the economy by their effect on the costs of exchange and production. Together with the technology employed, they determine transaction and transformation (production) costs that make up total costs. The cost lines of information is the key to the costs of transacting, which consists of the costs of measuring the valuable attributes of what is being exchanged and the costs of protecting rights and economic institutions (1990, pp. 5-6; pp. 27)”. The definition of institutions as provided by North (1990, pp. 3): “Institutions are the rules of the game of a society, or, more formally, are the humanly devised constraints that structure human interaction. In consequence they structure incentives in human exchange, whether political, social, or economic.” Constraint is the key word in the definition of institutions. Institutions comprises of any form of constraint that human beings come up with to shape

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human interactions. The author is of the view that, institutions are made up of formal rules created by human beings such as common law, statute law, and regulations, informal constraints such as norms of behavior, conventions and imposed codes of conduct; and the enforcement characteristics of both. The definition of institutions gives three dimensional views: The first dimension is the formal or written rules and it includes: economic policy, political systems, laws of contracts, the imposition of taxes, regulation of banks, tariffs, etc. This can be created by governments as well as firms and other organizations. The second dimension is the informal or unwritten rules – norms of behaviour, values, religions, culture, customs, etc. They are products of shared social interactions among humans and the interactions are acceptable because of the sole purpose of structuring the relationships among people. The third dimension is the enforcement mechanisms – institutions are said to be ineffective where enforcement and implementation are not carried out. The integral part of the institutional framework of a society lies in the enforcement mechanisms adopted and implemented. North was of the view that the main role of institutions is “to reduce uncertainty by establishing a stable (but not necessarily efficient) structure to human interaction” and stated that formal and informal institutions are evolving and changing, thus, the dynamic nature of both the formal and informal institutions has continually altering the choices available to us (1990, pp. 6). The dynamism of institutions is something of steady occurrence since it is a consequence of the inherent nature of informal constraints in societies. While the dynamism in formal rules may occur as fast as overnight; “informal constraints embodied in customs, traditions, and codes of conduct are much more impervious to deliberate policies” (1990, pp. 6). The link between the past and the future are linked by cultural constraints and provide “the key to explaining the path of historical change.” Thus, there is a complex interaction between the State as a designer of formal rules and the society as being bounded by its informal constraints.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in Nigeria to ensure the emerging economy perspective. The research follows an empirical analysis of primary data which is collected based on cross sectional survey design through a well-structured questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire consists of four construct which include construct of competitors, legal environment, high market shares, shareholders’ wealth. The four constructs included their defining variable that formed and explained the constructs. The construct items in the questionnaire are developed on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents were asked to measure their responses for every construct and rate them on the given scale where 1 represent strongly disagree, 2 represent disagree, 3 represent neutral, 4 represent agree and 5 represent strongly disagree. The organization itself is what is used as the unit of analysis given the theories addressed- externalities and organizational growth and survival; therefore, the population for this study is made up of 116 drawn from three firms in Nigeria. Responses were drawn from respondents which were based on their positions in within their various organizations. The

population frame for this study is focused on managers and supervisors with particular focus on the following areas – Finance, Marketing, Managers, General Managers, and Procurement Managers, giving a total of 116 populations. The sample size for the study was determined using Yamane formula for sample size determination. The sample size is approximately 90.

The study adopted two forms of validity, namely, Discriminant and Content Validity. The instrument got received by experts within Management sciences. The Cronbach's Alpha Test was used in this study to measure the internal consistency and reliability of the adopted instrument used in measuring the variables (externalities and organizational growth and survival). The study employed the use of structural equation modeling (SEM) in other to evaluate the significance of the relationship between the dimensions of externalities and organizational growth and survival. The analysis was done using SMART-PLS 3.

4.1 Results and Discussion

Objective One: H_1 There is a significant relationship between competitors and high market.

Table 1a: Construct Validity and Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
<i>Competitors</i>	0.718	0.878	0.828	0.694
<i>High Market Shares</i>	0.754	0.879	0.892	0.695

Competitors and large market shares were measured for construct validity and reliability in Table 1a, and the results show that the study's variables are valid and reliable.

Fig 1: Measurement model showing the relationship between competitors and High market share

Figure 1 shows the factor loading of individual items and confirms the confirmatory factor analysis for competitors and high market shares. In other to examine the discriminant validity of these 2-variable we employed HTMT and Fornell Cornell Criterion.

Fig 2: Bar Chart of Average Variance Extracted for competitors and high market shares

The average variance extracted for competitors with large market shares is shown in Fig. 2, and the visual representation confirms that the data from Table 1a meet the criteria for content validity.

Table 1b: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	Competitors	High Market Shares
<i>Competitors</i>	1	
<i>High Market Shares</i>	0.476	1

Table 1c: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Competitors	High Market Shares
<i>Competitors</i>	0.833	
<i>High Market Shares</i>	0.925	0.833

***[Note: values in italic/bold represents square root of AVE] ***

There was no need to add or remove any items from the analysis because the factor loadings were generally satisfactory. We used the FornellLarcker criterion and the HTMT (0.90) to access the discriminant validity. We can observe that these criteria are well established by accessing

tables 1b and 1c. The HTMT proves that there is a relationship between strong competitors and high market shares.

Table 1d: Goodness of Fit Test

	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	RMSE
High Market Share	0.856	0.854	

Table 1e: Hypotheses testing results

Hypothesis		Beta	Std.Dev	T Statistic	P-Values
H₀₁	Competitors -> High market share	0.925	0.467	1.983	0.048

Table 1e is the test of hypothesis used to access if there is a significant relationship between competitors (CP) and high market share (HMS). The result revealed that at 5% level of significance competitors have a significant influence on high market shares given that $\beta = 0.925$ and P-value =0.048. This implies that a unit increase in the competitors will cause a corresponding unit to increase in the high market shares. Also, table 1d shows that 85.6% variation in high market share was explained by the competitor.

Objective Two:H₂ There is a significant relationship between the legal environment and maximization of shareholders' wealth

Table 2a: Construct Validity and Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Legal Environment	0.781	0.922	0.828	0.763
Shareholders Wealth	0.772	0.885	0.892	0.734

Table 2a is the construct validity and reliability measurement for the variables for legal environment and shareholders wealth, the result indicates that the variables of study are reliable and valid.

Fig 1: Measurement model showing the relationship between legal environment and shareholders wealth.

Figure 1 shows the factor loading of individual items and confirms the confirmatory factor analysis for legal environment and shareholders wealth.

Fig 2: Bar Chart of Average variance extracted for legal environment and shareholders' wealth.

Fig 2 is the Average variance extracted for legal environment and shareholders' wealth; the visual display supports the results from table 2a satisfying the requirements of content validity.

Table 2b: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	Legal Environment	Shareholders Wealth

<i>Legal Environment</i>	1	
<i>Shareholders Wealth</i>	0.331	1

Table 2c: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Legal Environment	Shareholders Wealth
<i>Legal Environment</i>	0.873	
<i>Shareholders Wealth</i>	0.967	0.857

***[Note: values in italic/bold represents square root of AVE] ***

The factor loadings were generally okay, hence there was no need to remove or eliminate any item from the analysis. To access the discriminant validity, we employed the **HTMT** (0.90) and FornellLarcker criterion. Accessing table 2b and 2c we can see that these criteria are well established. The HTMT also establishes that there is a positive relationship between legal environment and shareholders' wealth.

Table 2d: Goodness of Fit Test

	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square
Shareholders Wealth	0.935	0.935

Table 2e: Hypotheses testing results

Hypothesis		Beta	Std.Dev	T Statistic	P-Values
H ₀₁	Legal Environment -> Shareholders Wealth	0.967	0.459	2.109	0.035

Table 2e is the test of hypothesis used to access if there is a significant relationship between legal environment (LE) and Shareholders wealth (SW). The result revealed that at 5% level of significance competitors have a significant influence on high market shares given that $\beta = 0.967$ and P-value =0.035. The implies that a unit increase in the legal environment will cause a

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corresponding unit to increase in the high shareholders' wealth. Also, table 2d shows that 93.5% variation in shareholders' wealth was explained by the legal environment.

5.1 Discussion of Findings

The test indicates that externalities play significant role in the actualization of organizational growth and survival. The evidence of this is in the relationship between all the five dimensions of externalities and organizational growth and survival. The test on the relationship between competitors and high market share revealed that at 5% level of significant influence on high market shares. The results indicate that competitors play a significant role in retaining high market share and they do not just by increasing sales but by engaging in healthy competition. This tally with the emphasis on competitors by previous studies (Ugiagbe&Irechukwu 2017) which describe the variable as significant for an organization to make profit, that for an organization to grow and survive, they should be able to hold sizeable share of the market. Competitors in this sense complete to make profit by gaining high market. competitors in share. The findings of this study also collaborate the study by Onipe, Lamidi, Musa,Isah& BKU (2015) that identified that the competition stability view indicated that competition leads to lower loan interest rate and consequently lower moral hazard and adverse selection problem and less risky loan portfolios.

The evidence from the test on the relationship between legal environment and shareholder wealth the result revealed that at 5% level of significance legal environment has a significant influence on shareholders' wealth. As such, all previous hypothetical statement in line with the relationship of the variables was accepted. The legal environment creates systems that were accepted. The legal environment creates a system that builds investors' confidence by providing policy framework for all financial investors and management. This is evident in line with the observation of Urieto (1999) who opined that changes in policy formulation can lead to opportunities for some firms and threats to others. Some of the factors that can pose threats or opportunities to business are consumer law, environmental law, labor law, etc. the operations of an organization its cost and demand for its can be affected by these factors in the legal environment, thus having an effect on shareholders' wealth. Ugiagbe&Irechukwu (2012), stated that government functions as regulatory body that makes regulatory laws which affects business either negatively or positively, thus this has an impact on the shareholders' wealth.

5.2 Conclusion

This empirical study has established the externalities as an antecedent of organizational growth in Nigeria. The findings of the study gave a premise for the position of this study as it affirms that practices that effects taking into notes of competition /competitors as an important tool for growth and survival through increased market share. The extent organizations grow and survive in Nigeria through shareholders wealth. In conclusion the adoption of environmental scanning

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and SWOT analysis are imperative in understanding the external environment and making organization to set up strategies for survival and growth.

5.3 Recommendation

1. Organizations should adopt not only healthy competitive strategy that is dynamic to respond to environmental changes and competitor's strategies, but this will also enable an organization to have competitive advantage and gain more market share.
2. Organization should not only place more emphasis on the legal environment but should set up legal department that can come up with the best internal legal mechanism that will guide the operations of the organization. This will boost the standard and entries of the organization in the public.

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CASH FLOW MANAGEMENT AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

**Relationship between Cash Flow Management and Financial Performance of Listed Food
and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria**

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: The study investigated the relationship between cash flow management and financial performance of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria, and the specific objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between operating cash flow management (OCFM) and return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Methodology: The population of the study was eleven (11) listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study made use of secondary (historical) data from the annual reports of the selected listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2010-2021. The sample size was seven (7) listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria using purposive and convenience sampling techniques. The research design was cross sectional using time series data. The variables were subjected to descriptive statistics to determine the features of the data, and it was found that the data distribution was abnormal and therefore, the data were further tested through the diagnostic tests (co linearity and Durbin Watson) ,and it was found that the data have no multi co-linearity or autocorrelation among the variables and the explanatory variable was regressed against financial performance measures The software used was Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version Twenty-five (25) applying simple ordinary least square regression analysis.

Findings: The findings revealed that operating cash flow management (OCFM) has insignificant relationships with return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS).

Conclusion: The study concluded that it could be due to the hidden information concerning the total assets and obtained earnings or profit due to the satisfaction of the managers of manufacturing companies' selfish interests at the expense of the shareholders.

Recommendations: Hence, the study recommended that the entire management should raise a solid policy framework that will forestall transparency in the management team by strengthening their internal control mechanism in order to minimize the chances of asymmetric information perpetrated by the managers.

Keywords: *Cash Flow Management, Operating Cash Flow Management, Financial Performance, Return on Asset, Earnings Per Share.*

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Introduction

Financial performance is relative to profitability, and it is the ability of a business enterprise or manufacturing entity to arrive at a profit by efficiently utilized its resources. This is the ability to create value in form of returns on investment from its business activities. Profitability evaluates management efficiency in the utilization of organizational resources in adding value to the business (Nishanthini & Nimalathan., 2013). Profitability of firms is determined by both internal and external factors. Internal determinants of profitability are firm's financial resources while the external factors are industry related. Internal factors are size, liquidity, leverage and financial assets have been discovered to have a major effect on profitability (Nishanthini & Nimalathan., 2013). The performance is the end result of economic production which any firm employs to achieve a target financial objective or goal. The level of success of a firm is measured through its financial performance based on a selected period of time (Liao & Wu., 2009).

Alfred (2007), stated that financial performance is the evaluation of how a business entity has utilized its resources to generate revenues. The financial performance of business entities is determined by the financial statements of the business entities which are collection of reports on the business financial outcome for a given period of time. Moreover, it is a measure of an organization's financial condition or financial outcomes resulting from management decisions carried out by organization members (Harash et al., 2013). A firm Cash flow management policy which manages working capital in the form of cash receivables (cash collection and cash receipts from other revenue) from customers, inventory holding and cash payments to suppliers is broadly connected to the improvement of firm financial performance (Kroes & Subramantam., 2012). Robert and Hamacher (2015), investigating the effect of cash flow management on performance of mutual funds identified that an improvement in cash flows positively affected the financial performance.

Adomako and Danso (2014), noted that the entrepreneurial transactions of business are destroyed when the entrepreneur does not have the relevant skills needed to administer and manage their finances effectively. Turcas, (2011), noted that solvency, flexibility and financial performance of the firm are set on the firm's ability to generate positive cash flows from the operating, investing and financing activities. Wasw et al. (2018), observed that careful consideration and planning of funding current asset management is one of the mediums to determine financial performance and therefore, firms should increase their operating cash flow to positively influence their performance. Podilchuk (2013), noted that financial optimization of a company is usually performed on long-term and short-term basis. The former is aimed at capital structure optimization which is the balance of debt and equity maximization of the value of the firm. Short term optimization focuses on liquidity management.

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Gao (2010); Miller *et al.* (2013) observed that financial performance of a firm is the profitability of this firm given by financial measures. Besides, it refers to the ability to operate efficiently, make profit, survive and grow. Free cash flow is one of the financial tools used to gauge a firm's financial performance. It shows the firms available cash after taking into consideration how much has been spent on development and as well as recurrent expenditure. The financial performance has become an issue of common concern as it reflects its development condition (Wang., 2008; Wu *et al.*, 2010) reported that good financial performance is the precondition for the firms to achieve sustainability. Human capital development has been adopted as one of the most important managerial tools that can improve enterprises financial performance (Ganotakis., 2010; Ofoegbu, 2013). (Jin *et al.*, 2010) observed that human capital is one of the most important industry success factors in order to generate better financial performance. The statement of cash flows replaced the fund flow statement because it is a movement or change in funds, and fund flow by certain standards have been interpreted as a net liquid funds and some scholars expressed fund flow as working capital because of its ambiguity in its interpretation, and the concept of cash generated by operations resulted to the concept of cash flows. The cash flow statement is based on the funds but not in a deeper manner as compared to funds flow statement.

Thus, the cash flow statement gives the overall picture of the financial position of the firm based on the cash like cash owed to creditors, bank loan, taxes and dividend for shares, etc and revenue of the firm. The cash flow statement is applicable for the short term financial planning and it is void in the long term financial planning. The concept of cash basis accounting is applied in the cash flow statement. The cash flow statement can be prepared based on the balance sheet of the starting and ending period, the income statement and some additional data which includes the transactions which is not included in the books. The cash flow statement explains about the changes in these three activities. Among many financial statements, the cash flow statement is considered as a standard one. The cash flows are sources in which the corporate entities, especially, the manufacturing company acquire cash receipts and cash payments for the period and which is subdivided into four dimensions, such as (i) operating activities or operating cash flow management (ii) investing activities or investment cash flow management (iii) financing activities or financing cash flow management, and (iv) cash and cash equivalents. The operating cash flows management are derived from the principal revenue-generating activities (cash collection from customers on goods and services, cash receipts from other revenue, i.e royalties, fees and commission) of any entity and it indicates the strength of an entity because it is an important means of internal financing. While investing cash flow management include the purchase and disposal of property, plant and equipment and other long-term assets, such as investment property, purchase and sale of debt, equity and debt instruments of other entities that are not considered cash and cash equivalents. Financing cash flow management include obtaining resources from and returning resources to the owners, such as proceeds from issuance of share capital, proceeds from issuing

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debt instruments (debenture), proceeds from bank borrowings as cash flows while payment dividends to shareholders, repayment of principal portion of debt, including financial lease obligations and repayment of bank borrowings (Wang, 2008; Wu et al., 2010) .

Therefore, cash flow management relative to liquidity is the management that is concerned with the collection, disbursement and the management of cash in such a way that firm's liquidity is maintained and that is the focus of this study. The objective of cash flow management is to have adequate control over the cash position, so as to avoid the risk of insolvency and use the excessive cash in some profitable way. The cash is the most significant and highly liquid asset the firm holds, hence, proved to be significant as it is used to pay the firm's obligations and helps in the expansion of business operations, (Collis & Hussey., 2013). The process of managing cash has become a major challenge for most of the manufacturing firms, because of its significant impact on the outcomes of a company. The success of any business venture is predicted on how the management has planned and controlled its cash flow (Akinsulire., 2003). Effective cash flow management is the fundamental standing point to ensure that the firm's finances are in a strong position. Managing cash is a real challenge to financial managers as a result of their opportunistic behavior because; most firms obtain cash from inappropriate sources which creates problems in cash management, therefore, bringing misleading investments decisions. Therefore, this study is focusing on the cash flows management, especially, the operating cash flow management because it is part of the total cash flow of any corporate organization which involves the cash collection, cash receipt from other revenue. The gap in this study is that the study is only investigating the relationship between operating cash flow management and return on equity of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Properly, cash flows are the major strength of any manufacturing companies within the country and outside world because it makes up the principal amount from where operating activities, investing activities, financing activities and cash and cash equivalent are carried out to accomplish the targeted objective). In a developing country like Nigeria, cash flows management is the lifeline of every manufacturing company. Despite, the benefit accrued to it, there are problems that actually affect the cash flows management in Nigeria, and they are identified within the business enterprises and they here stated: Manipulation of the financial records by the management of the manufacturing companies through discretionary accruals consequential to their opportunistic behaviour, and third party disguise contracts as asymmetric information (Information unknown to the owners of business) as in the case of World Com financial fraud in 2001 and cadbury plc here in Nigeria (Debt, 2005). Badawi, (2008), reports a list of firms involved in cases of accounting scandals related to poor audit quality and earnings manipulations in the past decade which also affects the cash flow management. In Nigeria, corporate scandals include the cases of Cadbury Nigeria Plc and African Petroleum (Okolie & Agboma, 2008); Savannah Bank and African

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International Bank (Odia, 2007); Wema Bank, Nampak, Finbank and Spring Bank (Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010); and more recently Oando Plc and African Petroleum Plc. These are known publicly reported cases that resulted in misleading financial reports or records.

Cheatham et al. (1989), indicated that one of the most dangerous misconceptions is the common belief among manufacturers is that adequate profits will automatically result in an adequate cash flow. The lack of cash management knowledge and skills prevent the small and medium size manufacturing firms' owners to adequately manage their cash flow. Another disturbing financial fraud that affects the financial performance is the over quotation of the prices of supplying of raw materials made by the insiders who compromise the suppliers. Therefore, for the problems stated above, this study is intending to measure the cash flows management by the net cash (revenue), retained earnings (net profit) of the listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria to determine the relationship between cash flow management and financial performance of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework on Cash Flow Management and Financial Performance of Listed Food and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

Source: Author's Observation Modified by Saliu (2017).

1.4 Aims and objectives of the study

The main aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between cash flow management and financial performance of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Investigate the relationship between operating cash flow management (OCFM) and return on asset (ROA) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

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2. Investigate the relationship between operating cash flow management (OCFM) and earnings per share (EPS) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research Question

1. What is the relationship between operating cash flow management (OCFM) and return on asset (ROA) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria?
1. What is the relationship between operating cash flow management (OCFM) and earnings per share (EPS) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

1. Operating Cash Flow Management (OCFM) has no significant relationship with return on asset (ROA) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
2. Operating Cash Flow Management (OCFM) has no significant relationship with earnings per share (EPS) of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Cash Flow Management (CFM)

A cash flow statement is a financial report that shows where your money is coming from and where it's going. It's also known as a 'statement of cash flows'. At first glance, a cash flow statement looks similar to an income statement. But cash is different to income. Cash only includes spendable money while income includes fixed term assets, long term assets and sales made on credit. Cash flow statements show whether you're able to cover short term expenses like bills and employee wages. It is also useful for investors, as it shows how well your business can bring in money. Cash flow management is the process of tracking how much money is coming into and out of your business. This helps you predict how much money will be available to your business in the future. It also helps you identify how much money your business needs to cover debts, like paying employees and suppliers. Cash flow is the term used to describe changes in how much money your business has from one point to another. Cash flow management is keeping track of this flow and analyzing any changes to it. This helps you spot trends, prepare for the future, and tackle any problems with your cash flow. It pays to practice cash flow management often to make sure your business has enough money to keep running (Ogbonnaya et al., 2016).

Cash flow is the movement of cash and cash- equivalents within the business. Positive cash flow from operations reveals that a company's liquid assets are improving, and this enables the entity

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to settle its debt, achieve profit maximization to shareholders, pay expenses and accommodate a buffer against future financial challenges. Negative cash flow reveals that a company's liquid assets are decreasing (Ogbonnaya et al., 2016). Cash flow management is, therefore, the process of ensuring that businesses have good cash balances to ensure that they continue to stay in business. Thus, prudent cash flow management ensures that businesses would be able to honour its debt obligations as and when they fall due and also to facilitate the responsibility of the firm to pay for its upcoming expenses (Attom, 2014). Cash flow management forms an integral part of working capital management. Hence, it is considered as component of the scope of a good working capital management in modern businesses (Brealey et al., 2008).

Njeru et al. (2015) defined Cash flow management as a financial discipline that adopts the same principles, regardless of the type of business, size or age of an enterprise. Cash flow management would focus on building sustainable cash by forecasting receipts and payments in order to establish the lines to funding with banks and thus managing day- to-day operations of business to minimize the amount of cash required to achieve sustainable business growth. Cash flow management is necessary to avoid mismatches between the timing of payments and availability of cash. Many business firms have maintained large cash reserves and liquidity positions within their investment portfolios in an effort to partially accommodate unforeseen expenditures.

Figure 2.1.1 Summary of the Cash Flow Components (Cash Inflows and Cash Outflows)

Researcher's Constructing, 2022.
Dimensions of Cash Flows Management

Various creators or scholars have measured cash flow management differently according to the aim and objective of the studies, such as Konark., (2018) who measured cash flow by its components (operating, investing, and financing activities), and other scholars in the same direction but this study considered items of the cash flow components and measured the cash flow management as the independent variable, such as equity share capital (operating activities), account receivable (sundry debtors) as cash and cash equivalent and debt instrument (debenture) as financing activities which is also the departure from the extant literature. And they are duly discussed:

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Operating Cash Flow Management (OCFM)

This mainly is derived from the principal revenue generating activities of any corporate organization. It is the critical indicator of the financial strength of an entity because it is an important source of the internal financing. The stakeholders or users of financial statement usually glimpse at cash flows from operating activities as a gauge of an entity's ability to maintain its operating capability and support other activities, such as servicing debt and repaying of borrowings, paying dividends to shareholders and making investment without recourse to external funding. It includes: cash collection from customers on sale of goods and rendering of services, cash receipts from other revenue, such as royalties, fees and commissions etc (Pandey, 2007).

Concept of Financial Performance

The financial performance is associated to money and management of money. Hence, financial performance is considered to be as a managerial transactions or operations of economic agents (corporate entities) which include the planning, acquisition, utilization and apportionment of scarce financial resources. It is also termed to be as execution, accomplishment and fulfillment of corporate financial objective by the management extended efforts efficiently and effectively and transparently reporting the annual financial statements. However, financial performance reflected by past cash flows are achieved through quality information which helps the users of financial statements assess the entity's ability to generate future net cash inflows which if efficiently and effectively utilize will create future value which is also financial performance in regard to returns on investment. It indicates how the reporting entities obtain and spend cash. Besides, the information also covers borrowing and repayment of debt, cash dividends or other cash distributions to investors, and other factors that may affect the entity's liquidity or solvency. It shows the act of managing the financial activities of an organization. Manufacturing companies play a significant role in the economic resource allocation of any countries. They are able to do so because they can generate or earn income to cover their operational cost incurred during the process of economic production. For the manufacturing companies to sustain intermediary role, they need to obtain profit or be profitable and above the intermediation role, the corporate financial performance has critical implications for economic growth of countries.

Quality corporate financial performance rewards the owners (capital providers) for their economic and financial investments, consequentially, encourage additional economic and financial investments which result to economic growth in the countries. Moreover, poor corporate financial performance can lead to companies' financial failures or crisis which can also lead to seizure or liquidation of the company's economic operation which will have negative repercussion on the economic growth and development. The companies' financial performance can be influenced by internal and external factors (Al-Timimi, 2014; Aburime, 2005). These internal factors are (i) size

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of cash flow (ii) labour productivity, (iii) state of information technology, (iv) risk level, (v) management quality, (vi) company size and (vii) ownership structure. The external factors are (i) macroeconomic policy stability, Gross Domestic Product, inflation, interest rate and political instability and in all, incessant chronic corruption in almost the manufacturing companies, especially, Cadbury financial scandal or crisis in 2007

Dimensions of Financial Performance

Some measures of financial performance focus on accounting figures as reported in the annual financial statements of corporate entities. These measures involve the use of one or more accounting ratios to explain how well a firm has achieved its target in a given area and there are also different financial performance measures, such as the return on assets (ROA) which determines an organization's efficiency in the ability to make use of its assets and return on equity (ROE) which reveals the return investors expect to earn on their investments and return on sales (ROS) which reveals how much a company earns in relation to its net turnover. There are four useful measures of profitability and they are; rate of return on assets (ROA), rate of return on equity (ROE), operating profit margin (OPM), and net income (Ahmed et al., 2013). However, liquidity measures the ability of a business to meet up its financial obligations as they fall due. When profitability ratios are computed with the help of investments it is known as return on investment.

There are three different concepts of investments in vogue in financial literature- assets, capital employed and shareholders' equity (Khan & Jain, 2005). According to the available literature, there are three broad categories of return on investment and they are as follows- (i) Return on Assets (ii) Return on Capital Employed (iii) Return on Shareholders' Equity. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, we considered measuring the corporate financial performance using the return on equity alone which is the major part of returns to the capital providers. The measure of corporate financial performance that is considered in this study is discussed below-

Return on Asset (ROA)

This return on asset shows the relationship between net profit after tax and how assets are used in business to generate profits. The return on assets gives an idea as to how efficient management is using its assets to generate earnings. It reveals that what a company can do with what it possesses in terms of its assets. Generally, it is used by companies, banks, financial institutions and other stakeholders for determining of the performance (Rohit, 2014). The return on assets may also be called profit to asset ratio. The returns on assets indicate the profitability position of the firm with respect to assets employed in the business. This measures the relationship between net profit and assets of a firm. It is also known as profit to assets ratio. Assets may be as total assets, fixed assets

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and tangible assets, and any type to be used will depend on the purpose for the calculation. The basis of calculation that underestimates the value of return on total assets as interest paid to creditors is excluded is demonstrated. Return on Asset is one of the most important profitability ratios and indicates management performance regarding firm's resources and assets calculated by dividing net profit by total assets.

Calculating accounting profit considering the price volatility may make difficult decision making for firm's performance evaluation. However, recent year's economy situation has changed management performance measurement evaluation. One of management performance measurement evaluation is Return on Asset. Return on Asset evaluates firm's ability in profit making according to total investments in assets. The term return on assets (ROA) refers to a financial ratio that indicates how profitable a company is in relation to its total assets. Corporate management, analysts, and investors can use ROA to determine how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate a profit. The metric is commonly expressed as a percentage by using a company's net income and its average assets. A higher ROA means a company is more efficient and productive at managing its balance sheet to generate profits while a lower ROA indicates there is room for improvement (Rohit, 2014).

Earnings per Share

The earnings per share reveal the correlation between net profit after tax and preference dividend to number of outstanding equity shares. Earnings per share are good determinants of profitability. It exhibits a significant function in determining the market price of equity shares. It reveals the ability of the company to pay dividend to its shareholders. It defines the cash generating ability of the firm. It is computed by adding non-cash expenses, such as depreciation and amortization with net profit available. An earnings per share is a determinant that indicates to the investors about the profit derived from the money invested by them (shareholders) (Ejoh & Ejom, 2014). It also determines the profitability of shareholders' investment and reveals the net income as a proportion of the shareholders' investment. Earning is a fundamental and prominent accounting variable when it comes to the investigation of the relevance of accounting information.

This is due to its superiority over cash flow in this respect. However, the market will for both cash flow and net book value, if the earnings figures are perceived to be inadequate (Amudo & Inanga, 2012). The earnings per share which is a parameter that can be used to measure the earnings ability of firms is required to be disclosed by companies quoted or about to be quoted in the public security market (Arwinge, 2013). Earnings per share are also known as net income per share is a market prospect ratio that determines the amount net income earned per share of stock outstanding. Reversely, this is the amount every share of stock would receive if all the profits were distributed to the outstanding shares at the end of the period; it is computed to indicate how profitable a company is on a shareholder basis. Even today, EPS is considered to be the single most popular,

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widely used financial performance benchmark of all. Graham, Harvey and Rajgopal, (2004) surveyed 400 financial executives in the USA and reported that the majority, by far, were of the opinion that earnings were the most important performance measure they report to outsiders. EPS is also the linchpin undergirding strategic decision making like share valuations, management performance incentive schemes and merger and acquisition negotiations. EPS is simple to calculate and easily understood and management is congratulated when there is positive EPS growth.

Cash flow theory

Jensen., (1986). The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on the free cash flow theory. The proponent of the free cash flow theory is Jensen., (1986). This theory is of the view that dangerously high debt levels will increase value, despite the threat of financial distress, when a firm's operating cash flow significantly exceeds its profitable investment opportunities. The free cash flow theory is designed for mature firms that are prone to over invest (Jensen., 1986). The free cash flow model implies that for an over-investor, an increase in leverage should lead to a reduction in unprofitable investment spending. Additional leverage does not significantly affect the overall level of internal funds, but rather tightens the control and improves the efficiency of investments (Harbula., 2001). This theory presents debt primarily as a measure of control, and not as a source of funds, as debt acts to restrict managers' ability to pursue unprofitable projects that do not increase investor wealth. Therefore, to achieving the aim and objectives of the study, the researcher decided to anchor the study on this particular theory because it also advocates that sourcing of fund by corporate manufacturing companies should involve the debt instruments and not only from equity or share capital because it encourages the management or the managers to efficiently and effectively utilize the accumulated cash flow because it makes them reduce the intention of investing in unprofitable projects having known that there is debts which conforms to the cash flow management, thereby, ensuring quality financial performance of the listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria or otherwise.

Empirical Review.

Soet et al. (2018), investigated the effect of operating cash flow management on financial performance of mutual funds in Kenya. The study employed causal research. Secondary panel data from the audited financial statements of 22 mutual funds were retrieved from financial reports for the period 2011-201 as a sample size. The p-value at 5% level of confidence for each t-test was used to make conclusions on whether to accept or reject the null hypotheses. The study found out that operating cash flow management had significant and positive effect on return on assets and insignificant and positive effect on return on equity.

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Kinyanjui et al, (2017), investigated the effect of cash management practices (cash holding practices, use of technology and cash pooling practices) as well as analyzed the combined effect of the cash management practices on financial performance of SMEs in Nyeri town, Kenya. The study employed a descriptive research design with target population being the registered SMEs in Nyeri town. Data was collected using a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire from a sample population of 62 SMEs operating in Nyeri town and registered by the business registrar's office in Nyeri County. Data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) to generate descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that cash holding practices and use of technology in cash management had a relevant effect on financial performance of SMEs in Nyeri.

Afrifa, and Tingbani (2017) conducted a study on the relationship between working capital management (WCM) and SMEs' performance by taking into consideration the plausible effect of cash flow. The study adopted a panel data regression analysis on a sample of 802 British quoted small and medium enterprises listed on the alternative investment Market for the period from 2004 to 2013. The results of the study demonstrated the importance of cash flow on SMEs' WCM and performance. According to the findings, WCM has a significant negative impact on SME performance. Additionally, the evidence reveals that cash flow constrained (non-constrained) SMEs are able to enhance their performance through decreased (increased) investment in working capital.

Ogbonnaya et al. (2016), investigated the relationship between cash flow and performance in the Banking sector of Nigeria. The study involved a survey of four (4) Banks quoted in the Nigeria Stock Exchange. Data were obtained from the annual report and accounts of selected Banks. The data were subjected to statistical analysis using correlation technique. The result of the study revealed that operating cash flow has a significant and strong positive relation with performance in the Banking sector in Nigeria, it was also identified that investing cash flow and financing cash flow have negative and weak relationship. The study recommends that regulatory authorities such as CBN, SEC, CAC and NDIC should be securitizing their financial statement and also external auditors of the quoted Banks in the Banking sector to use cash flow ratio in evaluating performance which will help investors make good decisions.

Kim and Kross, (2005), ascertained the capacity of past earnings to predict future cash flows over the period (1973-2000). They used time-series and cross-sectional regressions. Their results show that in one-year-ahead predictions of operating cash flows, current earnings perform better than current operating cash flows.

Methodology

The population for this study embraces the current eleven listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). To achieve the aim of this study, seven listed food and beverage manufacturing companies were selected using the purposive sampling and convenience sampling techniques. The research design was cross sectional using time series data from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) 2010-2021. The simple ordinary least square regression was used for the empirical analysis by the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.

Data Analysis/Results.

Univariate Analysis

In Table 4.1 below for the descriptive statistics of the study variables which is aiding in improving the assimilation of the distinctive characteristics of the dimension in the cross-sectional and time series data. The observations were 84, while the descriptive statistics include mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis, these statistics helped to demonstrate the distributions of the data over the sample period. The variables are operating cash flow management (OPCM) as independent variable measure and return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS) as dependent variable measures of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.1

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
				Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Operating Cash Flow Management	84	6.182594	3.3033511	-3.505	.263	11.348	.520
Return on Asset	84	.414405	1.4255080	5.589	.263	32.603	.520
Earnings Per Share	84	2.074048	3.1418409	1.485	.263	3.414	.520
Valid N (listwise)	84						

Source: SPSS Version, 25

Table 4.1 reveals the descriptive statistics of the study variables which aids in ascertaining the characteristics of the different variables in the historical data. The observations were 84, while the descriptive statistics include mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis, these statistics aided to indicate the distributions of the data. The variables are OCFM, ROA, and EPS. Table 4.1 above indicated that the mean of OCFM, ROA, and EPS. The mean values are: 6.182594, 0.414405 and 2.074048 all through are relatively to the sampled cash flow management and financial performance of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange.

As we compare two principal study variables, specifically: ROA and EPS (dependent measures), the OCFM, ROA, and EPS revealed variability (their SD =3.30333511, 1.4255080 and 3.1418409); where SD is standard deviation. The three variables were negatively and positively skewed (-3.505,5589 and 1.485). As a consequence, OCFM gathered under or below the mean while ROA and EPS gathered above the mean estimate rather than below the mean estimate.

Besides, the kurtosis coefficients of the variables are above the average kurtosis of 3. Therefore, considering the kurtosis and skewness statistics values are above 3. Therefore, the collinearity tests in built in regression analysis (Durbin Watson and Variance Inflation factor) showed that there was no multicollinearity or auto correlation among the variables warranted further regression analysis of the study.

Data Analysis/Results. Test of Null Hypothesis (HO₁, HO₂ & HO₃)

Table 4.2 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.052 ^a	.003	-.009	1.4322111	2.165

a. Predictors: (Constant), Operating Cash Flow Management

b. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset

Table 4.3 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.461	1	.461	.225	.637 ^b
	Residual	168.201	82	2.051		
	Total	168.662	83			

a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset

b. Predictors: (Constant), Operating Cash Flow Management

Table 4.4 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics

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	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.275	.333		.825	.412		
Operating Cash Flow Management	.023	.048	.052	.474	.637	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset

Model 1 Estimates and their Interpretation

Applying the historical data in simple ordinary regression analysis statistical approach, the result indicated that R Squared (R^2) in Table 4.1 above as the coefficient of correlation squared, that represents the proportion of variance in the return on asset (ROA) explained by simultaneous inclusion of the predictor, which is the proportion of variance in ROA accounted for by model 1, the model being the regression of ROA on the linearity of OCFM. R^2 of 0.003 in the simple regression analysis above showed that OCFM in linearity regression predicted ROA. The R^2 indicated that about 3% of the variance of ROA is explained by its linear relationship with the one predictor measure in this analysis. OCFM in linearity regression does not significantly predict ROA at 97%. The Variance Inflation Factor and Durbin Watson in built in regression model showed that there is no multi-collinearity autocorrelation among the variables and that makes the variables suitable for the regression analysis. In table 4.4, the simple ordinary regression showed that OCFM has a coefficient value as 0.25 and the p-value is 0.412 above the level of significance which means that OCFM has insignificant relationship with ROA. Therefore, we reject the alternate hypothesis which states that there is significant relationship between OCFM and ROA of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Table 4.5 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.157 ^a	.025	.013	3.1215471	1.837

a. Predictors: (Constant), Operating Cash Flow Management

b. Dependent Variable: Earnings Per Share

Table 4.6 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.294	1	20.294	2.083	.153 ^b
	Residual	799.013	82	9.744		
	Total	819.307	83			

a. Dependent Variable: Earnings Per Share

b. Predictors: (Constant), Operating Cash Flow Management

Table 4.7 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.149	.726		1.582	.118		
Operating Cash Flow Management	.150	.104	.157	1.443	.153	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Earnings Per Share

Source: SPSS Version, 25

Model 1 Estimates and their Interpretation

Applying the historical data in simple ordinary regression analysis statistical approach, the result indicated that R Squared (R^2) in Table 4.5 above as the coefficient of correlation squared, that represents the proportion of variance in the return on asset (ROA) explained by simultaneous inclusion of the predictor, which is the proportion of variance in ROA accounted for by model 1, the model being the regression of EPS on the linearity of OCFM. R^2 of 0.025 in the simple regression analysis above showed that OCFM in linearity regression predicted EPS. The R^2 indicated that about 3% (approximately) of the variance of EPS is explained by its linear relationship with the one predictor measure in this analysis. OCFM in linearity regression does not significantly predict EPS at 97%. The Variance Inflation Factor and Durbin Watson in built in regression model showed that there is no multi-collinearity autocorrelation among the variables and that makes the variables suitable for the regression analysis. In table 4.7, the simple ordinary regression showed that OCFM has a coefficient value as 0.150 and the p-value is 0.153 above the 0.05 level of significance which means that OCFM has insignificant relationship with EPS. Therefore, we reject the alternate hypothesis which states that there is significant relationship

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between OCFM and EPS of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the relationship between cash flow management (OCFM) and financial performance of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange. From the study empirical findings, the outcomes revealed that operating cash flow management (OCFM) has insignificant relationship with return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS). This is the major source of the listed food and beverage manufacturing companies to finance their economic production of goods and services efficiently and effectively in order to sustain and enhance their financial performance on behalf of the capital providers, but in this case, there is no significant relationship with the manufacturing firms' financial performance. This could be asymmetric information perpetrated by the management concerning the company's total assets and earnings accrued due to ineffective and efficient utilization of the stated productive resources.

Conclusions

The study investigated the relationship between cash flow management and financial performance of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange using operating cash flow management (OCFM) as dimension of cash flow management (independent variable), while return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS) as dimensions of financial performance of listed food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange. From the empirical results, the researcher concluded that operating cash flow management (OCFM) has insignificant relationship with return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS). This could be due to the hidden information concerning the total assets and obtained earnings or profit due to the satisfaction of the managers of manufacturing companies' selfish interests at the expense of the shareholders.

Recommendations

1. The entire management should raise a solid policy framework that will forestall transparency in the management team by strengthening their internal control mechanism in order to minimize the chances of asymmetric information perpetrated by the managers.
2. The management and utilization of the total assets and earnings or profits obtained should be taken seriously, so that operating cash flow management will correlate to an improvement of the manufacturing companies' financial performance in Nigeria.

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